
D2.4 / Updated report on domain review and datasets

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List of abbreviations

18F-FP-CIT PET	18F-fluorinated N-3-fluoropropyl-2-beta-carboxymethoxy-3-beta-(4-iodophenyl) nortropane (18F-FP-CIT) positron emission tomography (PET)
ADL	Activities of daily living
aHR	Adjusted hazard ratio
AI	Artificial intelligence
ALC	Acute Levodopa Challenge
AMP-PD	Accelerating Medicines Partnership: Parkinson's Disease
AUC	Area Under the Curve
AUPRS	Area Under the Precision Recall Curve
AUPRS	Area Under the Precision Recall Curve
BDI	Beck Depression Inventory
BIDI-II	Beck Depression Inventory II
BJLOT	Benton Judgment of Line Orientation Test
BMI	Body mass index
BN	Bayesian network
CDR SB	Clinical dementia rating sum of boxes
CE-mark	Conformité Européenne
CF	Chronic Treated
CI	Coefficient interval
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COURAGE-PD	Comprehensive Unbiased Risk Factor Assessment for Genetics and Environment in Parkinson's
CSF	Cerebrospinal Fluid
CV	Cross Validation
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
DA	Dopamine agonists
DAT	Dopamine transporter (DAT) imaging
dBM	Digital Biomarker
DL	Deep learning
DDS	Dopamine-dysregulation syndrome
DIGPD	Drug Interaction with Genes in Parkinson's Disease
DMLF	Dense Multi-Layer Perceptron
DT	Decision Tree
EMG	Electromyography

ESS	Epworth Sleepiness Scale
ET	Essential tremor
EUROHIS-QOL8	8-item global quality of life questionnaire
EuroQol	European harmonization of the measurement of health-related quality of life
FD	Functional dependency
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FedAvg	Federated Averaging
FoG	Freezing of gait
GDS	Global Deterioration Scale
GeDS	Geriatric Depression Scale
GLSLM	General Least Squares Linear Model
GRS	Genetic Risk Score
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Study
H&Y	Hoehn and Yahr Scale
HADS	Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale
HbA1c	Glycated haemoglobin
HC	Healthy controls
HR	Hazard ratio
HRQL	Health-related quality of life
HVLT	Hopkins Verbal Learning Test
HY	Hoehn and Yahr Scale
ICBs	Impulse control behaviors
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision
IH	Idiopathic Hyposmia
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IPDG	International Parkinson's Disease Genomics Consortium
IPD	Idiopathic Parkinson Disease
iRBD	idiopathic REM sleep behaviour disorder
KASP	Kompetitive Allele Specific Polymerase
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbors
LABS-PD	The Longitudinal and Biomarker Study in PD
LADS	Leeds Hospital Anxiety & Depression Scale
LASSO	Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator
LEDD	Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose

LGBM	Light Gradient Boosting Machine
LID	Levodopa Induced Dyskinesia
LOSO	Leave One Subject Out
LR	Logistic Regression
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MCI	Mild cognitive impairment
MDS	Movement Disorders Society
ML	Machine learning
MMNS	Mild motor-non-motor subtype
MMSE	Mini Mental State Examination
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MR	Mendelian Randomization
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
M5F	M5 model trees
MS	Motor symptoms
NA	Noradrenaline
NB	Naive Bayes
NMS	Non-motor symptoms
NN	Neural Network
NPI	Neuropsychiatric Inventory
OD	Olfactive dysfunction
OR	Odds ratio
PCRLDR	Multiplex polymerase chain reaction-ligase detection reaction method
PD	Parkinson Disease
PD-CRS	Parkinson's Disease Cognitive Rating Scale
PD-DH	Dualhit in PD
PD-MCI	Parkinson Disease Mild Cognitive Impairment
PDQ-39	39 item Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire
PDQ8	Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire
PDSS	Parkinson's Sleep Scale
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PHS	Polygenic Hazard Score
PIGD	Postural Instability Gait Difficulty
PKG	Personal KinetiGraph
PPMI	Parkinson's Progression Marker Initiative

PQ-10	Rating of global perceived QoL (PQ-10) on a scale from 0 (worst) to 10 (best)
PSD	Power Spectral Density
PRS	Polygenic Risk Scores
QoL	Quality of life
QUIP	Questionnaire for Impulsive Compulsive Disorder
RBD	Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder
RBDQ-HK	RBD Questionnaire-Hong Kong
RBDSQ	REM Sleep Disorder Questionnaire
RF	Random Forest
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROMP	Radboud Oral Motor Inventory for Parkinson's Disease
RPE	Rate of perceived exertion
RR	Relative risk
S&E	Schwab and England Scale
S&E-ADLS	Schwab and England Activities of Daily Living Scale
SCD	Subjective Cognitive Decline
SCOPA-AUT	Scale for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease for Autonomic symptoms
SDM	Symbol Digit Modalities
SPECT	Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography
SMNS	Severe motor-non-motor subtype
SNCA	Synuclein Alpha gene
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
STAI	State Trait Anxiety Inventory
SVM	Support Vector Machine
T2DM	Type 2 diabetes mellitus
TD	Tremor dominant
TUAG	Timed Up and Go Test
UA	Uric Acid
UPDRS	Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
UPSIT	University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test
VAS	Visual analogue scales
VIPD-Q	Visual disturbances in patients with Parkinson's Disease questionnaire
WES	Whole-Exome Sequencing
WGS	Whole-Genome Sequencing

Executive summary

This deliverable D2.4 meets the project's objectives by constituting the final version of the domain review and accessed datasets report, following the preliminary document deliverable D2.3. The D2.4 presents the literature review performed to delineate the State-of-the-Art to date in predicting Parkinson's disease (PD) risk, PD progression and response to medication. It thus includes all relevant articles covering the past 12 years of research dedicated to PD (1/1/2013-1/2/2025). The main focus of D2 this updated report was to review advances in the state of the art that occurred between 1/1/2024 and 1/2/2025. It also summarizes the relevant digital technologies that are currently available both in Europe and America to monitor movement and balance in PD patients. Based on the literature review findings and the available digital technologies, we have requested access to various datasets and biobanks containing health, digital, lifestyle and genetic information. A detailed final list is outlined in the current document. Additionally, harmonisation and curation techniques to be employed on these datasets are presented.

During this period, regarding PD risk, population studies focusing on incident PD using Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven approaches confirm that accelerometer-based features effectively predict the risk to develop PD. Genetic research has identified 31 new single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), five genetic segments, and three polygenic risk scores (PRSs) linked to PD risk, while research on REM Sleep Behaviour disorder (RBD) detection and daytime somnolence, two established clinical biomarkers of early non motor PD symptoms, remains limited, highlighting an important gap in the literature. Conclusions are presented separately in each section.

Regarding updates on PD progression and medication response, new research reveals some clinical predictors of levodopa-induced dyskinesia (LID) including axial symptoms, freezing of gait, and rigidity, and some non-motor symptoms such as co-morbid impulse control behaviours and apathy. New genetic variants influencing both progression and medication response have been identified. AI-driven approaches for modelling disease progression incorporate repeated clinical assessments over time, enabling sequential prediction of cognitive decline, identification of motor subtypes based on progression trajectories, and multivariate modelling of UPDRS-III changes.

As far as new digital technologies, two devices have been approved by the FDA for PD monitoring (NeuroRPM and Nush Smart Shoes). In the past year we have gained access to two new data sets to help develop AI risk models (UK Biobank and ILON) and four new data sets to monitor PD progression and response to treatment (Opisleep, Bial BIPANK I and II, Capture 14 and NTD Dataset).

This updated report highlights the significant progress in understanding and predicting PD risk, progression and response to treatment. The integration of clinicodemographic information, lifestyle factors, genetic and digital biomarkers, key knowledge gaps are now addressed. Novel approaches to pre-process and analyse the data using advanced AI techniques are identified and presented. This knowledge paves the way for more targeted and sophisticated model developments under the prism of AI-PROGNOSIS.

1 Introduction

This deliverable D2.4 is the final version of the Datasets and Domain Review of the Horizon Europe AI-PROGNOSIS project. This is the updated version of Deliverable D2.3 and adds all the relevant articles regarding the state of the art in PD risk and PD progression and medication response published during 1/1/2024-1/2/2025. It also includes all the newly accessed datasets (identified between January 2024 and February 2025) and adds the recently (commenced after 2024) approved digital technology, helping to extend and complete the previous version.

The objectives of this deliverable are:

- To provide an extensive domain review regarding the current state-of-the-art (SoA) in assessing Parkinson's Disease (PD) risk based on clinically-driven models and digital biomarkers (dBM) and point out research opportunities and challenges,
- To provide an extensive domain review regarding the current SoA in monitoring and predicting PD progression and medication response based on data-driven models and dBM and point out research opportunities and challenges,
- To provide an updated review of FDA- or CE-approved digital technologies currently used to monitor PD.
- To delineate pertinent, multi-source datasets from AI-PROGNOSIS partners or third-party (large-scale) databases/biobanks/cohorts that include long-term follow-ups of people with PD and incident cases. This final updated list comprises datasets that have been accessed and assessed for quality according to the established framework. To describe how these datasets have been stratified by utility for R&D within the AI-PROGNOSIS project objectives: PD risk, REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) detection, and monitoring of PD progression and medication response,
- To describe how the data have been sanitised, debiased, munged, and harmonised using a common data model, following established standards and clinical knowledge for the standardisation of representations of multi-site outcome assessments.

1.1 Document scope

This document constitutes the final version of the review performed within the scope of the Horizon Europe AI-PROGNOSIS project. It is designated as deliverable D2.4 "Updated report on domain review and datasets" and is submitted in Month 25. It follows the deliverable D2.3 "Initial report on domain review and datasets", scheduled for submission in Month 10. Both documents are integral to Task 2.1 "Domain and data landscape review" under Work Package (WP2) "Foundation, data curation and co-creation". This updated report provides the building blocks for AI and dBM development in WP3 "Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response".

1.2 Document structure

This document is structured into four principal sections after a brief introduction. Section 2 presents two domain reviews of the current SoA in the assessment of clinical, demographic, and lifestyle variables, genetic associations, data-driven approaches, and digital tracking for a) PD risk and b) PD progression and medication response. The references cited in document D2.3, along with the updated references covering the update period, both for PD risk and for PD progression, are listed at the end of the document. Section 3 outlines the currently available and validated digital technologies used for PD monitoring. Section 4 describes the third-party open datasets that have been accessed by the consortium and their utility for the project, as

well as the datasets that have been declined after request. Section 4 describes the dataset harmonisation and curation process. All literature tables display new entries (pertaining to the period 1/1/2024-1/2/2025) at the top, with D2.3 entries listed at the bottom.

2 Literature review

2.1 Search methodology, outline, and definitions

To support this objective, two literature searches were initially conducted for articles published between 1/2013-1/2024 (as reported in D2.3). For this updated report, two further searches were performed to cover articles published from 1/1/2024 to 1/2/2025. Searches were conducted across three databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. We followed the same methodology as for the previous deliverable.

Briefly:

- The first literature search aimed to capture all relevant articles pertaining to clinical and genetic approaches to predict PD risk and monitor disease progression and response to treatment that could be relevant for our project.
- The second literature search aimed to capture all relevant articles regarding AI-driven methodologies and digital assessments used to monitor PD risk and PD disease progression monitoring and response to treatment.
- We included all articles found in a common Rayyan database (<https://www.rayyan.ai>) to be used by all consortium partners.
- The two SoA reviews were divided into subsections (i) PD risk, (ii) PD progression and response to medication. Each subsection was assigned to two consortium partners based on their area of expertise. Each author accessed both Rayyan databases to select the relevant articles for their topic based on keywords and abstract/title searches as detailed below. When deemed necessary, authors added other search strategies as explained below.

This updated review presents all relevant articles published between 1/1/2013-1/2/2025, to give the reader a complete SoA in the assessment of clinical, demographic, and lifestyle variables, genetic associations, data-driven approaches, and digital tracking for a) PD risk and b) PD progression and medication response.

2.1.1 Clinical and genetic assessment approaches

We performed the same bibliographic search as for our previous deliverable, aiming to identify the clinical and genetic assessment approaches to investigate PD risk and PD progression and medication response. The search terms used were: (“Parkinson Disease” OR Parkinson*) AND (“Risk factors” OR “treatment outcome” OR “disease progression” AND (“machine learning” OR “big data” OR “algorithms” OR “automatic data processing” OR “biomarker” OR “surveys” OR “disease monitoring”) AND (“olfaction” OR “hyposmia” OR “REM sleep behaviour disorder” OR “daytime somnolence” OR “tremor” OR “rigidity” OR “bradykinesia” OR “posture” OR “balance” OR “falls” OR “freezing” OR “cognition” OR “dementia” OR “cognition” OR “gene” OR “genetics” OR “genome” OR “dyskinesia”).

The updated search yielded 6877 (65 PubMed, 6659 Scopus, 153 Web of Science) references that were included in a Rayyan database (**Figure 1**). The initial search can be found in **Figure 2**.

After exclusion of duplicates, 4789 articles remained. The number of duplicates is high because Scopus, PubMed, and Web of Science found the same papers, and Scopus has a much larger number because it is broader and includes more technical papers. There are additional records identified through other sources; especially for the genetic assessment as described below: GWAS catalogue (1), and citation searching (1).

We proceeded to filter these articles by excluding all articles that were not in English and had the keywords rats, mice, cells, case reports; and by including all articles containing in the title or abstract: Parkinson* AND Machine learning OR artificial intelligence; Parkinson* AND REM OR RBD OR Sleep OR somnolence OR tremor OR dyskinesias OR rigidity OR bradykinesia OR slowness OR motor OR limb OR posture OR balance OR falls OR freezing OR cognition OR dementia OR cognitive OR dysexecutive OR amnesia OR memory and Parkinson* AND gene OR genetic OR DNA OR SNP OR GWAS. This reduced the number of possibly relevant references to 861. The rest of the search strategy is described in each subtopic below in the Results section.

Figure 1 PRISMA flow chart clinical and genetic bibliographic search (1/1/2024-1/2/2025)

*After excluding by automation tools with the keyword's: "rats", "mice", "cells", "case reports", "no-randomized", "survey", "cross-sectional", and "case control"

** Full text was read to confirm eligibility

** Excluded, with reasons: wrong population, wrong publication type, wrong intervention. Described below for each subtopic

***Described below for each subtopic

Figure 2 PRISMA flow chart clinical and genetic bibliographic search (1/2013-1/2024)

*After excluding by automation tools with the keyword's: ‘rats’, ‘mice’, ‘cells’, ‘case reports’, ‘no-randomized’, ‘survey’, ‘cross-sectional’, and ‘case control’

** Full text was read to confirm eligibility

** Excluded, with reasons: wrong population, wrong publication type, wrong intervention. Described below for each subtopic

***Described below for each subtopic

2.1.2 AI-driven and digital approaches

We performed the same bibliographic search as for the previous deliverable, aiming to identify the relevant articles describing AI-driven and digital approaches for identifying PD risk and monitoring PD progression and medication response. The search terms used were: (Parkinson Disease OR Parkinson*) AND (Artificial intelligence OR AI OR “computational intelligence” OR “machine intelligence” OR “machine learning”) AND (“Digital Technology” OR “Wearable Electronic Devices” OR “Smartphone” OR accelerometer* OR app OR apps OR “assistive device*” OR “assistive technolog*” OR device* OR “digital health” OR “digital biomarker*” OR “digital phenotyp*” OR ehealth OR e-health OR “electronic health” OR eyetracking OR facetracking OR handtracking OR “health tech*” OR mhealth OR m-health OR “mobile application*” OR “mobile health” OR monitoring OR motiontracking OR selfmonitoring OR selftracking OR sensor OR sensors OR smart-phone* OR smartphone* OR smart-watch* OR smartwatch* OR tracking OR wearable*).

This search yielded 4871 references (374 PubMed, 3927 Scopus, 570 Web of Science) that were included in a second Rayyan database. There are additional records identified through citation searching (**Figure 3**). The initial search can be found in **Figure 4**. After duplicate exclusion, there were 4033 references. After including all articles containing in title or abstract:

Parkinson AND artificial intelligence OR artificial intelligence OR AI OR computational intelligence OR machine intelligence OR machine learning OR Digital Technology OR Wearable OR Smartphone OR accelerometer OR app OR apps OR assistive device OR “assistive technology OR digital health OR digital biomarker OR ehealth OR e-health OR mhealth OR m-health OR monitoring OR sensor OR sensors OR smartwatch OR tracking OR wearable, a total of 544 possibly relevant references were identified. Both the data driven/clinical Rayyan database and the ML/dBM database were further filtered by the clinical and technical partners in the consortium regarding the different sections of the reviews by a more targeted selection of keywords, as described in more detail in the Results section below, under each topic.

Figure 3 PRISMA flow chart for wearable sensors and AI-driven methodologies bibliographic search (1/2024-2/2025).

*After excluding by automation tools with the keyword's: "rats", "mice", "cells", "case reports", "no-randomized", "survey", "cross-sectional", and "case control"

** Full text was read to confirm eligibility

** Excluded, with reasons: wrong population, wrong publication type, wrong intervention. Described below for each subtopic

***Described below for each subtopic

Figure 4 PRISMA flow chart for wearable sensors and AI-driven methodologies bibliographic search (1/2013-1/2024).

*After excluding by automation tools with the keyword's: "rats", "mice", "cells", "case reports", "no-randomized", "survey", "cross-sectional", and "case control"

** Full text was read to confirm eligibility

** Excluded, with reasons: wrong population, wrong publication type, wrong intervention. Described below for each subtopic

***Described below for each subtopic

2.2 Parkinson's disease risk

2.2.1 Introduction

For the AI-PROGNOSIS project, this review aims to investigate the diagnostic value of demographic, lifestyle and clinical factors, as well as genetic factors and dBMs associated with PD risk and prodromal PD. Furthermore, our project aims to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of dBMs developed using accelerometers that have gained popularity in movement disorders research. For genetic markers we particularly focus beyond the monogenic forms of PD considering common genetic variants with low individual strength, but cumulative predictive effect that can be calculated into a PRS. For the multisource data to provide meaningful and accurate PD risk assessments, AI applications are crucial. We hence reviewed the most common AI-driven approaches for identifying people at risk of developing PD, as well as the digital assessments of two of the well-established prodromal clinical risk factors of PD: RBD and daytime somnolence.

According to the current classification of PD, we can divide the disease in three stages: 1) preclinical PD, where the neurodegenerative processes has started, but there are no detectable symptoms or signs; 2) prodromal PD, where non motor or/and motor symptoms

and signs are present, but not sufficiently to reach the defining features of the disease (this phase can last years to decades and indicates the slowly progressive spread of PD pathology); and 3) clinical PD, where the diagnosis can be made based on the classic motor signs (Berg and Postuma, 2014). Currently there is ongoing debate within the movement disorders community regarding the biological definition, classification and staging of PD. This may better define the initial stages of the disease for research purposes, based on biological biomarkers such as synuclein assays, genetics and neuroimaging (Cardoso and Goetz, 2024; Hoglinger and Adler 2024; Simuni and Chaline 2024).

The clinical risk markers for developing PD are currently demographic factors such as age, sex, family history of PD or genetic background (known gene mutation or polygenic risk score), lifestyle factors such as regular exposure to pesticides or occupational solvents, physical inactivity, non-use of caffeine or never having smoked and pre-existing conditions such as diabetes mellitus, bipolar disease, and low plasma urate levels (Heinzel et al., 2019). Prodromal PD is defined by some clinical evidence of ongoing neurodegeneration. The currently identified prodromal markers for PD are RBD, reduced striatal dopaminergic innervation as measured with single photon emission tomography (SPECT) or positron emission tomography (PET), presence of neuronal α synuclein (positive α syn assay in CSF or skin biopsy), subthreshold parkinsonism, abnormal quantitative motor testing, olfactory loss, constipation, excessive daytime somnolence, orthostatic hypotension, erectile and urinary dysfunction, depression and a global cognitive deficit.

We present the literature review methodology and results for each section below. This is the updated version of the report to cover 2024 through early 2025.

2.2.2 Clinical, demographic, and lifestyle factors associated with PD risk

Study selection

The search was performed within the Rayyan clinical and genetic assessments bibliography using the following combination of search terms: 'diabetes' OR 'uric acid' OR 'demographic' OR 'age' OR 'sex' OR 'lifestyle' OR 'urban' OR 'rural' OR 'pesticides' OR 'employment' OR 'exercise' OR 'diet' alongside "risk" and "prodromal.". **Table 1** outlines the selection criteria for investigating the risk of developing PD in health populations or PD phenoconversion in prodromal populations, based on demographic, clinical, or lifestyle factors. Cross-sectional studies and review articles were excluded. A total of 26 studies were found following these selection criteria and screened by three independent reviewers. Six relevant studies were added to the 27 from the previous search.

Table 1 Selection criteria for clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD Risk

Item	Definition
Population	General healthy populations or prodromal PD populations
Analysis	Incident PD/PD phenoconversion
Results	Clinical, demographic or lifestyle variables

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	105	26	129
Articles included in literature table	27	6	33

Study characteristics

Among the 33 articles, **Table 2** summarizes each article by date of publication (most recent first), all considered demographic variables except one (Skaramagkas 2023), all focused on clinical variables except 2 (Power 2023 and Venkatesan D 2021), 10 focused on lifestyle variables (Bazo-Alvarez, Jacobs 2020, Kang 2023, Noyce 2017, Schrag 2023, Sood 2023, Terracia 2023, Venkatesan D, Postuma 2015, Zhang 2022). Most were observational cohorts, except 5 case control studies (Park et al., 2022; Song et al., 2020; Shrag et al., 2023; Xiang et al., 2023, Bazo-Alvarez 2024). Time of follow up ranged from 3-47 years. There were 23 general population studies, most of them following large cohorts (range 146-938.635) through health registries longitudinally with incident PD as the main outcome. Some of them (Doun et al., 2022; Marini et al., 2020; Noyce 2017; Park 2022; Sharamagkgas 2023; Sood 2023, Koo Y 2025) used predictive algorithms to determine clinical, demographic and lifestyle variables associated with risk of developing PD.

Ten studies investigated prodromal PD populations, most of them focused on RBD, while one study looked at essential tremor patients and 2 considered people with hyposmia. These studies were smaller, with a sample size ranging from 36-1160 people.

Clinical, demographical and lifestyle factors

General population studies investigated clinical non-motor symptoms associated with PD, such as hyposmia, RBD, distressing dreams, sleep and fatigue, affective disorders, subjective cognitive decline, and dysautonomic symptoms, while others looked at prodromic motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, walking pace or tapping speed. Some studies investigated the association of PD with other diseases, such mental disorders (anxiety, depression, bipolar disease), hyperuricemia, hypertension, stroke, dislipemia and diabetes mellitus. Many cohorts focused on lifestyle factors, such as smoking, caffeine and alcohol intake, religiosity, physical activity, and demographic factors, such as age and sex, body mass index, profession, and socioeconomic status.

Table 2 Studies about clinical (C), demographic (D) and lifestyle (L) factors associated with PD risk.

Author/Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
A. Population studies							
Bazo-Alvarez JC et al., 2024	C,D,L	10	Non anxiety cohort (878,256) Anxiety cohort (109,435)	Investigate if anxiety is a risk factor for developing PD, controlling for other C,D,L factors	Used the IQVIA Medical Research Database database, which includes de-identified data from The Health Improvement Network (THIN), a large UK primary care dataset. Within THIN, all people aged >50 y/o who were registered with participating practice between 2008- 2018 and had ≥1 anxiety record in GP database after ≥1 year of no previous records of anxiety were identified and age/sex matched to 4 HC. Weibull survival regression models were fitted and hazard ratios (HRs) for modelling time-to-PD were estimated. Results adjusted for known D, C and L factors	> 50 year old Healthy controls in UK primary care	In Anxiety cohort, risk of PD increased two-fold compared with the non-anxiety group after adjustment for age, sex, social deprivation, lifestyle factors, severe mental illness, head trauma, and dementia (HR 2.1, 95% confidence interval = 1.9 to 2.4). In group with anxiety: depression, hypotension, tremor, rigidity, balance impairment, constipation, sleep disturbance, fatigue, and cognitive impairment were associated with an increased risk of developing PD.
Guo J et al., 2024	C,D		89330 (52%, mean age: 75.7)	Assess association between Sodium Glucose cotransporter 2(SGLT2) inhibitors and risk of PD in older populations with Type2 Diabetes (T2D).	Medicare claims data from 2016 to 2020 to identify non PD patients with T2D and age ≥65 years. The initiation of an SGLT2 inhibitor was compared with that of a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP4) inhibitor. Outcome was incident PD since date initiating either SGLT2 inhibitor or DPP4 inhibitor. Employed a 1:1 propensity score matching to balance baseline covariates between treatment groups (D, C factors and co-mediations). Cox regression models to assess effect of SGLT2	T2D elderly (>65 year olds)	0.6% (n = 537) had incident PD over the follow-up. SGLT2 inhibitor group was associated with a significantly lower risk of incident PD than the DPP4 inhibitor group (hazard ratio: 0.70 [95% confidence interval: 0.55–0.89]).

Author/ Year	Factors (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
					inhibitors versus DPP4 inhibitors on incident PD.		
Koo Y et al., 2025	C,D	11	820 PD, 8200 age sex matched HC	To Improve performance of deep-learning-based screening for detecting prodromal PD using medical-claims data, including diagnostic and prescription information.	PD diagnosis and HC based on ICD-10 coding. Enrolled patients diagnosed with PD between 2008 and 2010 and aged over 50 years at time of diagnosis. Restricted predictive analysis to participants who had at least one medical record and one diagnostic record for each year during the 6-year prodromal period. Matched to HC by age and sex. A deep-learning algorithm was developed using various combinations of diagnostic codes, medication codes, and prodromal periods.	Korean National Health Insurance Service claims data. Covers 1,025,340 people. (2.2% of the Korean population)	During prodromal period (year-3 to year 0), predicting PD using only diagnostic codes yielded high accuracy of 0.937. For prodromal period (year-6 to year-3), accuracy of PD prediction decreased to 0.890. Inclusion of all medication-codes data increased accuracy to 0.922. Conclusion: A deep-learning algorithm using both prodromal diagnostic and medication codes was effective in screening PD. Developing a surveillance system with automatically collected medical-claims data could be cost-effective.
Xu X et al., 2024	C,D	mean 13.8	501,233 HC (54%, mean age 56.5)	Investigate relationship between Bipolar Disorder (BD) and neurodegenerative diseases: dementia and PD	Follow cohort until incident PD	UK Biobank	Participants with BD had a significantly higher risk of PD (adjusted HR 2.88, 95% CI 2.03-4.08). Findings suggest that up to two-thirds of this association may be mediated by BD-related medications.
Beydou et al., 2022	C,D	14±6	1756	To evaluate sleep and affective (mood/anxiety) disorders as clinical predictors of incident Parkinson's disease (PD) among women ≥65 years of age.	Time-to-event was calculated from baseline (1993–1998) to year of incident PD, loss to follow-up, death, or December 31, 2018, whichever came first.	Women older than 65	Among older women, joint sleep/affective disorders and affective disorders alone are strong clinical predictors of incident PD over 14 years.
Dou et al., 2022	C,D	5	3 models N=609; N=516; N=477	Develop and validate clinical risk models using non-motor predictors to distinguish between early PD and healthy individuals.	Multipredictor modelling to distinguish PD from HC.	PPMI data base	Eight variables: age, gender, family history, UPSIT, MOCA, RBDSQ, alpha synuclein in CSF and SNCA rs356181 polymorphism in model. High accuracy. AUC of 0.93

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
Flores-Torres et al., 2023	C,D	47	12.427	Examine whether subjective cognitive decline (SCD) is more likely to be present in women with features suggestive of prodromal PD (defined as hyposmia, RBD and constipation) compared with women without these features	Biannual self-administered questionnaires about hyposmia, constipation and RBD	Nurse Health Study. The prodromal PD Subgroup	Women experiencing the three examined nonmotor features (hyposmia, constipation, and probable rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder) had the worst mean SCD score and the highest odds of poor subjective cognition
Jacobs et al., 2020	C,D L	12.01	1276 PD 500,406 controls	Investigate the association of clinical, and lifestyle risk factors and prodromal features with incident Parkinson's disease and the interaction of genetic risk with these factors.	Determined association of risk factors with incident PD using adjusted logistic regression models. Constructed polygenic risk scores (PRSs) using external weights and selected the best PRS from a subset of the cohort (30%). The PRS was used in a separate testing set (70%) to examine gene-environment interactions and compare predictive models for PD.	UK Biobank	Evidence of association between PD and a positive family history of PD, a positive family history of dementia, non-smoking, low alcohol consumption, depression, daytime somnolence, epilepsy and earlier menarche. The effect of diabetes on PD risk appears to depend on background genetic risk for PD.
Kang et al., 2023	C,D,L	17	938.635	Investigate the incidence of PD in Korean population by age and year for each sex as well as the modifiable risk factors for PD. Explore the HR and RR for each modifiable risk factor	Chart review by ICD-10 diagnosis of defined modifiable risk factors: hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidaemia, ischemic stroke, haemorrhagic stroke, ischemic heart disease, depression, osteoporosis, obesity, physical activity, smoking and alcohol consumption. End point was PD development	Korean population in National Health service without PD or dementia	1.1% developed PD. Incidence of PD increased with age up to 80 years. Presence of hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidaemia, ischemic stroke, haemorrhagic stroke, ischemic heart disease, depression, osteoporosis, and obesity were independently associated with a higher risk for PD
Liu et al., 2023	C	12.5	419.572	To quantify the association of handgrip strength and self-reported walking pace with incident PD in the general population.	Handgrip measured by dynamometer and gait measured by self-report. Study endpoint was PD diagnosis	General population without PD from UK Biobank	Low handgrip strength and slow walking pace together (HR 2,89 95% CI 2.30-3.65) were significantly associated with a higher risk of incident PD, regardless of the individuals' genetic risk profile

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
Marini et al., 2020	C	10	574	To apply the PREDICT-PD algorithm of risk indicators for PD in a prospective community-based study x representative of the general elderly population	PREDICT-PD risk scores were calculated based on risk factor assessments obtained at baseline. Outcome: incident PD	General elderly (The Bruneck study)	The PREDICT-PD score was associated with an increased risk for incident PD in our sample and may represent a useful first screening step in future algorithms aiming to identify cases of prodromal PD
Noyce et al., 2017	C,D,L	3	1323	To test an online, evidence-based algorithm to identify risk indicators of PD in the UK population.	Participants completed an online survey and keyboard-tapping task annually over 3 years and underwent smell tests and genotyping. Outcomes: incident PD, and intermediate markers of PD: smell loss, RBD score, and slowed tapping speed	UK population	The online PREDICT-PD algorithm is a unique and simple method to identify indicators of PD risk. The predictive power for incident PD was improved by the addition of genetic variants to risk scores.
Otaiku et al., 2023	C,D	50	6991	Investigate the association between distressing dreams in childhood and the risk of developing cognitive impairment or PD by age 50.	Proxy report of distressful dreams (from mother) at age 7 and 11 correlated with incident PD at age 50 (diagnosed by doctor)	British Birth Cohort Study	Having persistent distressing dreams during childhood may be associated with an increased risk (OR 1.85 95% CI 1.1-3.1) of developing cognitive impairment or PD by age of 50.
Otaiku et al., 2023b	C,D,L	8.1	2.672	Investigate whether low religiosity in adulthood is associated with increased risk for developing PD.	Self-report questionnaires on religiosity. Estimated OR for developing PD adjusted for sociodemographic and health factors.	English Longitudinal Study of Aging and the Midlife in US study	Low religiosity in adulthood may be a strong risk factor (OR 9.99 CI 3.28-30.36) for developing PD.
Park et al., 2022	C,D,L	10.4	1.102	PD prediction models using ML algorithms	Chart review of national registry of patients with >5 follow-ups between 2002-2015 investigating C, D and L variables. Endpoint was diagnosis of PD. Machine learning algorithm were applied for PD prediction	National Health Insurance Service-Health Screening datasets group with PD and matched	The most important factor for predicting PD was BMI, followed by total cholesterol, glucose, haemoglobin, and blood pressure levels. Smoking and alcohol consumption (in men) and socioeconomic status, physical activity, and diabetes mellitus (in women) were highly correlated with occurrence of PD

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
						1:1 non-PD cohort	
Power et al., 2023	D	8.3	5.125	Investigation of the association of military employment and PD, because persons with military involvement may be more likely to have PD risk factors.	Self-report or PD prescription refills to identify prevalent and incident cases	Adult changes in thought study	At enrolment 6% of 5,125 eligible participants had military employment and 1.8% had prevalent PD; During follow up 3.5% developed PD. We found no association between military employment and PD
Schrag et al., 2019	C,D	5	8.166	Develop and validate a prediction model for diagnosis of PD based on presentations in primary care.	Multivariate analysis: tremor, constipation, depression or anxiety, fatigue, dizziness, urinary dysfunction, balance problems, memory problems and cognitive decline, hypotension, rigidity, and hypersalivation.	Primary care consultations	The risk algorithm applied to routine primary care presentations can identify individuals at increased risk of diagnosis of PD within 5 years. Also, 99% of those who were not classified as high risk would not be diagnosed with PD
Schrag et al., 2023	C,D,L	6 (SD 2)	138.345 PD 276.690 controls	To identify the association of PD diagnosis with a range of lifestyle factors, comorbidities, and potential extracerebral manifestations of PD.	PD patients and matched controls by age, sex, region and first medical consult. Chart review of risk factors and prodromal features of PD, using the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, Tenth Revision (ICD-10) coding.	General German population using insurance claims of outpatient consultations	Risk factors included traumatic brain injury, odds ratio (OR), 1.62; alcohol misuse, OR, 1.32; hypertension, OR, 1.29; anosmia, OR, 2.16; and parasomnias (including RBD), OR, restless legs syndrome (OR, 4.19), sleep apnoea (OR, 1.45), epilepsy (OR, 2.26), migraine (OR, 1.21), bipolar disorder (OR, 3.81), and schizophrenia (OR, 4.48). Associations even 5 to 10 years before diagnosis included tremor (OR 4.49; 9), restless legs syndrome (OR, 3.73), bipolar disorder (OR, 3.80), and schizophrenia (OR, 4.00).
Skaramagas et al., 2023	C		31 PD and 14 HC	To develop a robust model for accurate PD detection using accelerometer data collected from PD and non-PD individuals with mild or no	The dataset used in this study contains IMU signals captured in the wild via the accelerometer sensor embedded in modern smartphones for the purpose of	PD and HC	The proposed model outperforms existing approaches and holds promise for detection of PD with subtle symptoms, like tremor, in the wild. Such symptoms can present in the early or even prodromal stage of the disease, and

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
				tremor during phone conversations	detecting tremorous episodes related to PD		appropriate mobile-based applications may be a practical tool in real-life settings to alert individuals at risk to seek medical assistance or give patients feedback in monitoring their symptoms.
Song et al., 2020	C,D	5-25	61,748 stress 595,335 matched HC; 44 839 stress 78 482 unaffected siblings	To examine the association between stress-related disorders and risk for neurodegenerative diseases	Matched cohort design. Individuals who received their first diagnosis of stress-related disorders between 1987 and 2008, matched to healthy controls and/or siblings. Followed until 2013. Outcome: Incident PD or other neurodegenerative disease	Swedish National Patient Register.	No statistically significant association was found with stress-related disorders and Parkinson disease
Sood et al., 2023	C,D,L	10	1178 HC and 24 Incident PD	Artificial intelligence (AI) to learn and quantify PD marker interdependencies via a Bayesian network (BN) with probabilistic confidence estimation using bootstrapping	Used prospective data of 18 established risk and prodromal markers of PD in healthy, PD-free individuals and incident PD cases collected longitudinally in 4 visits over up to 10 years.	Tubingen evaluation of Risk factors for Early detection of Neuro Degeneration (TREND) study. PD and HC	Altogether our work demonstrates the potential of modern AI approaches (specifically BNs) both for modelling and understanding interdependencies between PD risk and prodromal markers, which are so far not accounted for in PD prediction models, as well as for generating realistic synthetic data.
Terraccia et al., 2023	C,D,L	15	491 603	To assess whether loneliness is associated with risk of incident PD and whether the association is independent of other risk factors or modified by age, sex, and genetic vulnerability	This large cohort study found that loneliness was associated with risk of incident PD across demographic groups and independent of depression and other prominent risk factors and genetic risk. The findings add to the evidence that loneliness is a substantial psychosocial determinant of health	UK Biobank	2822 developed PD during the 15-year follow-up. Individuals who reported being lonely had a higher risk of PD (hazard ratio [HR], 1.37; 95%CI, 1.25-1.51). Loneliness was associated with risk of incident PD across demographic groups and independent of depression and other prominent risk factors and genetic risk.

Author/Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
Venkatesan D et al., 2021	D,L	5.1 ± 2.0	146 total 73 PD 73 HC	Determine the association of lifestyle, environmental factors, biochemical parameters and genetic insights in Indian population	Standardised questionnaires about environmental factors for PD and age matched controls during 5 years.	Tamil Nadul Indian population HC and PD patients	Smoking, alcohol, caffeinated drinks, occupational influence of agriculture and industry and pesticide exposure had more association with PD occurrence.
B. Prodromal population studies							
Benbir-Senel G. et al., 2024	C,D	8	45 (57.8 %men)	Investigate demographic and neurophysiological factors that predict phenoconversion in an RBD population.	Patients underwent evaluation every 6-12 months for 8 year follow up with: UPDRS part IIISniffin' Sticks Odor Identification Test, Farnsworth-Munsell 100 Hue Color Vision test, Beck Depression Inventory and Rome III Criteria for constipation, polysomnography and heart rate variability (HRV) were analyzed.	RBD >18 y/o Istambul Medical School Hospital	8 patients phenoconverted to PD. Slowing in EEG spectrum power, with age ≥60 years, anosmia and constipation were best predictors of phenoconversion (Odds ratio –122.5 (9.7-1543.8); kappa = 3.051–).
Byun JI et al., 2025	C,D	3.7 ± 2.0	238 (compared to 242)	Compare phenoconversion to PD of Seoul National University Hospital (SNUH) RBD cohort to Montreal RBD cohort	Patients underwent polysomnography for RBD diagnosis. Follow up for atleast 1 year with clinical motor scales. Compared phenoconversion to motor disease in SNUH cohort (N=238) and Montreal cohort (N=242).	RBD patients in Korean National Hospital	N=34 (11.8%) patients in the SNUH cohort converted to degenerative disease: 18 (52.9%) PD, 9 (26.5%) LBD, 7 (20.6%) MSA. Conversion rate in the SNUH cohort was significantly lower than in Montreal cohort (log-rank test, P = .002). Fewer patients in SNUH group than Montreal group converted to LBD (Gray's test P = .001). Conclusions: More investigation needed in racial and geographical factors contributing to such disparities
Froehner GS et al., 2022	C,D	3	36	Evaluate the risk of developing PD based on DAT Scan in ET patients	Underwent clinical assessment (neurological, MDS UPDRS III and Archimedes spiral) and DAT scan at baseline. Clinical assessment after 3 years	Essential tremor patients	Advanced age at the onset of tremor, the presence of bradykinesia, and asymmetrical alterations in SPECT may be related to progression to PD in patients with ET

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
Joza et al., 2023	C,D	3.3 ± 2.2	1160	Study the progression of clinical markers in prodromal Parkinson's disease	Periodic structured sleep, motor, cognitive, autonomic and olfactory testing.	RBD patients from 28 countries (International REM study group)	Motor variables tended to progress faster. By contrast, cognitive, olfactory and autonomic variables showed modest progression with higher variability
Koros et al., 2023	C,D	5 years	65	Assess the role of serum uric acid as a putative biomarker in a prodromal PD cohort (39 RBD and 26 Hyposmia) with abnormal DAT Scan	Longitudinal serum uric measurements from Prodromal population and compared to de novo sporadic PD (423) and 196 HC	Prodromal PD (RBD and hyposmia) in PPMI	Serum uric acid levels are higher in prodromal PD subjects compared to those with manifest PD indicating decrease in the levels of serum uric acid occurs with transition from prodromal to clinical PD
Postuma et al., 2015	C,D,L	4	279	Assess whether risk factors for PD increase rate of defined neurodegenerative disease in RBD	Self-reported questionnaire about D and L. variables including pesticide exposures, occupation, comorbid conditions, medication use, family history, and autonomic/motor symptoms. At 4 years follow-up, clinical assessment for dementia or parkinsonism. Endpoint:	iRBD population without PD from 12 centres	33.3% developed neurodegenerative disease. Patients who converted were older, with similar sex distribution. Neither caffeine, smoking, nor alcohol exposure predicted conversion. Convertors were more likely to report family history of dementia (odds ratio [OR] = 2.09), without significant differences in PD or sleep disorders. Autonomic and motor symptoms were more common among those who converted.
Shin et al., 2020	C,D	5	89 total 31 PD, 39 iRBD, 19 HC	To elucidate longitudinal changes in the DAT availability in association with the prodromal markers in iRBD.	All participants were evaluated for olfaction, neuropsychological tests, and the MDS-UPDRS and underwent 18F-FP-CIT PET scans every 2 years. Calculated the DAT pattern by performing the principal component analysis of tracer uptakes in 6 striatal regions	naive PD, HC and iRBD from clinic population	Baseline and longitudinal monitoring of the DAT pattern can be a useful biomarker in identifying individuals with a high risk of disease conversion and in selecting the potential population for clinical trials in iRBD
Vaswani et al., 2022	C,D	10	186	Hyposmia on a single test has been associated with increased risk of PD, but, taken alone, lacks specificity.	Serial olfaction tests were performed, assessed with the UPSIT at baseline and on average 1.4 years later. Multiple logistic	Hyposmia	Relative risk of clinical conversion to PD was 8.3 (95% CI:0.92–75.2, p = 0.06) and of abnormal DAT scan was 12.5 (2.4–156.2, p = 0.005) for persistent hyposmia,

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
				We evaluated whether repeating olfactory testing improves the diagnostic characteristics of this screening approach	regression and Cox proportional hazards regression were used to estimate the hazard of development of clinical PD or abnormal DAT imaging.		compared to reversion. Repeat olfactory testing may be an efficient and cost-effective strategy to improve identification of at-risk patients for early diagnosis and disease modification studies.
Xiang et al., 2023	C,D		278-RBD 556 HC	To investigate the risk factors for RBD in a case-control study	Participants with probable RBD (pRBD) were defined using the RBD Questionnaire-Hong Kong (RBDQ-HK).	iRBD and HC	We determined several risk factors for pRBD in this case-control study. Future studies are needed to understand the mechanism underlying the association between these factors and pRBD.
Zhang et al., 2022	C,D,L	5.8	281	To assess risk factors for phenoconversion to PD in patients with RBD	Detailed questionnaire about L. Patients were prospectively followed and received assessments for parkinsonism or dementia during follow-up.	iRBD from 12 centres	46.3% patients developed neurodegenerative disease. Overall phenoconversion rate was 24.2% after 3 years, and 67.5% after 10 years. Patients with older age (adjusted hazard ratio [aHR] = 1.05) and nitrate derivative use (aHR = 2.18) were more likely to phenoconvert. Prior pesticide exposure, rural living, lipid-lowering medication use, and respiratory medication use were associated with lower phenoconversion risk.

General discussion

This review aims to provide an update on the clinical, demographic and lifestyle variables that increase the risk of developing PD or phenoconversion from prodromal PD to clinical PD, as well as the different types of approaches to assess these markers. These longitudinal studies have variable strengths and limitations based on study characteristics, assessment models (e.g., prospective versus retrospective, AI-driven approaches), precision of marker estimates (e.g., clinical versus self-reported) and the certainty of PD phenoconversion (e.g., medical records vs. imaging etc.) and data quality of markers (sensitivity and specificity). Population studies aimed to find independent factors that increase the risk of PD incidence, while some, such as the Predict PD algorithm, used multivariate analysis to predict the risk of developing PD (Schrag et al., 2019). The limitation of population studies is that the incidence rate of PD is approximately 200 per 100,000 person-years in those over 60 years old. Therefore, cohorts need to be very large and are thus highly costly, while their representativeness is limited (Noyce et al., 2017). The smaller prodromal population studies aimed to characterize the interaction of these underlying prodromal states (such as RBD or hyposmia) with other demographic or environmental factors. These studies are less costly and help identify populations for clinical trials that seek neuroprotective interventions but are also less representative of the general population.

Clinical PD is a heterogeneous and complex disease with many different possible aetiologies and thus prodromal PD is probably also heterogeneous and needs to be further investigated. For example, a subgroup of PD patients may have few or irrelevant non motor symptoms, and thus their prodromal state probably differs from other PD subtypes. Thus, phenotyping prodromal PD subtypes is likely to be important and will help delineate other variables that may influence if and when individuals phenoconvert to clinical PD.

2.2.2 Genetic markers associated with PD Risk

Genetics are highlighted as a key factor in the risk for Parkinson's disease (PD) (Bandres-Ciga, S. *et al.* 2020). Although numerous genetic studies have been conducted on PD over the past decades, Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS), meta-analyses, and Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) continue to be actively performed (Sia MW *et al.* 2021). Understanding the genetic basis of PD risk is crucial to facilitate early prognosis and accurate diagnosis of the disease. This review aims to (1) report the genetic variants associated with PD risk through GWAS, Mendelian randomisation and meta-analysis, and (2) assess the PRS predictive models for PD risk published between 1/1/ 2013 and 1/2/2025.

Study selection

The search was performed within the Rayyan bibliographic searches tool using the same combination of search terms that were used in D2.3: “gene” OR “genetic” OR “GWAS” OR “PRS” OR “Polygenic Risk Score” OR “SNP” OR “polymorphism” OR “genetic association” AND “risk” OR “prodromal”. This first search yielded 122 and 12 articles, respectively. Nine of these articles were duplicates, thus 125 articles were screened, e The criteria for inclusion were similar the previous systematic review (D2.3) and described in **Table 3**. All included titles and abstracts were screened by two independent reviewers. Fifty-three articles were excluded because they conveyed an incorrect publication type (e.g., reviews, case reports). Where appropriate, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. Fifty-eight of the remaining articles were also excluded as they did not refer to PD, were not relevant to genetics, did not have clear genetic/statistical results or were not related to PD risk. Nine of the remaining studies were excluded because they included statistical associations that did not meet the above p-value thresholds. This filtering and cut-off resulted in 6 records. A second search was also performed through the PRS (<https://www.pgscatalog.org/>) and GWAS (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>)

catalogues, as well as a manual search to assess whether some important studies were missing. Through the second search, two additional studies, one from the GWAS catalogue and one from a manual search, were added. Eight articles were finally recorded and summarised in this updated version and added to the 43 studies of the previous report.

Table 3 Criteria for Study inclusion in the systematic review

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Data	Generated or re-analysed available genetic data related with PD risk
Results	GWAS or meta-analysis study with a significant statistical association with p-values less than 5×10^{-8} and 5×10^{-6} , respectively or PRS study

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	249	125	374
Articles included in literature table	43	8	51

Study characteristics

The summarised articles include meta-analysis/mendelian randomisation of GWAS data, proteogenomic, GWAS and PRS studies. Most of the studies do not include clinical scale data, and only a small number of the studies reported the proportion of participants based on gender. All studies reported the sample size (cases/controls) and some cohort characteristics such as population and database cohort. Healthy control individuals were recruited for all the recorded studies.

Genetic associations

Table 4 summarises the study characteristics (sample size, study type) and the statistically significant reported variants or PRS. Studies recruited through Deliverable 2.3 are shaded with a light grey colour, while the studies recruited through this updated search are presented first in the table. Healthy control participants were reported for all included studies, and a comparison between the genetic data of patients with PD and healthy controls was performed to identify genetic variants that are associated with PD risk. Through the previous search, 43 GWAS, meta-analysis, PRS and GWAS with meta-analysis/ PRS studies were recorded. The updated search revealed eight new meta-analysis/Mendelian randomisation of GWAS data, proteogenomic and PRS studies. Two studies reported PRS association with PD risk, and the remaining six studies identified significant genetic variants associated with PD risk. In all studies, samples/data were recruited from large repositories, such as the UK Biobank. Most of the recorded studies used Mendelian randomisation analysis.

Table 4 Studies about genetic markers and PD risk. Publications reported in the previous version of the deliverable are presented at the top of the table.

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Abolfazl Doostparast Torshizi et al., 2024	7,099 cases and 531,918 controls	Proteogenomic analysis	GBA1 (rs2230288); TMEM175 (rs34311866); SNCA (rs1372519); LRRK2 (rs34637584); HIP1R (rs10847839); GCH1 (rs11158026); KANSL1 (rs4630591); NECTIN2 (rs6857); STK39 - RN7SL813P (rs9917256); HLA-DRB1 - HLA-DQA1 (rs2760980)
Alexandra Reynoso et al., 2024	18,819 cases/ 545,751 controls	Statistical interactions between PD and genetic, PRS	PRS (55 variants)
Astros Th Skuladottir et al., 2024	12,185 PD/ 780,058 controls	Genetic association and meta-analysis	ITSN1 (75 loss of function variants)
Kim et al., 2024	57,893 European ancestry cases, 1,505,102 European ancestry controls, 7,046 East Asian ancestry cases, 176,756 East Asian ancestry controls, 2,440 Hispanic or Latin American cases, 582,220 Hispanic or Latin American controls, 288 African ancestry cases, 193,985 African ancestry controls; Replication:NA	GWAS and Meta-analysis	(rs12497850); (rs6803771); (rs7636454); (rs11729193); (rs75072999); (rs34311866); (rs11941559); (rs7673321); (rs6854006); (rs356182); (rs1372518); (rs79214011); (rs75541595); (rs1867598); (rs246815); (rs9461359); (rs9468199); (rs12528068); (rs9487736); (rs41286192); (rs34096562); (rs11783129); (rs13294100); (rs13664); (rs2178923); (rs4910150); (rs6592142); (rs3802920); (rs73273590); (rs34773022); (rs10847864); (rs1078514); (rs1956438); (rs11158026); (rs1561758); (rs1870293); (rs850731); (rs8327); (rs713522); (rs199453); (rs61169879); (rs8091977); (rs55818311); (rs6060983); (rs1736020); (rs2248244); (rs11164870); (rs114138760); (rs146143531); (rs35682329); (rs10737170); (rs35161831); (rs148163066); (rs17411858); (rs28370650); (rs17442721); (rs17443414); (rs190807041); (rs11177328); (rs10513789); (rs71314284); (rs16843452); (rs4698412); (rs1550556); (rs4859676); (rs114762839); (rs79483792); (rs78327649); (rs145138919); (rs13117519); (rs7434295); (rs34133110); (rs3104776); (rs113487377); (rs11650438); (rs665268); (rs62066707); (rs62053943); (rs7225082); (rs34724124); (rs148528915); (rs77483524); (rs4485435); (rs4588066); (rs75344947); (rs4815573); (rs73174657); (rs10775809); (rs12734374); (rs10903); (rs12118655); (rs4653767); (rs1326293); (rs11683001); (rs57891859); (rs12987123); (rs6808178); (rs199351); (rs1293298); (rs6469271); (rs10756905); (rs6476434); (rs118117788); (rs6658353); (rs4421827); (rs1108439); (rs16833168); (rs6806917); (rs1442190); (rs6582586); (rs78299420); (rs28659953); (rs11610045); (rs1127021); (rs8018800); (rs8012377); (rs112288215); (rs28648524); (rs2251086); (rs11956597); (rs9393826)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Matthew J Kmieciak et al., 2024	PD(LRRK2 G2019S - 188; Non-carriers- 2113)/ Older non-manifest (LRRK2 G2019S -717; Matched Controls-7170)	LRRK2 G2019S variant-PD risk; PRS	Original PRS (1,770 variants); Modified PRS (1,724 variants)
Paula Reyes-Pérez et al., 2024	37.7K cases, 18.6K proxy cases (having a first-degree relative with PD), and 1,417,791 controls	PD risk at the genome-wide and local genomic regional level data	genomic segment 133778459 - 133826880 (113 SNPs); genomic segment 133710526 -133715433 (24 SNPs); genomic segment 66147151 - 66276451 (454 SNPs); genomic segment 66093868 - 66276446 (633 SNPs); genomic segment 41641615-41682255 (79 SNPs); genomic segment 41697526-41756151 (89 SNPs); genomic segment 66452664-66460588 (32 SNPs); genomic segment 41601209-41627275 (90 SNPs); genomic segment 41487790-41576081 (154 SNPs); genomic segment 41625517-41636938 (17 SNPs); genomic segment 17713713-17740325 (37 SNPs); genomic segment 123972608-124084500 (313 SNPs); genomic segment 243651535-244014381 (524 SNPs); genomic segment 66386212-66423538 (86 SNPs); genomic segment 161128662-161350305 (496 SNPs)
Sreemol Gokuladhas et al., 2024	33,674 PD cases & 449,056 control	De novo analysis integrating the Brain Cortex-specific Gene Regulatory Network (BC-GRN), PPIN and GWAS data	MMRN1 (rs3775467); GPNMB (rs858271); NUPL2 (rs1637221); PRSS36 (rs113448632); CD38 (rs4698413); LINC02210 (rs77692262); ARHGAP27 (rs79724577); ADORA2B (rs4792713); STX4 (rs11640957); RAB29 (rs10900524); KANSL1 (rs11656151); ZSWIM7 (rs1860643); KLHL7-AS1 (rs10231555); KAT8 (rs7187995); TMEM175 (rs2306244); RNF40 (rs8046391); TTC19 (rs2285583)
Weimin Li et al., 2024	380 PD patients and 178 healthy controls	Identify potential causal associations	KANSL1 (rs78938131, rs4471723, rs62061848, rs17577369, rs17660228); BST1 (rs6852450, rs11724635, rs4698412, rs34559912, rs4389574)
Zhe Han et al., 2025	15,056 cases and 12,637 controls	Association analysis through summary-based Mendelian Randomization (SMR)	BST1 (rs34559912); RP11-707O23.5 (rs2532233); DND1P1 (rs113991678); RP11-115L11.1 (rs4698119); SETD1A (rs7206511)
Bandres-Ciga et al., 2019	PD: 4,639, HC: 2,949; Replication: NA	GWAS	SNCA(rs356182); LRRK2(rs190807041); KANSL1, MAPT(rs113434679); HLA-DQB1(rs9275152); CRHR1(rs62053943);

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Blauwendraat et al., 2020	PD: 1,588, HC: 7,584; Replication: PD: 1,194, HC: 13,901	GWAS	SNCA(rs356219)
Bobbili et al., 2020	PD:340, HC: 146	genetic association and PRS	PRS (43 SNPs-singleton loss-of- function variants); (PRS_LRRK2)
Brolin et al., 2022	PD: 929, HC: 935; Replication:NA	GWAS, meta-analysis	(rs12771445)
Chairta et al., 2021	PD: 235, HC: 464	PRS	PRS (12)
Chang et al., 2017	PD: 20,184, HC: 397,324; Replication: PD:5851, HC: 5866	Meta-analysis	MICU3(rs591323); BAG3(rs117896735); DLG2(rs3793947); MIR4697(rs329648); LRRK2(rs76904798); OGFOD2(rs11060180); GCH1(rs11158026); TMEM229B(rs1555399); VPS13C(rs2414739); ZNF646, KAT8(rs14235); ARHGAP27, CRHR1, KANSL1, SPPL2C, MAPT, STH(rs17649553); SYT4(rs12456492); LSM7(rs62120679); DDRGK1(rs8118008); ITPKB(rs4653767); IL1R2(rs34043159); SCN3A(rs353116); SATB1(rs4073221); NCKIPSD, CDC71(rs12497850); ALAS1, TLR9, DNAH1, BAP1, PHF7, NISCH, STAB1, ITIH3, ITIH4(rs143918452); ANK2, CAMK2D(rs78738012); ELOVL7(rs2694528); ZNF184(rs9468199); CTSB(rs2740594); SORBS3, PDLIM2, C8orf58, BIN3(rs2280104); (rs10929159); (rs67460515); (rs10463554); (rs17767294); (rs943437); (rs2921073); (rs2296887); (rs9568188); (rs9516970); (rs8017172); (rs316619); (rs5910); (rs6416935); GBA(rs35749011); NUCKS1, SLC41A1(rs823118); SIPA1L2(rs10797576); TMEM163, CCNT2(rs6430538); STK39(rs1474055); MCCC1(rs12637471); TMEM175, DGKQ(rs34311866); FAM200B, CD38(rs11724635); FAM47E(rs6812193); SNCA(rs356182); HLA-DRB6, HLA-DQA1(rs9275326); KLHL7, NUPL2, GPNMB(rs199347); SH3GL2(rs13294100); FAM171A1(rs10906923); GALC(rs8005172); COQ7(rs11343); TOX3(rs4784227)
Do et al., 2011	PD: 3,426, HC: 29,624; Replication: NA	GWAS	SCARB2(rs6812193); SNCA(rs356220); MAPT(rs12185268); MCCC1, LAMP3(rs10513789); GAK(rs6599389); LRRK2(rs34637584); GBA(i4000416)
Foo et al., 2017	PD: 779, HC: 13,227; Replication: PD: 5,125, HC: 17,604	GWAS	MCCC1, DCUN1D1, LAMP3(rs2270968); SNCA, GPRIN3(rs8180209); LRRK2, SLC2A13, C12orf40(rs1384236)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Foo et al., 2020	6,724 East Asian ancestry cases, 24,851 East Asian ancestry controls; Replication:57,545 European ancestry cases, 1,868,816 European ancestry controls, 988 Japanese ancestry cases, 2,521 Japanese ancestry controls	GWAS and Meta-analysis	SNCA(rs6826785); PARK16(rs6679073); MCCC1(rs2292056); ITPKB(rs16846351); DLG2(rs12278023); FYN(rs1887316); RIT2(rs4130047); BST1(rs6449168); SV2C(rs246814)
Hamza et al., 2010	PD:2,000; HC: 1,986; Replication: Up to 1,447 PD, 1,468 HC	GWAS	SNCA (rs356220); GAK (rs11248051); HLA-DRA(rs3129882)
Hill-Burns et al., 2014	sPD: 1,565, familial PD: 435, HC: 1,986; Replication: sPD: 1,528, familial PD: 707, HC: 796	GWAS	HUSEYO(rs2338971); SNCA(rs356220); SNCA(rs356220); HLA(rs3129882); HLA(rs3129882); HUSEYO(rs2338971)
Ibanez et al., 2017	PD: 829, HC: 432	PRS	PRS (16)
Jacobs et al., 2020	PD :1276, HC: 500 406	PRS	PRS (Nalls, 90 SNPs) highest 10% of PRSs
Le Guen et al., 2021	PD: 6451 (male), 3551 (male proxy cases), HC: 251,229; Replication: PD: 1027, HC: 1147	Meta-analysis	(rs111841435); (rs28602900); (rs7066890); (rs11796528); (rs41306249); (rs28602900)
Lee et al., 2021	PPMI (367 sPD), 72 LRRK2 (G2019S), and 39 GBA (N370S) PD patients, HC: 213); GSH (38 sPD, 71 HC)	genetic association and GRS	PRS (45 SNPs)
Lee et al., 2022	de novo PD: 413, HC: 195	PRS	PRS (87)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Li et al., 2019	PD: 418, HC: 426	genetic association and PRS	PRS1 (13 SNPs); PRS2 (9 SNPs); PRS3
Lill et al., 2012	PD: 2,197, HC: 2,061; Replication: Up to 98,080 European and Asian ancestry individuals	Meta-analysis	LRRK2(rs34778348); LRRK2(rs1491942); GAK, DGKQ(rs11248060); MAPT, STH(H1H2 (chr17:42131818–41149582)); SNCA(rs356219); SNCA(rs6532194)
Liu et al., 2011	PD: 268, HC: 178; Replication: PD:1,782; HC: 1,658	GWAS, meta-analysis	NSF (rs183211); UNC13B(rs10121009); WNT3(rs415430)
Liu et al., 2022	IPDGC, 7,204 PD and 9,412 HC and validation cohorts COURAGE-PD, 8,968 PD and 7,598 HC; UK Biobank, 2,639 PD and 14,301 HC; AMP-PD, 2,248 PD and 2,817 HC	PRS and genetic association in meta-analysis	LINC01262(rs62325099); TBCA (rs2652202); LINC01375(rs12245509); C18orf42(rs292289); PRS (1,060); PRS (1,034); PRS (977); PRS (802)
Nalls et al., 2011	PD: 5,333, HC: 12,019; Replication: PD: 7,053 cases, HC: 9,007 controls	Meta-analysis	GAK (rs6599388); BST1(rs11724635); LRRK2(rs1491942); SYT11(rs34372695); ACMSD(rs6710823); MCCC1, LAMP3(rs11711441); SNCA(rs356219); STK39(rs2102808); HLA-DRB5(6:32588205); CCDC62, HIP1R(rs12817488); MAPT(rs2942168)
Nalls et al., 2014	PD:13,708, HC: 95,282; Replication: PD: 5,353, HC:5,551	Meta-analysis	CCDC62(rs11060180); GCH1(rs11158026); TMEM229B(rs1555399); VPS13C(rs2414739); BCKDK, STX1B(rs14235); MAPT(rs17649553); RIT2(rs12456492); SPPL2B(rs62120679); DDRGK1(rs8118008); FGF20(rs591323); GBA, SYT11(rs35749011); NUCKS1, RAB7L1(rs823118); SIPA1L2(rs10797576); ACMSD, TMEM163(rs6430538); STK39(rs1474055); MCCC1(rs12637471); TMEM175, GAK, DGKQ(rs34311866); BST1(rs11724635); SCARB2, FAM47E(rs6812193); SNCA(rs356182); HLA-DQB(rs9275326); GPNMB(rs199347); INPP5F(rs117896735); DLG2(rs3793947); MIR4697(rs329648); LRRK2(rs76904798)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Nalls et al., 2019	PD: 15,056, 18,618 proxy cases, HC: 449,056; Replication: PD: 22,632, HC: 968,735	meta-GWAS and PRS	<p>CHRNA1(rs12600861); RETREG3(rs12951632); UBTF(rs2269906); FAM171A2(rs850738); CRHR1(rs62053943); CRHR1(rs117615688); WNT3(rs11658976); BRIP1(rs61169879); DNAH17(rs666463); ASXL3(rs1941685); RIT2(rs12456492); MEX3C(rs8087969); SPPL2B(rs55818311); CRLS1(rs77351827); DYRK1A(rs2248244); SEMA4A(rs35643925); TMEM163(rs4954162); SNCA(rs356228); SNCA(rs356203); ZNF608(rs6875262); SLC44A4(rs9267659); FGD4(rs181609621); LRRK2(rs117073808); CNTN1(rs141128804); GXYLT1(rs138017112); ITGA8(rs896435); GBF1(rs10748818); BAG3(rs72840788); INPP5F(rs117896735); RNF141(rs7938782); DLG2(rs12283611); IGSF9B(rs3802920); LRRK2(rs76904798); LRRK2(rs34637584); SCAF11(rs7134559); HIP1R(rs10847864); FBRSL1(rs11610045); CAB39L(rs9568188); MBNL2(rs4771268); MIPOL1(rs12147950); GCH1(rs11158026); RPS6KL1(rs3742785); GALT(rs979812); VPS13C(rs2251086); SYT17(rs6497339); CD19(rs2904880); SETD1A(rs11150601); NOD2(rs6500328); SCARB2(rs6825004); FAM47E(rs4101061); FAM47E-STBD1(rs6854006); SNCA(rs356182); SNCA(rs5019538); CAMK2D(rs13117519); CLCN3(rs62333164); ELOVL7(rs1867598); PAM(rs26431); C5orf24(rs11950533); LOC100131289(rs4140646); KCNIP3(rs2042477); HLA-DRB5(rs112485576); TMEM163(rs57891859); FYN(rs997368); SATB1(rs73038319); GPNMB(rs199351); IP6K2(rs12497850); CTSB(rs1293298); MED12L(rs11707416); BIN3(rs2280104); MCCC1(rs10513789); GAK(rs873786); TMEM175(rs34311866); BST1(rs4698412); LCORL(rs34025766); PMVK(rs114138760); KRTCAP2(rs35749011); GBAP1(rs76763715); FCGR2A(rs6658353); VAMP4(rs11578699); NUCKS1(rs823118); RAB29(rs11557080); ITPKB(rs4653767); SIPA1L2(rs10797576); KCNS3(rs76116224); TRIM40(rs9261484); MAP4K4(rs11683001); RIMS1(rs12528068); STK39(rs1474055); RPS12(rs75859381); LINC00693(rs6808178); GS1-124K5.11(rs76949143); KPNA1(rs55961674); FGF20(rs620513); SPTSSB(rs1450522); FAM49B(rs2086641); SH3GL2(rs13294100); SH3GL2(rs10756907); UBAP2(rs6476434); GXYLT1(rs144755950); MAP3K14(rs17686238); CRHR1(rs9912362); MAPT-AS1(rs7221167); KANSL1(rs7225002); NSF(rs199453); DDRGK1(rs2295545); CASC16(rs3104783); CHD9(rs10221156); PRS(PRS (1805)); PRS(PRS (90))</p>

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Pan et al., 2023	PD: 1,972, HC: 2,478; Replication: PD: 8,209, HC: 9,454	GWAS	(rs421016); (rs823118); (rs11557080); (rs34594498); (rs34778348); (rs11158026); (rs2251086); (rs61204179); (rs10513789); (rs4698412); (rs356182); (rs997368)
Pankratz et al., 2012	PD: 4,238, HC: 4,239; Replication: PD: 3,738, HC: 2,111	Meta-analysis	SNCA(rs356220); intergenic(rs9917256); BST1(rs4698412); CNKSR3(rs2275336); LOC642072(rs2395163); GBA(rs12726330); intergenic(rs6430538); DGKQ(rs11248060); intergenic(rs1296028); SH3GL2(rs1536076); intergenic(rs11026412); SLC2A13(rs10877840); intergenic(rs10519131); POL3S(rs11865038); WNT3(rs199515); RIT2(rs12456492)
Park et al., 2023	554 East Asian ancestry female cases, 2,610 East Asian ancestry female controls; Replication: NA	GWAS	(rs34778348); (rs3796661)
Pavelka et al., 2022	IPD :430, HC:556	PRS	PRS (90 SNPS)
Pickrell et al., 2016	9,619 European ancestry cases, 324,522 European ancestry controls; Replication: NA	summary statistics of GWAS	PKP2, SYT10(rs144847051); HLA-DQA1, HLA-DRB5(rs17425622); GBA(rs2230288); STK39, CERS6(rs13016703); GAK(rs35541465); GCH1(rs11158026); DCUN1D1, MCCC1(rs9858038); FAM126A, KLHL7(rs10256359); RAB7L1, NUCKS1(rs823118); TIAL1, BAG3(rs188789342); FAM47E(rs6812193); BST1, CD38(rs4266290); RIT2(rs4130047); ZNF184,HIST1H2BL(rs4713118); CCDC62(rs11060180); CTNND1, OR9Q1(rs687432); PRICKLE1, ADAMTS20(rs148294058); SH3GL2(rs2209440); SYT17, CLEC19A(rs11343); NDUFAF2(rs162227); GPRIN3, SNCA(rs356182); LRRK2(rs28903073); CRHR1, LRRC37A3(rs365825)
Rahman et al., 2023	PD: 6,868, HC: 204	GWAS	GBA: Missense Variant(i4000415); TRIM46: Intron Variant(rs114525519); ASH1L: Intron Variant(rs116540837); PBXIP1: Intron Variant(rs116114495); GBA: intergenic variant(rs1630500); ARHGEF2: Intron Variant(rs71628699); RIT1: Intron Variant(rs1749409); SEMA4A: Missense Variant(rs41265017); LMNA: Intron Variant(rs513043); LMNA: Intron Variant(rs577492); LMNA: Intron Variant(rs553016); PMF1-BGLAP: Intron Variant(rs1800247); (rs2764407); (rs35902694)
Rizig et al., 2023	PD:1488, HC: 196 430	GWAS and meta-analysis	GBA1(rs3115534)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Rodrigo et al., 2021	5,167 European ancestry cases, 5,366 European ancestry controls; Replication: NA	GWAS	ASH1L(rs145330152); TEK4(rs187989831); TMEM175(rs34311866); SNCA(rs983361); WDR41(rs137887044); MUC12(rs78837976); CARS2(rs74125032); HASPIN(rs117672332); MAPT(rs7221167); WNT3(rs199501); GBA(rs35749011); SNCA(rs3806789); HASPIN(rs11653889);
Saad et al., 2011	PD: 1039, HC: 1984; Replication: PD: 3232, HC: 7064	GWAS	SNCA(rs356220)
Sakaue et al., 2021	2,638 European ancestry cases, 477,380 European ancestry controls, 340 East Asian ancestry cases, 175,788 East Asian ancestry controls; Replication: NA	GWAS	(rs35643925); (rs356220)
Satake et al., 2009	PD: 988, HC: 2,521; Replication: PD: 933, HC: 15,753	GWAS	SNCA (rs11931074); BST1(rs4538475); LRRK2(rs1994090); SLC45A3, PARK16, PM20D1, NUCKS1, RAB7L1, SLC41A1(rs947211)
Sia et al., 2021	PD: 333, HC: 25,313	PRS	PRS (6)
Siitonen et al., 2017	PD: 403, HC: 1,650; Replication: NA	GWAS, find genetic associations with PD	COL18A1(chr21:46916033); ADAMTS9, AS2(chr3:64699445); PPFIBP1(chr12:27737074); SNX29P2(chr16:29348809); WWOX(chr16:79360135); ZFAT(chr8:135611154); ZNF98(chr19:22620820); ZNF277(chr7:111916329); FER(chr5:108436958); RPL18P3(chr5:120977240); FRRS1L(chr9:111929013); PBX1(chr1:164546863); CEL(chr9:135955826)
Simon-Sanchez et al., 2009	PD: 1,713, HC: 3,978; Replication: PD: 3,361, HC: 4,573	GWAS	SNCA(rs2736990); NSF(rs199533); MAPT, C17orf69, KIAA1267, LOC644246(rs393152)
Smeland et al., 2021	PD: 20,184, HC: 397,324; Replication: NA	GWAS	KLHL7(rs28624974); RN7SL474P(rs11203810); SH3GL2(rs13294100); CCNT2-AS1(rs6430538); STK39(rs4667572); TBC1D5(rs13078687); PKP2(rs138895122); CCDC62(rs11060112); BST1(rs12651314); GPR65(rs8005172); RP11-16217,

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
			1(rs3889108); STX1B(rs140820592); ELOVL7(rs1867598); POLRMTP1(rs148534175); HLA-DRB1(rs2647062); RAB25(rs34372695); CTSB(rs1293298); NUCKS1(rs3805); BAG3(rs144814361); IGSF9B(rs3802920); BICD1(rs77669894); SLC2A13(rs28370664); MCCC1(rs140278703); TMEM175(rs34884217); GCH1(rs11158026); FAM47E:FAM47E-STBD1:FAM47E-STBD1(rs12643261); SNCA(rs10516839); KANSL1(rs113564729); ZNF608(rs6875262); RIT2(rs12456492); RSL24D1P1(rs9468195)
Spencer et al., 2011	PD: 1,705, HC: 5,175; Replication: PD: 1,039, HC: 1,984	GWAS	MAPT(rs8070723) SNCA(rs356220)
Tirozzi et al., 2023	PD: at least 37,688, HC: at least 18,618; Replication:NA	GWAS	(rs356219); (rs1372518)
Vacic et al., 2014	PD: 1130, HC: 2611; Replication: PD: 306, HC: 2583	GWAS	LRRK2(rs1442190); MAPT(rs17577094); GBA(rs1630500)
Wainberg et al., 2023	PD GWAS: 37,688 cases, 18,618 proxy cases from the UK Biobank with a family history of PD, and 1,417,791 HC + summary statistics for all participants from 23andMe	genetic association, identify loci associated with PD through GWAS	LCORL(rs34025766); SETD1A(rs11150601); BCKDK (rs889555); GRN(rs5848); FAM171A2(rs850738); LINC02210- CRHR1(rs62053943); WNT3(rs199526); GAK(rs873786); TMEM175(rs34311866)

General discussion

This review aims to record all the variants as well as PRS which are reported to be associated with PD risk, up to date. The summarised studies suggest that several genes and genetic variants might be related to PD. It is observed that although some SNPs are reported only in a specific population, some others overlap between different populations and studies. Some studies were carried out in specific and small populations, while other studies combined different available data and performed meta-analyses. A study in a specific population has the limitation of a small sample size but simultaneously has the advantage of discovering something unique for the studied population.

This updated version of the systematic review/search focuses on the studies published between 1/1/2024 and 1/2/2025 that report statistically significant associations of genetic variants and PRSs with PD risk. Despite the short search period, eight new studies were published that meet the inclusion criteria. These studies report 31 SNPs, five genetic segments with groups of SNPs, and three PRSs that are significantly associated with PD risk. SNP rs34559912 is reported in two studies (Li, W., *et al.* 2024; Han, Z., *et al.* 2025) to be associated with a decreased risk of developing PD. Interestingly, SNPs located at PD-related genes were also reported. For example, Doostparast Torshizi A., *et al.*, (2024) used European ancestry cases and control individuals and reported variants associated with PD risk that are in the *GBA1*, *SNCA* and *LRKK2* genes. Some studies showed associations with genomic segments (not individual SNPs), indicating that a group of SNPs in specific regions is associated with PD risk. For instance, Reyes-Pérez, P., *et al.* (2024) showed a significant association of PD with 113 SNPs in the genomic segment 133778459 - 133826880 (chromosome 22: 41452876-41829000). In addition, two PRS studies were recorded. Reynoso, A., *et al.* (2024) used PD cases and healthy controls of the 23andMe research cohort and reported a 55-SNP PRS, while Kmiecik, M. J., *et al.* (2024) used sub-cohorts of PD patients (*LRRK2* G2019S carriers and non-carriers) and highlighted 2 PRSs, an original and a modified PRS, that are associated with PD risk. Although several variants and PRSs have been reported over the years, further investigation is essential to validate these findings, which could potentially be used for predictive testing.

2.2.3 AI-driven approaches for PD risk modelling

Study selection

Within the Rayyan software the following keywords were used: “machine learning”, “artificial intelligence”, “sensitivity”, “specificity”, “area under the curve”, “AUC”. For the initial literature search spanning between 2013 and 2023, these keywords prompted alongside “risk” and “prodromal” yielded 71 and 15 records respectively. When the same search was performed for papers published for the updated search (spanning between 2023 and 2025), 87 and 10 papers were identified for “risk” and “prodromal” respectively. Subsequently, three independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Where necessary, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. Studies comparing PD with other diseases such as Alzheimer’s Disease, Progressive Supranuclear Palsy, or Lewy Body disease were dropped to minimize the analysis complexity. Also, genetic studies were excluded and can be found in the “Genetic Markers” subdomain of this deliverable, resulting in 13 records in total for the initial and 3 for the updated review.

Table 5 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. We did not restrict our search to studies utilizing digital technologies as our aim was to provide a comprehensive review of commonly used AI-driven approaches for identifying people at risk of developing PD. The updated version of the literature review particularly focused on studies including incident PD, to align with the objectives of PD risk model development are the focus of another deliverable (see D3.2 and upcoming D3.4).

Table 5 Selection criteria for AI-driven approaches and PD risk

Item	Definition
Population	Incident PD, or prodromal PD
Analysis	AI-driven approach
Results	At least one model performance metric

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	86	97	183
Articles included in literature table	13	3	16

Study characteristics

Eight studies analysed open-source data (e.g., UK biobank, PPMI or other data-sources) and the remainder employed their own experimental design and data collection methods. Among these, seven aimed to predict future diagnosis of PD (incident PD), monitoring participants for periods ranging from 5 to 10 years. Eight papers predicted the presence of prodromal symptoms. The latter included people with REM Behaviour Disorder (RBD; 5 papers) and people with Idiopathic Hyposmia (IH; 3 papers).

The included studies recruited people with PD with range of mean age 60 to 81; one study did not report age, but stratified participants in 10-year age bands. A few studies failed to report important clinico-demographic information. Indicatively, two studies did not report sex, 10 studies did not report disease duration, all but two studies did not report PD subtype, and six studies did not provide information for the reported motor severity score (MDS-UPDRS-III). However, the absence of clinical information for incident PD is not surprising.

Measurements and AI-driven approaches

Table 6 summarizes the models and approaches used in the included studies, highlighting the use of various input features such as voice (six studies) and kinematic data from wearables (six studies).

The most common model used to predict PD risk was Random Forest (RF), utilised in eight studies. Other models used were Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naive Bayes Classifiers (NB), Binary Logistic Regressors (LR), Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), XGBoost, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM), and General least squares linear models (GLSLM). Survival probability analysis was performed by one study using Survival Random Forest.

Input datasets are often plagued by collinearities, stemming from the utilisation of high dimensional datasets. To mitigate this risk, 12 of the selected studies opted for feature selection, before applying any ML algorithm. This approach aims to improve model accuracy and interpretability of the findings. In addition, all but two studies documented a validation strategy for evaluating the robustness of the model results.

Table 6 Studies about AI-driven approaches and PD risk

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Acquah et al., 2024	Accelerometer based step count	94,696 of whom 407 were Incident PD	62,3	44	Cox regression	No	No	-	-	-	HR >12369 steps = 59% lower risk (HR 0.41) than those <6276 (HR=1.00). 1000 step increase = 8% lower risk of PD (HR=0.92)	Higher accelerometer-derived physical activity associated with a lower risk of incident PD
Favaro et al., 2024	Voice features (intensity, variability, pause length etc)	40 incident PD and 40 HC	NA	NA	Bagging, Extreme Gradient Boosting, Multilayer Perceptron, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine	Nested cross validation	Nested cross validation	Incident PD vs HC: 57-73	-	-	AUC: Incident PD vs HC: 0,72-0,75	Speech abnormalities can serve as early biomarkers for PD 10 y pre-diagnosis

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Felix et al., 2024	Electronic Health records	PD=9060, HC=26476 AD=11352 MS=5239 ALS=825	PD = 72, HC = 70	58	XGB w/ SHAP	XGB native feature selection	5-fold cross validation	-	--	-	AUC: 0.809 (0months), 0.738 (12months), 0.700 (24months), 0.651 (60months)	The closer to the diagnosis date, the more accurate the risk prediction model. Males, non-alcohol drinking, fallers are more prone to develop PD in 12 months
Allwright et al., 2023	Demographics, level of activity, clinical, medical records, blood assays	334062 (of which 2719PD)	60.2	PD=62, HC=44	XGBOOST, SVM, RF, LR	SHAP value importance to get the 50 most recurrent across 100 iterations	80-20 train-test	-	-	-	AUC=67	XGBoost outperformed the rest of the models. Being male, having bad overall health rating, slow walking pace, elevated IGF-1, lymphocyte count, and neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio were the highest risk factors.
Arora et al., 2018	Voice, balance, gait, finger tapping, RT, rest and postural tremor	RBD=104, PD=334, HC=84	RBD=64.5, PD=66.1, HC=66.3	RBD=88, PD=63, HC=67	RF	5 different ML models & majority voting	10-fold CV, LOSO, LOO	-	HC vs RBD: 91.9 PD vs RBD: 87.5	HC vs RBD: 90.0 PD vs RBD: 90.1		Smartphones and ML can discriminate among RBD, PD and HC. Posture, rest tremor and voice data provide the most

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Arora et al., 2021	Voice (337 voice features)	RBD=112, PD=335, HC=92	RBD=68.4, PD=69.5, HC=68.5	RBD=87, PD=61, HC=79	RF	RF feature importance	LOSO	-	HC vs RBD:60.7, PD vs RBD:74.9	HC vs RBD:67.6, PD vs RBD:73.2		discriminatory power Smartphone voice signals and ML can discriminate among RBD, PD and HC. Scores were lower when only one recording per patient was used
Cavallo et al., 2019	MDS related upper limb tasks (48 features)	IH=30, PD=30, HC=30	IH=66, PD=67.9, HC=65.2	IH=70, PD=83, HC=83	SVM, RF, NB	A) Pairwise comparisons. (Wilcoxon; p<0.05) B) Spearman correlation to identify collinearities	10-fold cross validation	SVM=71, RF=79, NB=70	SVM=71, RF=79, NB=80	SVM=86, RF=89, NB=70	Precision: SVM=72, RF=80, NB=72 F: SVM=71, RF=80, NB=71	Upper limb features discriminate among IH, RBD and HC. Best model performance was achieved when IH was grouped with HC
Jeancolas et al., 2022	Voice features	RBD=41, PD=117, HC=98	(M/F) RBD=68.2/- , PD=63.8/63.7, HC=60/59.3	RBD=100, PD=64, HC=55	SVM	-	-	Male: PD vs HC=89, RBD vs HC=63, RBD vs HC*=70 Female:	Male: PD vs HC=86, RBD vs HC=59, RBD vs HC*=73 Female:	Male: PD vs HC=92, RBD vs HC=67, RBD vs HC*=67 Female:		Voice related features can discriminate among RBD, PD and HC. Model performance is better in men than women. Model performance worsened when

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
								PD vs HC=70 <i>*RBD with motor symptoms</i>	PD vs HC=70 <i>*RBD with motor symptoms</i>	PD vs HC=70 <i>*RBD with motor symptoms</i>		phone mic features are used
Karabayir et al., 2022	Clinical and risk factor features	292 participants (25 developed PD within 5 years)	PD=80-81, HC=81	N/A	LGDBM	N/A	5-fold cross validation				AUC: PD3*=82, PD5**=77 <i>*Converted in 3 years, **Converted in 5 years</i>	ML trained with clinical data can predict future PD diagnosis. Model predicted those who converted within 3 years more accurately than those converting within 5 or more years.
Rovini et al., 2018	Lower limb features (23 features)	IH=30, PD=30, HC=30	IH=66.0, PD=67.9, HC=65.2	IH=70, PD=83, HC=83	SVM, RF, NB	A) Pairwise comparisons (Wilcoxon; p<0.05) B) Spearman correlation to identify collinearities	10-fold cross validation	SVM=69, RF=77, NB=76	SVM=69, RF=77, NB=76	SVM=84, RF=88, NB=88	Precision: SVM=74, RF=77, NB=76 F: SVM=71, RF=77, NB=76	Models trained on lower limb features can discriminate among IH, PD and HC. Models composed by both lower limbs provided better performance (compared to right and left separately).

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Rovini et al., 2019	Upper and Lower limb features (71 features)	IH=15, PD=15, HC=15	IH=66.5, PD=66.6, HC=64.9	IH=67, PD=47, HC=73	SVM, RF	A) Pairwise comparisons. (Wilcoxon; p<0.05) B) Spearman correlation to identify collinearities	5-fold cross validation	SVM=78, RF=91	SVM=78, RF=91	SVM=89, RF=96	Precision: SVM=80, RF=93 F: SVM=79, RF=92	Upper and lower limb features can discriminate among IH, PD and HC. The best discrimination achieved when PD were compared to HC. Models composed of both upper and lower limbs (rather than separately) provided better performance
Rusz et al., 2018	Voice features (11 features)	RBD=40, PD*=25, HC=25 <i>*de-novo PD</i>	RBD=66.4, PD*=62.3, HC= -	RBD=90, PD*=87, HC=-	Binary LR	A) Fisher least squares difference, B) consistency (r>.8) between recording devices	LOSO	-	PD vs HC=75 PD vs RBD=67 HC vs RBD=70	PD vs HC=79 PD vs RBD=71 HC vs RBD=65	AUC: PD vs HC=85 PD vs RBD=78 HC vs RBD=69	The model showing the best discriminatory performance was composed by 3 features
Rusz et al., 2021	Voice (7 features)	RBD=119, PD=110, HC=88	RBD=68.6, PD=67.4, HC=68.3	RBD=79, PD=74, HC=73	GLSLM	N/A	LOSO	-	PD vs HC=72 PD vs RBD=64 HC vs RBD=60	PD vs HC=72 PD vs RBD=64 HC vs RBD=60	AUC: PD vs HC=80 PD vs RBD=72 HC vs RBD=65	Voice features with ML can discriminate RBD and HC from PD. RBD was discriminated from HC with less discriminatory performance. Monopitch,

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
												prolonged pauses, and imprecise consonants provided the best discriminatory power.
Schalkamp et al., 2023	Genetics, lifestyle, biochemical, prodromal symptoms and accelerometer data	PD=158, Prodromal PD=113, HC=matched	PD=67.6, Prodromal PD=69.3, HC=67.6	PD=61, Prodromal PD=69, HC=6961	LASSO, Survival RF	LASSO feature importance	Nested 5-fold cross validation	-	-	-	AUPRS: PD vs HC=78, Prodromal PD vs HC=78	Accelerometry was the most important predictor among clinical, demographic, genetic data, and prodromal features. Sleep quality and duration are reduced in PD, with a unique reduction in acceleration and more severe sleep deterioration compared to other diseases.
Schrag et al., 2019	Symptoms and lifestyle factors	PD=8166, HC=46755	-	PD=60, HC=59	Backward Multivariate LR	Backward feature selection	70-30 train-test	-	43	99	PPV=37, NPV=99, AUC=80	Within a 5-year follow-up period, the algorithm predicted a future PD diagnosis correctly in 37 cases and predicted no future PD

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
												diagnosis in 99% of cases.
Yuan et al., 2021	demographics, diagnoses other than PD, timings between diagnoses	PD=8000, HC=42000 *2 independent data-sources	72-73	PD=58-61, HC=59-61	LR, RNN	Penalized feature selection	5-fold cross validation	-	-	-	AUC: LR=80, RNN=87	ML can identify the risk of converting to gait or tremor-specific PD. Participants were stratified into those developing gait or tremor symptoms first.

General Discussion

The aim of this review was to assess the effectiveness of AI-driven approaches to predict the risk of developing PD. The findings highlight the successful application of ML techniques in predicting both future PD diagnosis and prodromal PD diagnosis. Smartphone-based assessments, particularly focusing on voice signals and upper/lower limb features, demonstrate promising discriminatory power between people with PD, and prodromal PD (RBD or Hyposmia) and HC. Specifically, for the voice signals, gender differences are apparent, exhibiting better performance in men.

Noteworthy, to the best of our knowledge, only a limited number of recent focused on important features for predicting incident PD. The rest of them focused on indirectly estimating PD risk, by predicting people who were clinically classified as prodromal PD.

Accelerometry emerges as a crucial tool for predicting incident PD, showcasing better performance in identifying incident PD and showcasing its potential for prodromal PD detection. Among the reviewed papers, (Schalkamp et al., 2023) stands out as particularly critical for the objectives of AI-PROGNOSIS. Leveraging multimodal data, including smartwatch accelerometry, from the UK Biobank cohort, this study accurately predicted PD onset up to seven years prior to the clinical diagnosis. Notably, accelerometry data unveil increases in acceleration particularly during sleep, which are distinct to PD and highlight the severity of sleep disturbances in PD compared to other conditions. Leveraging accelerometry data, use of ML algorithms successfully predicts future PD diagnosis and offers a potential tool in detecting populations that may be susceptible to neuroprotective trials and early PD management. They achieved this by augmenting data by splitting them in into 30-second intervals and categorizing physical activity, enhancing the discriminatory performance of the predictive models.

We also encountered an additional critical study (Makarious et al., 2022) that did not pass our initial search criteria, due to its focus on unmedicated PD, rather than prodromal stages of the disease. Despite this, we consider the inclusion of this study in this discussion crucial, due to its exhaustive benchmarking of different Moaches. This study used open-source data (Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative; PPMI and PD Biomarker Program PDBP), aiming to predict PD utilizing UPSIT and genetic data. The AI models applied in its analysis constitute a super-set of the methods presented in the literature table of this sub-domain review. These include: LR, RF, AdaBoost, Gradient Boost, SGD, SVM, ML perceptron, KNN, Linear Discriminant Analysis, and XGBoost. Model performance was tested using the AUC method. UPSIT smell test score and PRS contributed most to the predictive power of the models.

The updated version of our search was focused on incident PD cases, to align with the objectives of AI-PROGNOSIS. Importantly, previous results were backed up by Acquah et al., 2024, in a study using accelerometer-based features to predict incident PD in the same database (UK biobank). Despite not using advanced AI-driven approaches to analyse their data, this study confirms that accelerometer data offer promising solutions to estimate the risk to develop PD. This result comes with no surprise, as it was based on the UK Biobank population, like the report by Schalkamp et al., 2023.

2.2.4 Digital assessments of REM behaviour disorder and daytime somnolence

Study selection for REM behaviour disorder

Digital technology is rapidly advancing in the field of neurology, offering, among other things, new avenues for assessing sleep-related disorders in PD. This review section focuses on the digital assessment of RBD and daytime somnolence, two prevalent non-motor symptoms in PD patients. We explore studies that utilize wearable sensors, smart devices,

and mobile applications to monitor and evaluate these sleep disturbances. Such digital tools facilitate the continuous and objective monitoring of RBD and daytime somnolence in the patient's natural environment, enhancing the understanding of symptom patterns and severity. This approach not only supports clinical decisions but also ties in with the endeavour of identifying those at risk for PD.

Within the framework of the Rayyan application and the accompanying bibliography, we searched for the key words "REM" or "RBD" or "sleep". Eighteen papers were screened, and three papers were considered pertinent.

Table 7 Selection criteria for digital assessments of REM behaviour disorder

Item	Definition
Population	Patients with PD and/or RBD
Outcome	Identify patients or nights with RBD
Apparatus	Wearable sensors and/or smart devices. Passive testing.

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	97	18	115
Articles included in literature table	3	3	6

Table 8 Studies about digital assessments of REM behaviour disorder

Authors	Study aim	Sample size	Sensors used	Model	Model performance metric	Model performance scores	Key take-away
Brink-Kjaer et al., 2023	Develop an ambulatory classifier that combines high-frequency wrist-actigraphy with a short questionnaire to detect isolated REM-sleep behaviour disorder (iRBD).	84 adults (42 iRBD, 21 other sleep disorders, 21 community controls)	1-s, tri-axial wrist-actigraphy + 9-item RBD questionnaire	Gradient-boosted decision-trees (multifeature «boosted DT»); ensemble with questionnaire	Sensitivity / precision (per-subject)	Actigraphy-only: 95.2 % sens., 90.9 % precision. Concordant actigraphy + survey: 100 % specificity/precision, 88.1 % sens.	A fully remote, low-cost pipeline can screen iRBD with clinic-level accuracy and perfect specificity when actigraphy and questionnaire agree.
Carluccio et al., 2024	Test whether sleep-stage time-series from <i>commercial smart-wristbands</i> can support automated RBD detection.	CAP Sleep Database of Physionet	Proprietary wristband sleep-stage output (no raw PSG)	Support-Vector Machine (SVM) out-performed k-NN, Decision Trees (DT), Naïve Bayes (NB) and Logistic Regression (LR)	Accuracy, precision, sensitivity and F1-score	Model Accuracy Precision Sensitivity F1-score kNN 0.872 0.895 0.819 0.855 DT 0.925 0.927 0.899 0.912 SVM 0.956 0.958 0.938 0.948 NB 0.881 0.864 0.855 0.860 LR 0.881 0.854 0.863 0.858	Sleep quality impacts physical and mental health, and this turns out to be more important for frail and elderly individuals. Modern smart bracelets integrate algorithmic logic capable of classifying sleep stages with good accuracy. From the scientific research point of view, it was deemed appropriate to investigate the appropriateness of using such data to provide an automatic tool capable of classifying RBD

Authors	Study aim	Sample size	Sensors used	Model	Model performance metric	Model performance scores	Key take-away
Raschellà et al., 2023	Build and externally validate "RBDAct", a home-use actigraphy classifier for RBD in Parkinson's disease.	26 PD (18 RBD / 8 No-RBD) + 18 insomnia controls	GENEActiv wrist-actigraph (40 Hz home; 100 Hz in-lab) on more-affected arm	SVM after LASSO feature-selection (best of five tested algorithms)	Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity	In-lab (4-fold CV, 100 reps): 92.9 ± 8.2 % acc., 94.9 ± 7.4 % sens., 92.7 ± 13.8 % spec. Home, 14 nights: 100 % acc. in PD; 94.4 % acc. in non-PD controls	Multi-night home actigraphy plus SVM reliably screens RBD in mild-moderate PD; a single wrist on the more-affected side is enough.
Dagay 2023	Explore the feasibility and validity of a new wearable system for accurately measuring sleep at home.	29 PD, 21 HC	PSG and new wearable	n/a	Cohen's kappa, sensitivity	Agreement between the two systems reached Cohen's kappa (k) of 0.688 with agreement in each stage of: wake $k = 0.701$; N1 = 0.224; N2 = 0.584; N3 = 0.410; and rapid eye movement = 0.723. The system reliably detected rapid eye movement sleep without atonia with a sensitivity of 85.7%.	The results demonstrate that the system is valid, accurate and allows for the exploration of sleep at home.
F.Raschella 2022	Classification of RBD patients with ML and actigraphy	26 PD of which 18 RBD, 18 HC	Actigraphy (and PSG for comparison)	Several machine learning classification algorithms (linear discriminant analysis; support vector machine logistic regression; nearest neighbour; Random Forest)	Accuracy	Accuracy of 92.9 ± 8.16 % during in-clinic tests. When validated on home recordings in Parkinson's disease patients, accuracy reached 100% over a 2-week window, and was 94.4% in non-Parkinson's disease control patients.	Actigraphy allows for an accurate classification of RBD subjects.
Ko 2022	Classification of sleep stages (Non-REM, REM)	27 PD. 30 HC	Smartwatch (Asus VivoWatch BP)	k-means clustering	Accuracy of NREM/REM detection	Accuracy of 2-stage (NREM/REM) classification 68.88%, for	The use of the smartwatch could enable detection of RBD, as exemplified by a higher percentage

Authors	Study aim	Sample size	Sensors used	Model	Model performance metric	Model performance scores	Key take-away
	and abnormal REM)					the 3-stage classification (Light/Deep/REM) 64.02%)	of abnormal REM-sleep experienced by PwPD as compared to controls (8.8 vs. 1.6%, p=0.04).

Study selection for daytime somnolence

Within the framework of the Rayyan application and the accompanying bibliography, we searched for the keywords: “somnolence” or “daytime” or “sleep”. The selection criteria are outlined in the **Table 9**. The initial list of the results provided 0 publications for “somnolence”, 6 for “daytime” and 97 for “sleep”. After an assessment of the 103 publications none was considered relevant.

Table 9 Studies about digital assessments of daytime somnolence disorder

Item	Definition
Population	PD patients with episodes of daytime somnolence
Outcome	Identify periods of daytime somnolence
Apparatus	Wearable sensors and/or smart devices. Passive testing.

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	451	103	451
Articles included in literature table	3	0	3

We used the same keywords within “Google Scholar,” and we identified 348 relevant publications. After careful assessment of the studies, a total of 3 papers were included in the systematic review a list of which is presented in **Table 10**. The updated literature database within Rayyan did not contain any of the aforementioned keywords for D2.4, hence there were no new papers included.

Table 10 Studies about digital assessments of daytime somnolence

Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Sensors used	Model performance metric	Model performance scores	Key take-away
Bolitho et al., 2013	PD 85, HC 21	To explore actigraphy as a measure of napping and its relation to performance on neuropsychological tests	Wrist actiwatch (minimittter Actiwatch Spectrum)	Correlations between excessive daytime napping as measured by actigraphy and neuropsychological tests	N/A	Patients with PD reported significantly greater number of nap bouts as well as time spent napping in the day, compared to healthy age matched controls. Patients with PD who exhibited excessive napping through the day had poorer performance on neuropsychological tests.
Höglund et al., 2021	PD 52	To investigate the relationship between daytime sleepiness and other non-motor and motor fluctuations in people with PD	Parkinson's KinetiGraph system (PKG)	Correlation of PKG data with sleepiness as reported by ESS and patient diary (KSS)	n/a	PKG data were weakly correlated with diary data. The fluctuation score (calculated using PKG-measurements) was the only PKG variable that correlated with daytime sleepiness.
Kotschet et al., 2014	PD 68, HC 30	To identify immobility via a wearable device	Parkinson's KinetiGraph system (PKG)	Concordance with PSG	There was concordance between immobility and PSG scores in 85.6% of the 1805 two-minute epochs: 1206 epochs were negative for sleep by both methods and 342 epochs were positive for sleep by both methods ($p < 0.0001$, Chi Squared test).	Immobility (or proportion of time immobile), as measured by the PKG, is a useful surrogate measure of daytime sleep or at least somnolence in PD patients.

General discussion

In this review, we focussed on research on identification of RBD and daytime somnolence that rely on gathering data passively, i.e., via body-worn sensors such as motion sensors or smartwatches. Hence, articles detailing algorithms to detect RBD using only traditional polysomnography (PSG) were excluded. Of the included articles for RBD detection, there is excellent diagnostic sensitivity and congruence with traditional PSG, when using only sensor-derived data (Oz et al., 2023; Raschella et al., 2022). These systems determine either the presence or the absence of RBD, the identification of different sleep stages seems to remain a bigger challenge with one study reporting an accuracy of around 64% (Ko et al., 2022). Encouragingly, these findings demonstrate that reliable RBD detection is possible without the use of traditional PSG, which seems relevant especially in the prodromal stages of PD and in identifying target populations for disease modifying studies.

Daytime somnolence is most assessed using questionnaire data (e.g., the Epworth Sleepiness Scale). Currently, there are no studies aiming at directly investigating or quantifying daytime somnolence. Two of the studies inferred daytime sleepiness from episodes of immobility during the day (Bolitho et al., 2013; Kotschet et al., 2014), one study found that only dyskinesias as measured by actigraphy correlated with self-reported measures of daytime sleepiness (Höglund et al., 2021). In the latter study, there is evidence that increased daytime sleepiness is associated with worse cognitive performance. Taken together, these findings suggest that there is a need of an extensive and dedicated study for assessment of digital biomarkers in daytime somnolence as promising results have been shown in other (related) diseases, such as Lewy body dementia (Wang et al., 2022) for the development of reliable sensors to directly assess daytime somnolence in PD, as this relates to aspects of safety (e.g., driving a car) and could also be related to disease progression, as exemplified by the association between daytime sleepiness and worse cognitive performance.

For the updated report in D2.4, no new findings on both RBD detection and measures of daytime somnolence could be identified, suggesting that there is still a lack of research on biomarkers in this area, which underlines the importance of the endeavours undertaken within the AI-PROGNOSIS project to fill these knowledge gaps..

2.2.5 Summary, unmet needs, and research opportunities

Within the scope of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, this updated review synthesises the current knowledge on risk factors in PD, with a particular emphasis on AI-driven approaches for predictive modelling, while underlying the interplay between clinical, demographic, lifestyle, and genetic factors influencing PD risk. The results of the review alongside the derived unmet needs and arisen research opportunities are outlined in **Table 11**.

To determine the clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors that may influence the risk of developing PD, there are predominantly general population and prodromal PD longitudinal studies that focus on phenoconversion to PD as an outcome. The resulting data suggest that many non-motor symptoms (particularly daytime somnolence and RBD), prodromic motor symptoms related to bradykinesia and demographic and lifestyle factors as well as comorbid diseases may increase the risk of developing PD. To determine the genetic markers related to PD risk, investigators use their own generated data or re-analysis of existing genetic databases on PD patients using GWAS, meta-analysis, and PRS studies. The resulting data suggest that many genes and genetic variants might be related to PD.

AI-driven approaches have proved useful in determining the risk of PD phenoconversion in both general populations and prodromal cohorts. Accelerometry data as well as clinical, genetics and lifestyle features are relevant factors to be included in successful models. Digital

sensors have demonstrated their role in diagnosing RBD as they highly correlate with PSG data which is currently the gold standard to confirm diagnosis. Both RBD and daytime somnolence are prodromal non motor symptoms and thus can be useful tools to detect prodromic populations.

Table 11 Unmet needs and research opportunities in PD Risk.

Unmet needs	Research opportunities
Predicting the risk or phenoconversion to Parkinson's disease	
<p>Most investigation regarding clinical PD risk are based on population studies that are very costly due to the relatively low incidence of PD.</p>	<p>Taking advantage of the widespread use of mobile phones, the AI-PROGNOSIS project will design applications like mAI-Health to detect prodromal and incidental PD. This will be less costly in terms of economic resources, time, etc. than the usual population studies.</p>
<p>Phenotyping prodromal PD subtypes is likely to be important and will help delineate other variables that may influence if and when individuals phenoconvert to clinical PD.</p>	<p>Diagnosing the prodromal phase of PD with high sensitivity and specificity will inevitably lead to a change in paradigm as our current concept of prodromal PD, in fact, becomes PD (Postuma et al., 2018). In the AI-PROGNOSIS project we aim to consider prodromal subtypes using AI models to define subtype-specific markers, thus increasing the diagnostic accuracy of prodromal PD.</p>
<p>The heterogeneity of PD and the influence of comorbidities and environmental exposures present challenges in risk assessment</p>	<p>Digital health technologies enable continuous data collection of lifestyle and clinical factors environmental factors, as well as the monitoring of dBMs such as gait patterns, voice changes, and sleep disturbances. These technologies hold promise for revealing novel risk factors</p>
<p>PD risk to prodromal PD to full clinical PD remains unknown. Further stratification of PD risk states and PD prodromal states would be helpful to select populations that are closer to phenoconversion.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project will use AI-driven approaches to predict PD phenoconversion. Self-reported symptoms may complement objectively assessed signs in the diagnosis of prodromal PD and thus the AI prognosis mAI health app plans to combine these inputs</p>
<p>Genetic studies in a specific population are less costly but limited by small sample size while large GWAS or meta-analysis increase the sample size but are more costly. PRS studies capture the overall genetic background of complex diseases but are also expensive and harder to interpret. As the field of genetic risk factors advances, the genetic risk load and one's individual genetic pathways that contribute to neurodegeneration need to be considered. Gene environment interactions may modulate the effects of many of the risk and prodromal factors that have been established in this review and need to be investigated further.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project includes genetic studies and AI models with large numbers of variables for subjects at risk of developing PD that will be followed clinically and through DAT imaging.</p>
AI-driven approaches	
<p>Existing algorithms have shown promise in identifying individuals at higher risk of developing</p>	<p>These limitations hinder real-world implementation and highlight the need for more</p>

<p>PD, with recent studies demonstrating improved performance. Nonetheless, few models have been adopted in clinical practice due to limited external validity. Many studies lack proper validation, with a significant portion failing to use holdout test sets or adequately report model tuning. Additionally, direct comparisons between models are rare, making it difficult to assess their true effectiveness.</p>	<p>rigorous validation and benchmarking in future research.</p>
<p>The current Bayesian model for predicting PD is based on the independence of the established risk and prodromal markers. However, some of these (e.g., physical inactivity, diabetes or hypotension) may be causally linked to each other or co-occur because of a common pathological process (e.g., RBD and hyposmia). Further investigation of marker clustering and interactions with demographic and genetic variables will probably improve diagnostic accuracy of prodromal PD.</p>	<p>AI-driven approaches can analyse marker clustering and assess interactions with demographic and genetic variables thus improving diagnostic accuracy of prodromal PD</p>
<p>Digital assessment of RBD and Daytime Somnolence</p>	
<p>Studies on the development of reliable sensors that detect REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder in selected populations is needed due to its importance as a prodromal marker. Continuous markers that signal faster progression or advanced prodromal PD states would aid in selecting populations and designing neuroprotective clinical trials.</p>	<p>Digital biomarkers for RBD as designed in the AI-PROGNOSIS project can provide these accurate measures that provide continuous monitoring along time and thus provide prodromal progression markers</p>

2.3 Parkinson’s disease progression and response to medication

2.3.1 Introduction

PD is a neurodegenerative disease and thus, by definition, progresses and the cardinal motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, rigidity, resting tremor and gait problems worsen. With time, the non-motor symptom burden (i.e., dysautonomia, sleep and mood disturbances, cognitive deficits) also increases, effectively leading to diminished quality of life. In addition, PD is a highly heterogeneous disorder and has multiple subtypes stratified according to presentation, medication responsiveness, and progression.

Identifying these subtypes is a priority as it can help estimate disease course and survival, providing a more accurate prognosis at the time of diagnosis. This is significant because PD has a very heterogeneous course in the early to middle stages, with different rates of progression and levels of disability. Initially, subtyping focuses on motor features (Postuma, Fereshtehnejad 2017) but new approaches suggest subtypes defined by both motor and non-motor features, with ongoing refinement through the incorporation of data from imaging, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and genetic biomarkers may be more useful. AI-driven approaches show promise for PD classification, symptom monitoring, and outcome prediction. While early models focused on single-timepoint predictions, such as determining when newly diagnosed PwPD would require symptomatic treatment, more recent models incorporate longitudinal data and weigh medication effects.

Regarding medication response, substitutive dopaminergic therapy effectively treats PD, but as the disease progresses, two key problems arise: 1) the response to medication changes and 2) some symptoms that are resistant to dopaminergic therapy can develop (i.e., imbalance, dysarthria, posterior cognitive dysfunction). As medication response changes due to continuous nigrostriatal degeneration, PD becomes a fluctuating disease. After a mean average of 5-6 years, most patients will encounter times where they do not benefit from dopaminergic therapy called “off periods”. During these episodes, which can happen from one-to-many times a day and for a variable amount of time (from minutes to hours), patients can experience the spectrum of Parkinsonian motor and nonmotor symptoms. At some point in disease progression (about 5.5 years), most patients will also show adverse effects from PD treatment and develop involuntary movements that remind one of chorea and are called dyskinesias. These usually occur in the areas most affected by PD and thus occur in the face, neck, limbs, or trunk. Future research should determine whether digital biomarkers can complement clinician-based decisions and establish personalized response thresholds

PD progression varies among individuals, encompassing slower and faster-progressing forms and more disabling motor fluctuations and dyskinesias.

This review focuses on demographic, clinical, and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression and response to medication. We also focus on the genetic aspects, specifically on those genes with a poorer prognosis in the evolution of the disease. Furthermore, common AI-driven approaches are reviewed for predicting progression factors, alongside digital assessments of symptoms most closely linked to disease evolution: tremor, bradykinesia, dyskinesia, posture, balance, and cognition.

2.3.2 Clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Study selection

The purpose of this part of the review is to summarise studies that identify clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors that predict or determine PD progression, more specifically, those that predict or determine changes in:

- Motor impairment (including freezing and dysphagia)
- Non-motor impairment (including cognition and hallucinations)
- Disability (including falls and functional impairment)
- Medication (e.g., increase in the Levodopa Equivalent Dose)

Only publications reporting validated clinical scales were included. Moreover, studies were required to report longitudinal data with a minimum of 3 months follow-up. Studies focusing on predictive fluid and imaging biomarkers were excluded as they are not in the scope of our project. The study selection criteria are outlined in **Table 12**.

This updated version of the review focuses on studies published between January 2024 and February 2025. The same search terms were used in Rayyan software as in D2.3 employing the following keywords: “Progression” OR “Demographics” OR “Lifestyle” OR “Diabetes” OR “Uric acid” OR “Urban/rural/rurality” OR “Employment” OR “Exercise” OR “Diet” OR “Pesticides” OR “Agriculture/agricultural” OR “Small particles” OR “Farmers” alongside the following keywords: “Prognosis/prognostic” OR “Prediction/predictors” OR “Subtyping/subtypes” OR “Progression”. Using the above keywords, 56 papers were identified and subsequently screened by three independent reviewers. Abstracts and, where required, the full article were read to confirm the articles' eligibility and extract the relevant information. A total of 10 articles fulfilled the eligibility criteria.

Table 12 Selection criteria for clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Item	Definition
Population	Patients with diagnosed PD
Analysis	Longitudinal/prognostic associations between clinical, demographic and lifestyle features and PD progression
Results	Clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	71	56	127
Articles included in literature table	31	10	41

Study characteristics

Out of the selected 31 papers presented in D2.3, 23 focus on clinical factors and 8 on lifestyle factors, and all of them consider demographic factors. A total of 12 papers report data derived from the PPMI database. Except for 2 randomised clinical trials on the effects of exercise (Alagumoorthi et al., 2022; Lauhoff et al., 2013), all other papers report longitudinal, observational designs in cohorts from various countries, ranging from Norway (Hiorth YH et al., 2017) to Spain (Santos et al., 2021) or China (Zhao et al., 2022; Ou et al., 2021). The reported follow-up period ranges from 3 months to up to 10 years. Among the more recent papers screened for this updated review, 10 additional papers were selected, all focusing on clinical and demographic factors (see **Table 13**).

Papers define PD progression in many different ways, but most commonly in terms of decline in motor symptoms as measured with the MDS-UPDRS-III and decline in cognition as measured with the MoCA (Ou et al., 2021). Other ways to define PD progression include time to reach disease milestones (Brumm et al., 2023), cognitive impairment measured with other scales such as the CDR sum of boxes (Meyers et al., 2021), onset of dementia (Compta et al., 2013), changes in the Hoehn & Yahr (H & Y) scale (Ren et al., 2021; Markaki et al., 2021), onset of freezing of gait (Wang et al., 2022) and functional dependency measured with ADL (activities of daily living) (Santos et al., 2021).

Table 13 Studies about clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Benito-Rodriguez et al., 2025	C	111	Median follow-up period 12.2 years (range: 0.03–23.9 years)	Risk of mortality in PD	UPDRS, dementia yes/no (DSM-IV), death certificates (using ICD-10 codes)	PD significantly increases mortality risk, particularly among those with early onset (before 65 years) and dementia. No significant differences in cardiovascular and cerebrovascular mortality between PD patients and controls
Chen et al., 2025	C	328	5 years	To explore the effects of excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) on the development of freezing of gait (FOG) in the patients with PD in a de novo cohort	MDS-UPDRS item 2.13 and 3.11	The EDS group experienced a higher incidence of FOG throughout follow-up. Subgroup analyses based on sex, age, TD/PIGD classification, depressive symptoms, cognitive impairment, revealed no significant interactions between subgroups
Fabbri et al., 2024	C, D	441	> 4 years	To evaluate the risk factors of axial postural abnormalities (PA). PA is associated with advanced stages of PD and greater severity of motor symptoms	MDS-UPDRS 3.13 item ≥ 2	Different features seem to predict the onset of axial PA, including a malignant phenotype, a higher burden of dysautonomic symptoms, an older age at baseline, and a higher severity of motor symptoms. Only older age at disease onset and motor symptom severity survived the multivariate analysis, being the strongest predictors of axial PA development. No influence of dopaminergic therapy on the development of PA was observed.
Gallagher et al., 2024	C, D	PPMI=417 Penn= 389	> 10 years	To determine long-term dementia risk in PD	MoCA score <21, MDS-UPDRS Part I cognition score ≥ 3	The study found that dementia may occur less frequently or develop over a longer period than has generally been assumed based on older studies. Probability of dementia at year 10 disease duration of 15-27%. Increasing age at disease diagnosis, male sex, and lower education level predicted development of dementia, consistent with previous literature.
Kawabata et al., 2024	C	140	5 years	To examine the clinical features of patients with different long-term cognitive trajectories in de novo PD over a 5-year follow-up	≥ 26 on MoCA at 5 five were classified as remitting MoCA decline (RMD). Those with at	The RMD group was associated with lower olfactory scores, whereas PMD was associated with higher depression scores, probable RBD, older age and lower educational attainment

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
					least one abnormal MoCA score before year 5 and remaining below the cutoff at year 5 classified as progressive MoCA decline (PMD)	
Murueta-Goyena et al., 2025	C, D	172	3.9 years	To assess risk factors for falls in early-stage falls-naïve cohort stratified by sex	falls were defined according to UPDRS Item 13	The risk factors for falls differ between female and male early-stage PD patients, In female PD, motor fluctuations and postural stability emerged as significant predictors for falls, whereas in male PD, freezing of gait and postural instability were the primary predictors for falls, although they were nonsignificant.
Shao et al., 2024	C	606	12 years	To examine the predictive modelling of the Walking and Balance Milestone (WBMS)	composite measure of the Walking and Balance Milestone (WBMS)	A predictive model based on five baseline clinical measures (Age, SDMT, PIGD score, MDS-UPDRS-I score, RBD) could effectively estimate the risk of the WBMS in early PD patients.
Sotirakis et al., 2024	C	104	5 years	To examine whether a short sensor-based assessment could predict falls over up to 5 years	Falls	Walking and postural variability measures were key predictors of falls. Adding clinicodemographic data, particularly age, improved model performance.
Wang et al., 2025	C	337	6 years	To predict cognitive trajectories in early PD patients	MOCA	Latent class mixed models (LCMM) identified two longitudinal cognitive subtypes: cognitive stable (276 cases, 81.9%) and cognitive deteriorating (61 cases, 18.1%). The cognitively deteriorating subtype presented poorer baseline cognition, older age, and more severe motor and non-motor symptoms. On biomarkers, the cognitively deteriorating subtype revealed higher serum NFL levels and lower mean striatum DAT uptake. Six baseline clinical variables (age, Letter Number Sequencing score, Symbol Digit Modalities Test score, Benton Judgment of Line Orientation Test score, Hopkins Verbal Learning Test-Revised score, and REM Sleep Behavior Disorder) were selected to construct the

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
						nomogram predictive model which achieved an AUC of 0.92
Zhang et al., 2024	C	422	8 years	To estimate the co-occurrence of ICBs and apathy in early Parkinson's disease (PD) and to determine whether this complex neuropsychiatric condition is an important marker of PD prognoses.	Changes in cognition (MOCA), motor symptoms (MDS-UPDRS part III), and LID	Co-occurrence of ICBs and apathy is common in patients with early PD and may help to identify the risk of L-DOPA-induced dyskinesia development
Alagumoorthi et al., 2022	L	192	0.25	To assess the effectiveness of Wii sports-based strategy training on risk of falling, falls, and quality of life in PD	Fall rate, Berg balance scale, Time up and go test, Parkinson's disease questionnaire 39	A 12 week exercise training using the Wii sports-based strategy decreases the number of fallers, fall rate, measures of risk of falling but did not alter the quality of life in adults with idiopathic PD
Aleksovski et al., 2018	C	254	4	Analyse the clinical progression of PIGD compared to TD	MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, Semantic Fluency, QUIP, GDS, STAI, and SCOPA-AUT	PIGD are characterized by more severe disease manifestations at diagnosis and greater cognitive progression, more frequent hallucinations, psychosis as well as features of dopamine-dysregulation syndrome (DDS) than TD patients
Athauda et al., 2022	L	167	3	Investigate the influence of type 2 diabetes (T2DM) on aspects of disease progression in PD	MDS-UPDRS II-III, NMSS, SE-ADL	T2DM is associated with faster disease progression in PD
Bruce et al., 2023	C	871	2-10	Identifying predictors of disease severity and progression	UPDRS-III, UPDRS-II, H&Y, MMSE	Modelling disease course using multiple objective assessments over an extended follow-up duration identified groups that more accurately reflect differences in PD course, prognosis, and outcomes than assessing single parameters over shorter intervals.
Brumm et al., 2023	C	376	5-10	Time-to-first-event analysis exploring whether baseline characteristics were associated with progression on 25 milestones across six domains ('walking and balance'; 'motor complications'; 'cognition'; 'autonomic dysfunction'; 'functional dependence'; 'activities of daily living')	Reaching 1 milestones (25 total milestones, chosen by a working group of clinical experts)	Baseline features predicting faster time to reaching a milestone included age, greater MDS-UPDRS total scores, higher GeDS-15 depression scores, lower dopamine transporter binding, and lower CSF total α -synuclein levels.

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Bugalho et al., 2021	C	72	4	Address the evolution of motor symptoms (MS) and non-motor symptoms (NMS), predictors of motor, cognitive, disability, and health-related quality of life (HRQL) status	MoCA, MDS-UPDRS II and III, S&E, HY, and EuroQol (VAS and Index)	NMS progresses heterogeneously. The multivariate analysis has shown that S&E and NMSS Domain 4: perception / hallucinations scores are the stronger predictors of HRQL and cognitive dysfunction variation
Cehn et al., 2022	C	420	5	To identify whether the concurrent presence of olfactory dysfunction and probable RBD (pRBD) in PD (Dualhit in PD, PD-DH) is associated with disease progression.	Progression in clinical/neuroimaging	Coexisting pRBD and OD (olfactive dysfunction) in patients with PD may be associated with faster progressions in motor measurement and in cognitive and autonomic symptoms, indicating PD-DH as a more aggressive subtype for PD
Chen et al., 2021	C	128	3-7	To develop a prognostic model for predicting mild cognitive impairment (MCI) in PD-RBD	PD-MCI yes or no	UPSIT, the mean signal and asymmetry index of the putamen on DAT imaging, p-tau/ α -syn and p-tau in CSF, and rs55785911 genotype were predictors of PD-MCI in PD-RBD patients
Chen et al., 2023	C	409	5	To assess the clinical features and explore the underlying biomarkers as predictors of CI in patients with newly diagnosed PD	Progression in clinical/neuroimaging	Cognitive impairment is predicted by: older age, hypertension, baseline lower MoCA scores, MDS-UPDRS III scores, and APOE status
Combs-Miller et al., 2019	L	74	2	To determine factors that predict motor, activity, and participation-based outcomes over two years in exercisers with PD.	Decline in motor activity (exercise behaviour) and quality of life (PDQ-39)	At least one exercise behaviour (minutes of exercise/week, peak rate of perceived exertion (RPE) and mode of exercise) was a significant predictor across most of the models. Younger age, male gender and lower disease severity also significantly predicted better outcomes over time.
Compta et al., 2013	C	27	1.5	To explore the relative and combined longitudinal CSF, neuropsychological and quantitative MRI associations with PD progression to dementia	Dementia yes/no (MDS criteria, MMSE < 24)	Combination of CSF amyloid- β , neuropsychological and cortical thickness biomarkers might provide a basis for dementia-risk stratification and progression monitoring in PD.
Constantini et al., 2023	L	426 de novo untreated PD patients	5	Examine the moderating effects of sex and uric acid on cognitive functions and psychiatric symptoms in early PD depending on motor symptom asymmetry	MDS-UPDRS III, MoCA, Geriatric Depression Scale (GeDS), State Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)	Lower serum UA appears to be associated with better memory performance in LPDf (female left dominant) patients. RPDm (males right dominant) patients exhibited particularly impaired cognitive and psychiatric outcomes.

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Dou et al., 2022	C	415 de novo PD patients	5	Evaluate the progression of non-motor symptoms (cognitive impairment, RBD, and depression) in early PD	UPSIT score, GDS score, QUIP score, MoCA score, CSF A β , α -syn, t-tau, MDS-UPDRS total score, MDS-UPDRS Part III score, ESS score, RBDSQ score, and level of LEDD.	RBD and education levels were associated with depression in PD. Olfactory impairment may be a significant predictor predicting the occurrence of non-motor symptoms in PD, particularly cognitive decline.
Fereshtehneja et al., 2017	C	421 de novo treatment-naive PD patients	>1	Identify distinct Parkinson's disease subtypes to predict progression and develop more efficient personalized care approaches	UPDRS I-III, Schwab and England ADL, MoCA	Diffuse malignant Parkinson's disease progressed faster in overall prognosis, with greater decline in cognition and in dopamine functional neuroimaging after an average of 2.7years
Hayete et al., 2017	C	244	7	To identify predictors of long-term motor and cognitive outcomes and rate of progression in PD	UPDRS III, MoCA, HY, S/E ADL, MMSE, BIDI-II, PDQ39, DAT brain imaging	Functional status (UPDRS parts I and II) at baseline is the strongest predictor of motor and cognitive decline. Older age at baseline was predictive of worse cognitive outcome. Lower DAT uptake at baseline, particularly in the caudate nuclei, and the presence of the minor allele of rs11724635 may also contribute to worse long-term cognitive outcomes.
Hiorth et al., 2017	C	181	7	To examine the frequency, development, concomitants, and risk factors of falls	Score > 1 on UPDRS item 13 (falling unrelated to freezing) or a score > 3 on UPDRS item 14 (falling related to freezing)	Higher age at baseline, PIGD phenotype at 1-year visit, and follow-up time were independent risk factors for incident falls during follow-up
Johansson et al., 2023	C	431	2	Assess the influence of subtyping (mild-motor predominant, intermediate, or diffuse-malignant) on clinical characteristics at baseline and on two-year progression	ROMP, MDS UPDRS I-IV, MoCA, BIDI-II, STAI, QUIP, PDQ39, VIPD-Q	Diffuse-malignant subtype motor symptoms are less lateralized and less confined to either the upper or lower extremities. Also was associated with increased severity of overall motor impairment and faster rates of progression but there were no between-subtype differences in the severity of resting tremor.
Lauhof et al., 2013	L	23	0.27	To establish the effect of a 6-week program of cycle ergometry training on exercise tolerance, balance, activities of daily living (ADL) and	Outcome measures included Six Minute Walk Test, Physiological Cost Index, Berg	Not significantly influence exercise tolerance in this sample, but improved balance, functional ability and PD-related disability were noted

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
				quality of life in individuals with Parkinson's disease. phase. Intervention consisted of 30-min cycle ergometry training once weekly.	Balance Scale, Timed Up and Go Test (TUAG), ADL and mobility sections of UPDRS and the Parkinson's disease questionnaire (PDQ).	
Li et al., 2023	L	501	5	Evaluate the risk of progression according to the proximity to residential and workplace pesticides application.	MMSE \leq 24 and UPDRS \geq 35	Pesticide exposure may be relevant for PD progression. There are implicated ten specific pesticide active ingredients in faster PD motor and non-motor decline
Liu et al., 2021	C	923	3	Investigate the impact of RBD on the longitudinal change of motor and nonmotor symptoms in patients with PD	UPDRS I-IV, Purdue Pegboard test, Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, (HADS) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), MoCa, MMSE	RBD is not just a prodromal symptom. PD with RBD is associated with higher rates of levodopa unresponsive symptoms, including cognitive impairment, PIGD phenotype, gait freezing, and falls.
Markaki et al., 2021	L	224	3	Investigate the association of glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels with motor and cognitive symptom progression	Hoehn and Yahr stage \geq 3 and mild cognitive impairment	Nondiabetic PD patients with low as well as high HbA1c developed balance impairment and reached the endpoint H&Y \geq 3 earlier than non-diabetic patients with euglycemia
Meyers et al., 2021	C	148	4.6	To examine specific symptom progression patterns and possible disease staging in Parkinson disease clinical subtypes ("Motor Only", "Psychiatric & Motor", "Cognitive & Motor")	UPDRS 3 Total, CDR sum of boxes, GDS, NPIQ	Parkinson disease clinical subtypes progress in clear, temporally distinct patterns from one another, particularly in cognitive and psychiatric features.
Ou et al., 2021	C	379	Minimum 1 year	To evaluate whether the control status of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) influences the progression of Parkinson's disease (PD)	UPDRS-III, time to death or time to MoCA 3-point decrease.	Poorly controlled diabetes is an independent risk factor contributing to motor progression in PD (but not cognitive progression nor time to death).
Ren et al., 2021	C	PPMI: 421; LABS-PD: 463	Up to 9 years	Develop a prognostic model using multiple, easily acquired longitudinal measures to predict temporal clinical progression from Hoehn and Yahr	progression to HY 3	Incorporating longitudinal information of multiple clinical measures significantly.

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
				(H&Y) Stage 1 or 2 to Stage 3 in early PD.		
Riboldi et al., 2022	C	423	3	To test the hypothesis that symptoms of dysautonomia and RBD may help to independently prognosticate disease progression.	MDS-UPDRS I, II, III, Total, H&Y, STAI, MOCA, GDS	Dysautonomia symptoms (SCOPA-AUT) predict severe progression of motor and non-motor symptoms better than RBD symptoms (RBDSQ) across the 3-year follow-up period
Santos et al., 2021	C	507	2	To compare the progression of independence in activities of daily living (ADL) in Parkinson's disease (PD) patients versus a control group, as well as to identify predictors of disability progression and functional dependency (FD).	Functional dependency was defined as an S&E-ADL score less than 80%. NMS, QoL, H&Y, UPDRS III-IV, FOGQ, PD-CRS, NMSS, BDI-II, PDSS, NPI, QUIP-RS, PDQ-39, PQ-10, EUROHIS-QOL8	Autonomy for ADL worsens in PD patients compared to controls. Cognitive impairment, gait problems, fatigue, depressive symptoms, more advanced disease, and a non-tremor phenotype are independent predictors of FD in the short-term
Shakya et al., 2022	C	408	3	Identify PD subtypes with distinct disease progression profiles		2 distinct subtypes of Parkinson's disease: (a) mild motor-non-motor subtype (MMNS) with milder motor, non-motor, and neuropsychiatric features and (b) severe motor-non-motor subtype (SMNS) with intense motor and non-motor features by including motor and non-motor features. Both subtypes showed peculiar progression patterns, with SMNS showing a more rapid decline in global cognitive functioning and MMNS showing a more rapid decline in motor functioning.
Urso et al., 2022	C	422	6	To investigate whether PIGD subtype classification or PIGD-related clinical features predict the development of cognitive decline in de novo PD patients.	HVLT recognition discrimination, Benton Judgment of Line Orientation, Letter-Number Sequencing, semantic (animal) fluency test, or Symbol-Digit Modalities	Postural instability, as assessed by MDS-UPDRS III, may serve as a possible indicator of the risk of developing cognitive impairment in de novo PD patients rather than the PIGD phenotype
Wang et al., 2022	C	183	5	To predict the onset of freezing of gait (FoG) in de novo PD patients using a battery of risk factors including clinical data	Onset of FoG	Combining motor and non-motor features including PIGD score, poor cognitive functions and CSF Abeta can identify PD patients with high risk of FoG onset.

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Zhang et al., 2022	L	139	2	To determine the roles of BMI and metabolic status on cognitive outcomes in Parkinson's disease (PD)	MoCA, Hopkins Verbal Learning Test, Benton Judgment of Line Orientation Test (BJLOT), Letter Number Sequencing and Semantic Fluency Test, Symbol Digit Modality Test, MDS-UPDRS III, H&Y stage	Metabolically unhealthy normal weight group showed more cognitive decline in global cognition (MoCA) and visuospatial perception (BJLOT) after a 48-month follow-up
Zhao et al., 2022	C	350	2	To develop a risk prediction model incorporating various elements available through clinical investigations to predict the probability of future onset of FOG in patients with PD	Onset of FoG	Longer disease duration, depressive symptoms and a higher total LEDD are associated with the onset of future FoG.

General discussion

Demographic factors such as age, gender and education were often identified as either independent predictive factors of disease progression (e.g., Brumm et al., 2023; Dou et al., 2022) or as effect modifiers of other clinical or predictive factors (Constantiniet et al., 2023). For instance, in a recent paper, older age at disease onset was the strongest predictor, alongside motor symptom severity, of axial postural abnormalities (Fabbri et al., 2024). Moreover, increasing age at disease diagnosis, male sex and lower education level were confirmed to predict development of dementia, as already suggested in previous literature (Gallagher et al. 2004). The following lifestyle factors emerged as influencing PD progression: exercise (Alagumoorthi et al., 2022; Combs-Miller et al., 2019; Lauhoff et al., 2013), diabetes (Athauda et al., 2022; Ou et al., 2021), unhealthy metabolic status (Zhang et al., 2022), elevated serum uric acid (Constantini et al., 2023), pesticide exposure (Li et al., 2023) and glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels in non-diabetic patients (Markaki et al., 2021).

Clinical factors that have been associated with disease progression in PD include greater motor and/or non-motor symptoms (Chen et al., 2023; Brumm et al., 2023; Urso et al., 2022; Wang. et al., 2022), dysautonomic symptoms (Ribold et al., 2022), functional status (Hayete et al., 2017), RBD (Liu et al., 2021) and postural instability and gait disorders (Aleksovski et al., 2018). Adding to this literature, there is increasing evidence suggesting that PD clinical subtypes characterised by distinct clinical features progress in clear, temporally distinct patterns from one another across motor, cognitive and psychiatric domains, opening new promising avenues for the personalised prognosis of PD patients (Meyers et al., 2021; Shakya et al., 2022; Fereshtehnejad et al., 2017; Johansson et al., 2023). A recent paper described also subtypes in terms of cognitive progression (Zhang et al., 2024). A set of clinical variables (including selected cognitive scores and REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder predicted the progression of patients into one or the other subtype.

2.3.3 Clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with response to dopaminergic medication

The purpose of this specific subsection is to summarize articles that identify the clinical, demographic or lifestyle factors associated or related to the response to dopaminergic treatment, specifically those predicting changes in motor impairment (including freezing or falls), non-motor impairment (including cognition or hallucinations), global disability, the requirement to adjust medication dose (e.g., increase Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose) or the occurrence of medication-related adverse events (especially dyskinesias or impulse control disorders).

Study selection

This updated version of the review focuses on studies published between January 2024 and February 2025. The same search terms were used in Rayyan software as in D2.3 employing the following keywords: 'levodopa' OR 'treatment' OR 'levodopa response' OR 'levodopa sensitivity' OR 'levodopa-induced dyskinesia', alongside 'phenotype' and 'subtype', yielding 36 and 13 articles respectively.

Table 14 outlines the selection criteria of the literature research. Articles related to other conditions like Alzheimer's Disease, Progressive Supranuclear Palsy, or Lewy Body disease were excluded as they were not the focus of the study. Additionally, cross-sectional studies and review articles were also excluded. All studies exclusively focusing on biomarkers and neuroimaging were also excluded.

Subsequently, three independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts, resulting in three articles selected for this updated search.

Table 14 Selection criteria for clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with medication response

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD treated with levodopa or drug naive
Analysis	Associations between clinical, demographic and lifestyle features and levodopa response or adverse events
Results	Therapy adjustment, clinical PD progression or adverse events related to medication

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	131	49	170
Articles included in literature table	8	3	11

Study characteristics

Of the 11 articles included (**Table 15**, 10 are longitudinal prospective registries with a range of follow up from 3 months to 8 years. One of them is a retrospective study based on medical records (Djaldetti et al., 2022).

All the studies included PD patients treated with levodopa except for 2 of them, which discusses de novo patients without treatment (Di Lazzaro et al., 2021; Verschuur et al., 2019) and their progression and response over time. In the study by Cilia et al. (2014), there is a subgroup of 21 patients who were drug naive at baseline, which revealed the median time to the development of motor fluctuations and dyskinesias after initiation of levodopa therapy.

In 3 of the PD populations treated with levodopa, attempts were made to divide them into subtypes, and predictive algorithms were used to determine possible factors affecting medication response (Zhou et al., 2023; Djaldetti et al., 2022; Kohat et al., 2021). In 2 of them, wearable devices are used to compare them with clinical data when deciding to make changes in medication (Joshi et al., 2019; Di Lazzaro et al., 2019).

Only two articles focused on adverse effects (Luca et al., 2021; Cilia et al., 2014), the first discusses levodopa-induced dyskinesias in relation to cognitive aspects, and the second one in relation to treatment and disease duration.

The three articles selected in this updated search focus on adverse effects, mainly Levodopa-Induced Dyskinesia (LID), with particular attention to clinical motor symptoms that are risk factors (Loo et al., 2024) such as affective symptoms like apathy and impulse control behaviors (Zhang et al., 2024). The study by Santos-García et al (2024), aims to measure the impact of LID on quality of life (QoL).

Table 15 Studies about clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with medication response

Author/ Year	Study duration (months)	Sample size	Study aim	Disease duration (years)	Motor severity (UPDRS part III)	Levodopa equivalent diary dose (LEDD)	Key take-aways
Loo et al., 2024	48	953	To explore machine learning (ML) methods using baseline clinical characteristics to predict the development of levodopa-induced dyskinesia (LID) in PD patients	4.5	28.5	> 400	Predictors positively correlated with LID include axial symptoms, freezing of gait, and rigidity in the lower extremities. The risk of developing LID was inversely associated with the occurrence of resting tremors, higher body weight, later onset of PD, and visuospatial abilities
Santos-García et al., 2024	60	672	To analyze the change in the frequency of LID over time, identify LID related factors, and characterize how LID impact on patients' quality of life (QoL).	5.5 ± 4.3	22.7 ± 11.2 (OFF)	580.6 ± 419.9	Factors associated with LID were a longer disease duration and time under levodopa treatment, a higher dose of levodopa, a lower weight and dose of dopamine agonist, pain severity, and the presence of motor fluctuations. LID significantly impacts QoL.
Zhang et al., 2024	96	422	To predict the development of levodopa-induced dyskinesia (LID) using baseline neuropsychiatric symptoms: apathy and Impulse control behaviours (ICBs)	4.9	21.49		Co-occurrence of ICBs and apathy is common in patients with early PD and may help to identify the risk of LID development.
Cilia et al., 2018	Cross sectional analysis and longitudinal analysis (31.2 ± 15.6)	-Cross sectional: 59 Ghanaian PD with levodopa 160 Italian PD with levodopa -Longitudinal	Investigate if the occurrence of motor complications is primarily related to the duration of levodopa therapy or to disease-related factors.	5.8 Ghana PD patients	23.5 Ghana PD patients	365 Ghana PD patients	Motor fluctuations and dyskinesias are not associated with the duration of levodopa therapy, but rather with longer disease duration and higher levodopa daily dose.

Author/ Year	Study duration (months)	Sample size	Study aim	Disease duration (years)	Motor severity (UPDRS part III)	Levodopa equivalent diary dose (LEDD)	Key take-aways
		21 drug-naive PD patients					
Di Lazzaro et al., 2021	36	36 de novo drug-free PD patients	Identify prognostic biomarkers in newly diagnosed PD and quantify therapy-response by technology-based kinematic assessments.	2 ± 2.04	V0: 22.3 ± 9.14, V2: 17.3 ± 6.67, V3: 15.36 ± 6.75	V0: 0, V2: 273.86 ± 110.85, V3: 368.47 ± 132.2	MDS UPDRS III scores decreased significantly after the initiation of the dopaminergic therapy (all tasks except tremor), and clinical improvement was observed in a measurable manner using wearable sensors. No significant differences were recorded in NMSS.
Djaldetti et al., 2022	At least 6	296	Identify factors predictive of long-term response to levodopa.	9.2 ± 4.5	UPDRS I-IV: Pre-levodopa: 27.4 ± 10.4 Post-levodopa: 14.3 ± 6.6	Included only patients who reached a minimal dose of 300 mg of levodopa	Time to initiation of levodopa treatment had no effect on responsiveness except in patients older than 72 years, who were less responsive. The main determinants of variations in levodopa responsiveness are gender, age, and clinical phenotype. Early use of dopamine agonists does not hamper levodopa responsiveness.
Joshi et al., 2019	At least 3	63	Frequency of Personal KinetiGraph (PKG) report use in treatment change decisions	10.8			Global bradykinesia requiring 1 or more doses of levodopa was the most frequently observed subtype in 47% of bradykinesia cases. Predictable dyskinesia requiring one or more treatments represented 44% of dyskinesia cases.
Kohat et al., 2021	36	170	Understand the distribution of PD motor subtypes: tremor dominant (TD) / postural instability gait disorder (PIGD) / indeterminate; and baseline factors that predicted subtype stability.	6.35 ± 6.50	23.51 ± 11.36	233.56 ± 177.72	LEDD is higher in the PIGD subtype. Lower LEDD and higher TD/PIGD ratios are independent predictors of stability of TD subtype
Luca et al., 2021	48	139 LID - 18 LID +	Evaluate possible associations between cognitive dysfunctions and	2.6±2.5 LID - 5.7±3.2 LID +	24.7±12.5 LID - 36.0±14.8 LID +	266.5±285.9 LID - 935.6±443.5 LID +	Impairment of the attention and executive domains increased the risk of dyskinesia

Author/ Year	Study duration (months)	Sample size	Study aim	Disease duration (years)	Motor severity (UPDRS part III)	Levodopa equivalent diary dose (LEDD)	Key take-aways
			development of Levodopa Induced Dyskinesia (LID)				
Verschuur et al., 2019	Early-start group: 20 months treated with levodopa -Delayed-start group: 10 weeks treated with placebo followed by 10 treated with levodopa	PD de novo patients (drug naïve): -222 early-start group -223 delayed-start group	Determining if levodopa also has a disease-modifying effect (measured by the difference in the mean change from baseline to end follow up period on the UPDRS scale.	Diagnosis <2 years	Early start group: 18.4±8.7 Delayed-start group: 19.5±9.4	300 or placebo	Among patients with early PD treatment with levodopa had no disease-modifying effect. The rates of dyskinesia and levodopa-related fluctuations in motor response did not differ significantly between the two groups.
Zhou et al., 2023	60	228	Compare PD subtypes with distinct trajectories of clinical, neurodegeneration events and treatment response	4.29 ± 2.82	22.69 ± 12.97	346.25 ± 272.41	Subtype 1 (with RBD, autonomic dysfunction as early manifestations) had weaker levodopa response and poorer prognosis than subtype 2 (with hyposmia, cognitive impairment, as early manifestations)

General discussion

As with deliverable D2.3, this updated version has faced challenges in identifying relevant articles on predicting response to dopaminergic treatment. It has been particularly challenging to find relevant articles regarding predicting response to dopaminergic treatment. This is probably because most articles related to treatment response were written at the beginning of levodopa introduction in the late 1960's, which is beyond our search filter criteria (2013-2025). Additionally, most articles only focus on levodopa and not on other pharmacological therapies.

Responsiveness to levodopa varies greatly among patients with PD, and the factors that affect it are poorly defined. The aim of the review was to identify these intrinsic factors related to demographic, clinical, or lifestyle features.

The resulting data suggest that all patients experience an improvement in motor impairment when taking levodopa, with tremor showing the smallest improvement. In general, all patients were assessed using the UPDRS-III to measure motor performance and there seems to be a good correlation with wearable sensors to predict response or progression (Joshi et al., 2019). As PD advances, axial symptoms like freezing of gait, postural changes and loss of balance respond less to levodopa (Kohat et al., 2021).

When trying to stratify patients with a poorer response to medication, it appears that those who show REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) or early autonomic symptoms, tend to have a worse progression of the disease and weaker levodopa response (Zhou et al., 2023).

The article by Djaldetti et al. (2022), suggested that for older patients (72 years or more), responsiveness was better when levodopa was initiated early after symptom onset, whereas for younger patients, delaying treatment was less critical in terms of levodopa responsiveness. Apart from age, there seems to be variation in response based on the clinical phenotype, with the PIGD subtype requiring higher doses (Kohat et al., 2021). The longitudinal analysis by Cilia et al. (2014) revealed that the median time to develop motor fluctuations and dyskinesias was 5.5 for motor fluctuations, and 6.5 for dyskinesias independent of when levodopa was started. It also showed that motor fluctuations and dyskinesias are not associated with the duration of levodopa therapy, so delaying its use for this reason is not justified. Recent studies from 2024 have further explored factors related to levodopa-induced dyskinesia (LID). Loo et al. (2024) found that predictors positively correlated with LID include axial symptoms, freezing of gait, and rigidity in the lower extremities. Santos-García et al. (2024) emphasized that LID significantly impairs quality of life. Meanwhile, Zhang et al. (2024) reported that the co-occurrence of impulse control behaviors and apathy is common in early Parkinson's disease and may help identify patients at higher risk of developing LID.

2.3.4 Genetic markers associated with PD progression and medication response

A genetic marker is a DNA sequence with a known physical location on a chromosome. These genetic markers can help identify a single gene or a group of genes that contribute to the development of an inherited disease (Davey et al., 2011). The review aims to report genetic markers associated with PD progression and medication response through GWAS, and meta-analysis studies published between January 1st, 2024 and February 1st, 2025.

Study selection

Within the context of the Rayyan software, “dopaminergic medication”, OR “longitudinal”, OR “progression”, AND “gene” OR “genetic”, OR “GWAS” OR “PRS” OR “polygenic risk score” OR “SNP” OR “polymorphism” OR “genetic association” keywords were used. These keywords along with “dopaminergic medication,” progression” and “longitudinal” yielded 14, 186, 64 records, respectively. While the second search yielded 93, 92 and 14 records,

respectively. Two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. A total of 439 studies were excluded as they conveyed i) incorrect publication type (e.g., case reports and reviews), ii) investigation other neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's Disease, Huntington's Disease, Multiple Sclerosis and Progressive Supranuclear Palsy and iii) not relevant to PD, genetics or did not have clear genetic or statistical results. The full text was read to confirm the eligibility of the article, where required. All PRS studies, as well as all GWAS and meta-analysis studies, only those with a significant statistical association of p-values less than 5×10^{-8} and 5×10^{-6} , respectively, were included. Thus, a total of thirty-five studies were included in the previous report. Through the second search, five additional studies were added, which were recorded and summarized in the updated version. **Table 16** outlines the study eligibility criteria implemented in the previous and current systematic review. A paper was considered eligible if:

A) Study participants were patients with PD before diagnosis, early or late onset, naïve drug free patients or individuals with clinical diagnoses of prodromal PD.

AND

B) In the case of dopaminergic medication response, a Levodopa dose was required for PD individuals irrespective of PD stage and onset.

AND

C) Disease progression and longitudinal outcome were also investigated, if possible, in terms of clinical genetic markers and Levodopa response.

Table 16 Selection criteria for genetic markers associated with PD progression and medication response

Item	Definition
Population	PD patients
Outcome	Genetic associations related to Levodopa dose, PD Progression and Longitudinal outcome
Results	Clinical genetic markers related to progression and longitudinal outcome of PD or levodopa response

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	264	199	463
Articles included in literature table	35	5	40

Study characteristics

Five studies met the inclusion criteria and included GWAS, proteogenomic and meta-analysis data. Among the reviewed studies, two reported Levodopa response, whereas the remaining studies failed to report Levodopa dose in terms of clinical genetic markers, PD progression and longitudinal PD outcomes. Fourteen studies used open-source data (e.g. PPMI and NS-PARK), the remaining twenty-six studies out of the forty studies within the review retained their own experimental design and data collection approaches. Eleven studies included clinical genetic makers in relation to Levodopa response.

Clinical genetic markers, levodopa, progression and longitudinal outcomes of PD

Table 17 summarises the clinical genetic markers, Levodopa response, progression and longitudinal outcomes in PD. The included studies present diverse methodologies at the experimental, bioinformatic and statistical level, capturing genes and their biological role in influencing progression and longitudinal outcomes of PD, while also investigating how Levodopa response may affect PD patients. Studies identified via an updated search for D2.4 are presented first in the table. The updated search identified five new studies.

Table 17 Studies investigating the association between the genetic markers and PD progression and medication Response. Studies highlighted in grey are from previous systematic review.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Greenberg et al., 2024	Study Cohort (n=100): GBA-PD : (n=21), Non-GBA-PD (n=79). PPMI Cohort-Baseline Visit (n=420): GBA-PD : (n=54), Non-GBA-PD (n=366). 12 month Visit (V12) (n=307): GBA-PD : (n=36), Non-GBA-PD : (n=269)	5 years	GBA-PD : 5.5 (0-40), Non-GBA-PD : 6.2 (0-26)	NR	Study Cohort-GBA pathogenic variants : N409S, R535H, L29Afs*18, H294Q, E365K, Q182, W387G. PPMI Cohort-GBA pathogenic variants : N409S, L483P, A495P, G154R, IVS2 + 1G > A, L29Afs*18, R502C, R83C, R159W, E365K, T408M, I528L, R78C (NR)	Non-GBA-PD subjects displayed statistically significantly higher scores on the MDS-UPDRS part I. Non-motor symptoms showed a trend towards higher rates among non-GBA-PD subjects, the difference was only statistically significant for urinary symptoms, and the only statistically significant difference in the PPMI cohort was frequency of hallucinations.
Hwang et al., 2024	Korean Sporadic PD (n=1,070)	5 years	Female : 5.45±4.79, Male : 5.12±3.97	NR	rs2134545 (p=1.89x10 ⁻⁸), rs4366309 (p=8.68x10 ⁻⁸)	rs2134545 and rs4366309 are likely functional variants that influence AAO in PD. rs2134545 reduced average AAO by 3.47 years, and variant in rs4366309 delayed average AAO by 3.05 years.
Lian et al., 2024	PPMI (Analysis I) : (n=516), PDBP (Analysis I) : (n=340), PPMI (Analysis II) :	Follow-up: 36 months	NR	PPMI (Analysis II) : 124.2 (321.0)	APOE4, GBA, LRRK2, SNCA, PRS90 (NR)	PRS90 for PD is linked to favorable short-term outcomes, characterized by either symptom improvement or stability, in both motor and non-motor aspects.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
	(n=361). HC: (n=168)					
Menon et al., 2024	MJFF: (n=253), NGC/NS-Park: (n=227), GPIp: (n=167)	NR	MJFF: 18.4±11.7, NGC/NS-Park: 16.0±11.1, GPIp: 20.2±14.6	MJFF: NA NGC/NS-Park: 430.2±317.8, GPIp: 587.7±574.2	Variants not previously identified: Q100H, P159L, H303Y, R275Q, P133Qfs44*, c.534+3, C166Hfs, C166Y, C352R, c.388_38 9insCAC (p.Asp13 0delinsA laHis), D53E, c.259del (p.Asp87 ThrfsTer 16), H433P, I29Cfs*27, N428S, P132Tfs*9, Q100*, Q376Sfs *59, C212G, A>G, C150* (NR)	Frequent variant overall was an exon 3 deletion (n = 145, 12.3%), followed by the p.R275W substitution (n = 117, 10%). Exon3, RING0 protein domain and the ubiquitin-like protein domain were mutational hotspots with 31%, 35.4% and 31.7% of index cases presenting mutations in these regions, respectively. The presence of a frameshift or structural variant was associated with a 3.4 ± 1.6 years or a 4.7 ± 1.6 years earlier age at onset of PRKN-PD.
Torshizi et al., 2024	PD: (n=2,864), Controls: (n=158,876)	NR	NR	NR	Meta-analysis of UKB and FinnGen: GBA (p=9.7E-19) STK39 (p=8E-11), TMEM175 (p=1.25E-12), SNCA (3E-12), HLA-DRB1 (p=2.8E-09), LRRK2 (p=7.16E-12), HIP1R (4.78E-8), GCH1 (p=3.4E-80), KANSL1 (p=1.4E-18), NECTIN2 (p=1.7E-09). PD SNPs associated with proteins (Network Analysis): rs2230288-T-EFNA (p=2.4E-10), rs34311866-C-Alpha-L-Iduronidase (p=4.6E-08), rs10847839-HIPIR (p=6.7E-30). Plasma proteins with MR & co-localization (Network and DEG Analysis): PYDC1 (p=8.5E-09), PRSS8 (p=8.8E-09), CTF1 (p=1.1E-08), CXCL10 (p=2.03E-07).	LGALS3, CSNK2A1, SMPD3, STX4, APOA2, PAFAH1B3, LDLR, HSPB1, BRK1 potential roles in disease pathogenesis.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Abdelmoaty et al., 2022	PD =5	12 month/ 2 & 6 post-treatment	8±5	<p>Carbidopa-Levodopa 25–100 mg, (n=3)</p> <p>Carbidopa-Levodopa 50–200 mg (n=1)</p> <p>Carbidopa-Levodopa 23–95 mg (n=1)</p>	<p>Downregulation HMOX1 (p=3.47x10-8) 2 months & (p=9.58x10-12) 6 months, TLR2 (p=0.0348) (2 months) & TLR8 (p=1.66x10-6) 6 months, RELA (p=0.0147) & IKBKG (p=00146) 2 months, LRRK2 (p=8.54x10-6) (2 month) (p=9.38x10-4) (6 month).</p> <p>Upregulation ATG3 (p=0.0279) ATG7 (p=0.0428) GABARAPL2 (p=0.0096) Expression of potential gene or protein biomarkers with UPDRS III scores: LRRK2 (n.s) HMOX1 (p=0.013), TLR2 (p=0.005) (decreased gene expression & improved motor function). Indirect correlation change in UPDRS III scores & ATG7 (p=5.1x10-7). LRRK2 & HMOX1 effect on UPDRS III score change (p=0.0336), LRRK2 & TLR2 (p=0.0012), TLR2 had a greater effect (p=0.0018). LRRK2 & ATG7 strong potential to affect changes in UPDRS III score (p=1.12x10-6), LRRK2 & ATG7 (p=1.3x10-6) predict a lower UPDRS score from baseline score. TLR2 & TLR8 (p=0.0009), TLR2 showing a greater effect (p=0.0002), TLR2 & ATG7 expression was significantly linked to the UPDRS III score (p=1.1x10-5), ATG7 having the greater influence (p=0.0012), combined effect of TLR8 & ATG7 correlated with the change in UPDRS score (p=3.8x10-6), ATG7 producing a greater diminution effect (p=6.8x10-7) a 1-fold increase in ATG7 expression decreased UPDRS III score</p>	<p>Sargramostim induces monocyte antioxidant and anti-inflammatory autophagy functions were differentially expressed by 2 and 6 months.</p> <p>LRRK2, HMOX1 & TLR2 proteins were significantly downregulated in 60%–80% of patients at 2 and 6 months of Sargramostim treatment.</p> <p>Downregulation of TLR8 & RELA proteins after 2 months in 60% (3/5) of patients with significant downregulation in 1/3 of patients for each protein.</p> <p>Monocyte profiles & both clinical motor function & disease progression during immune modulatory therapy</p>

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					change by 4 points. 7 variables showed a strong correlation on score changes from baseline (p=10x10 ⁻⁵). HMOX1, TLR8, & ATG7, (p=2.0x10 ⁻⁶) accounted for a score change from baseline strongest effect on change from UPDRS baseline was provided by ATG7 (p=2.1x10 ⁻⁶).	
Blauwen et al., 2019	IPDGC =17996 23andMe =10572	-	-	-	SNCA (rs356203) (p=2.00E-12) GAK, TMEM175 (rs34311866) (p=1.00E-08)	Not all PD risk loci influence AAO with significant differences between risk alleles for AAO
Cacabelos et al., 2020	(N=127). DF-PD =81 CF-PD =46	-	DF-PD & CF-PD	Atremorine (5g, p.o)	rs460000 (SLC6A3) (DA transporter): SLC6A3-C/C (p<0.05) A/A (p=<0.05), A/C (p<0.02), C/C (p<0.001), SLC6A2 (NA transporter): SLC6A2-A/A (p< 0.05), A/G (p<0.001), G/G (p<0.04). rs2020934 (SLC6A4) SLC6A4-A/A: (p<0.001), A/C (p<0.01), C/C (p<0.001) Dopamine (basal) (pg/ml) (p<0.001) Total 441.56±146.15 DF 12.14±0.34 CF 1221.53±389.94 Dopamine (treatment) (pg/ml) (p<0.001) Total 9847.21±1912.03 DF 6463.21±1306.90 CF 16028.54±4783.98	Basal plasma levels of DA lower in DF-PD than CT-PD. Low basal DA levels in SLC6A3-C/C carriers & DA response to Atremorine was significant in A/A, A/C, C/C carriers. Variations in both NA & DA transporters affect the response of DA to Atremorine. CF-PD patients show higher basal DA level after 12 h fasting. Females showed lower basal DA levels than males. DF-PD patients who take Atremorine (first time) showed an increase in DA levels.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
						<p>CT-PD showed an increase in DA levels.</p> <p>Atremorine enhances in dopaminergic effects of conventional anti-PD drugs.</p> <p>Atremorine influences neurotransmitter levels (catecholamines) & hormones regulated by DA (prolactin) with no effect on 5-HT or histamine synthesis and release</p>
Cacabelos et al., 2021	DF-PD & CF-PD=127	-	-	Atremorine (5g, p.o)	<p>ACMSD-T/T (p < 0.001)</p> <p>BCKDK-A/G (p < 0.003)</p> <p>BCKDK-A/A (p < 0.02)</p> <p>BCKDK-G/G (p < 0.001)</p> <p>GCH1-A/A (p < 0.05)</p> <p>GCH1-A/G (p < 0.001)</p> <p>GCH1-G/G (p < 0.007)</p> <p>GPNMB-A/A (p < 0.001)</p> <p>GPNMB-G/G (p < 0.007)</p> <p>(NUCKS1-T/T) (p < 0.02)</p> <p>NUCKS1-C/C (p < 0.001)</p> <p>LRRK2-A/A (p < 0.001)</p> <p>SNCA-A/G (p < 0.004)</p> <p>NMs (p < 0.001)</p> <p>IMs (p < 0.001)</p> <p>PMs (p < 0.001)</p> <p>UMS (p < 0.001)</p> <p>SOD2-T/T (p < 0.001) SOD2-C/T (p < 0.001), SOD2C/C carriers</p>	<p>Atremorine induced Dopamine response in PD patients.</p> <p>Several metabolic genes (CYP2D6, CYP2C19, CYP2C9, CYP3A4) transporter genes (ABCB1, SLCOB1) show differential DNA methylation after Atremorine administration</p>

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(p < 0.001) STP1B-CT (p < 0.001) ABCB1 (p < 0.001) SLC6A2-G/G (p < 0.04) SLC6A3-C/C (p < 0.001) SLC6A3A/C (p < 0.02) APOE-3/3 (p < 0.01) APOE-2/3 (p < 0.001) APOE-2/4 (p < 0.02) APOE-3/4 (p < 0.001) DRD2-G/G (p < 0.005) CYP2C19-NMs & UMs (p < 0.05) CYP2C9-NMs (p < 0.01) CYP3A4-PMs (p < 0.01)	
Cao et al., 2021	PD patients =365	Not provided Follow up 5 years	Rapid motor progression	-	Baseline autonomic dysfunction was associated with rapid progression (p=0.039). rs6808178 (LINC00693) associated with faster motor progression. (p=0.0004) after correction of multiple testing (p<0.0011).	Genetic & clinical features together demonstrated more predictivity towards fast motor progression. (LINC00693 rs6808178, CHMP2B rs115185635, IP6K2 rs12497850, TMEM175 rs34311866, OGFOD2 rs11060180, CAB39L rs9568188, and DLG2 rs3793947 were associated with rapid motor deterioration in PD.
Cha et al., 2020	Japanese. Responders (Zonisamide, Levodopa) =67 Poor Responders	-	-	Responders 469.9 (164.3) Poor Responders	4.00E-08	MDM4 (rs16854023) showed genome-wide significant association with reduced "off" time. Carriers of responsive genotype showed >7-fold decrease in mean "off" time compared to noncarriers.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
	(Zonisamide, Levodopa) =133			s 498 (170.9)		MDM4 encodes a negative regulator of p53. The association between improved motor fluctuation and MDM4 upregulation implies that p53 inhibition may prevent dopaminergic neuron loss and consequent motor symptoms.
Chaet et al., 2020	Japanese. Responders (Zonisamide, Levodopa) =67 Poor Responders (Zonisamide, Levodopa) =133	-	-	Responders 469.9 (164.3) Poor Responders 498 (170.9)	4.00E-08	MDM4 (rs16854023) showed genome-wide significant association with reduced “off” time. Carriers of responsive genotype showed >7-fold decrease in mean “off” time compared to noncarriers. MDM4 encodes a negative regulator of p53. The association between improved motor fluctuation and MDM4 upregulation implies that p53 inhibition may prevent dopaminergic neuron loss and consequent motor symptoms.
Chung et al., 2021	Norwegian ParkWest Study PD =171 APOEε4- =114 APOEε4+ =57 MAPT-H2 =38 MAPT-H1/H1- =133 COMTMet =134 COMTVal/Val =37	7 years/3 clinical visits	Early-stage PD	-	<i>COMT</i> ¹⁵⁸ Val/Val & faster decline in executive function (p=0.028) verbal learning & memory (p=0.029) & visuospatial skills (p=0.027) <i>BDNF</i> , <i>MAPT</i> & <i>APOE</i> genotypes were not significantly associated with longitudinal changes in individual cognitive domains. <i>APOE</i> -ε4 carriers had increased risk of mild cognitive impairment & dementia (OR 3.03; p = 0.006)	<i>COMT</i> predicted to a decline in executive function, verbal learning & visuospatial skills. <i>BDNF</i> , <i>MAPT</i> & <i>APOE</i> were not linked with changes in individual cognitive domains. <i>APOE</i> ε4 carriers are at 3-times increased risk of developing MCI or dementia.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
	BDNFMet =60 BDNFVal/Val n=111					
Dehestani et al., 2022	German GWAS Dataset PD=371 HC= 249	-	-	-	(p=2.00E-02)	PRS significantly predicts the PD status. Mito PRS are significantly associated with later age of onset in PD patient.
Fischer et al., 2022	N=217, Placebo =112 Tocopherol =105	-	Early PD stages (I & II)	-	SNPs altered BDNF transcript expression in brain regions. Caudate nucleus: rs1157659 (p=0.0051), rs11030094 (p=0.0059), rs6265 (p=0.0067). Survival analysis for time to needing dopaminergic therapy rs10501087: T/T (p=0.002) (HR: 28.3) &T/C (p=0.004) (HR:7.6) rs11030094: A/A (p=0.03) (HR:2.5), A/G (p=0.03) (HR:2.0) rs1491850 (time >12 months) T/T (p=0.02) (HR: 5.1) & T allele carrier vs C/C (p=0.04) (HR:3.5)	rs10501087,rs1491850 & rs11030094 associated with a slower rate of PD progression in unmedicated state. rs908867 & rs1157659 did not alter time to initiate Levodopa
Ghit & El Deeb et al., 2022	N=35 PD =20 HC =15	1 year/Not mentioned	-	Treatment duration: 3.9 ± 3.4	Cytokines (IL10, IL12, & TNF-α) & α-Synuclein in PD patients significantly higher than healthy individuals (p < 0.0001). miR-214, miR-221, miR-141) as well as antioxidants (UA, PON1, and ARE) in PD patients were lower than HC (p < 0.0001). Correlation among serum levels of immune & non-immune markers in PD patients and HC. Positive correlation IL10 & IL12	Increased sera levels of cytokines in PD patients as well as a positive correlation among them. A significant increase in sera levels of α-synuclein is associated with a decrease in miR-214 (regulates its gene expression). A decrease in sera levels of miR-221, miR-141, UA, PON1, & ARE, a role against oxidative stress. to correctly predict disease state and progression. A

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(p<0.0001) TNF-α & IL10 (p=0.002) TNF-α & IL1 (p<0.0001), Antioxidant enzymes PON1 & ARE (p=0.002). Negative correlation serum levels of miR-221 & TNF-α (p=0.01)	mix of non-invasive biomarkers is required.
Gu et al., 2022	PPMI PD =367	-	Low risk 7.02 ± 6.65, High risk 7.86 ± 9.28	-	Younger age at onset in patients with PD PRS 1 (26 SNPs) (p=3.00E-03) , PRS2 (23 SNPs) (p=3.00E-03) More extensive WM microstructural degeneration (High PRS) (p<0.05), Younger age of onset than that in low-PRS individuals (High PRS) (p=4.30E-02) Lower H&Y stage than the low-PRS group (High PRS) (p=4.00E-02)	PD-associated polygenic load aggravates the WM microstructural degeneration and these changes may lead to poor cognition with continuous dopamine depletion. This study provides advanced evidence that combined with cumulative PRS and DTI methods may predict disease progression in PD patients.
Hayete et al., 2017	Newly diagnosed PD patients =244	Follow-up 7 years	Since Diagnosis LABS-PD Baseline 0.8 (0.8) Baseline data for model 0.8 (0.8) Last follow-up 7.8 (0.8)	-	rs11724635 with MoCA scores, year 5 (p = 2.7E-5) year 6 (p= 0.053) & year 7 (p= 0.0424), ApoE isoforms, MAPT, SNCA (n.s)	rs11724635 associated with faster cognitive progression. Predictors of cognitive function were: UPDRS (parts I, II), S/E-ADL, striatal dopamine transporter binding & SNP rs11724635 in (BST1). Lower DAT uptake at baseline in the caudate nuclei & presence of rs11724635 may contribute to worse long-term cognitive outcomes.

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He et al., 2021	N=103 PD Stage II =8 Stage III =42 Stage IV =22 & =72 HC =31	-	Stage II Stage III Stage IV	-	<p>Distinguished stages II, III & IV from controls. hsa-miR-374a-5p Stage II: (AUCs: 0.758) (p=0.026), Stage III: (AUC: 0.780) (p=0.0001) Stage IV: (AUCs :0.798) (p=0.0012) hsa-miR-374b-5p Stage II: (AUCs: 0.798) (p=0.0101) Stage III: (AUCs: 0.742) (p=0.0004) Stage IV: (AUCs: 0.761) (p=0.0013). Distinguished stage II from control, stage III and stage IV. hsa-miR-199a-3p Control: (AUCs:0.738) (p=0.0402), Stage III: (AUCs: 0.729), (p=0.0416) Stage IV: (AUCs: 0.756) (p=0.0348). Distinguished stage III from control, stage II and stage IV. hsa-miR-28-5p Control: (AUCs:0.746) (p=0.0004) Stage II: (AUCs: 0.789) (p=0.0103), Stage IV: (AUCs: 0.738) (p=0.0019). Distinguished stage IV from control, stage II and stage III. hsa-miR-22-5p Control: (AUCs:0.817) (p<0.0001) Stage II: (AUCs: 0.773) (p=0.0244) Stage III: (AUCs: 0.700) (p=0.0089) hsa-miR-151a-5p Control: (AUCs: 0.741), (p=0.0031) Stage II: (AUCs:0.796) (p=0.0147) Stage III: (AUCs: 0.708) (p=0.0066), hsa-miR-29a-3p Control: (AUCs: 0.743) (p=0.0027) Stage II: (AUCs: 0.813) (p=0.0056) Stage III: (AUCs:0.712), (p=0.0056)</p>	hsa-miR-374a-5p, hsa-miR-374b-5p, hsa-miR-199a-3p, hsa-miR-28-5p, hsa-miR-22-5p & hsa-miR-151a-5p are potential biomarkers for stage-specific diagnosis of PD

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Henderson et al., 2021	N=30 PD =15 HC =15	-	Early PD stage	-	<p>FOSB (p=4.93E-05) ETV7 (p=4.93E-05) TUBB6 (p=7.32E-05) PC (p=1.70E-05) ZDHHC11 (p=9.27E-05) KLC3 (p=9.55E-05) LINC00265 (p=7.21E-06) TARS2 (p=7.31E-05) ZNF142 (p=4.28E-05) RPS24 (p=2.21E-05) CDK14 (p=1.06E-04) CLEC2B (p=5.84E-05) RPL34 (p=9.98E-05) BCL2A1 (p=6.74E-05) TCF4 (p=8.46E-05) COMMD6 (p=5.25E-05) LY96 (p=2.58E-05) LSM3 (p=2.59E-05) S100AB (p=1.11E-05) LSMEM1 (p=3.36E-05) COX6C (p=1.01E-04) COX7B (p=9.97E-05) RCAN1 (p=2.59E-05) RNF175 (p=6.96E-05) RAD51C (p=3.18E-05) FAM200B (p=4.75E-05) Inc-PDK3-1 (p=8.66E-05) GLIP41 (p=4.59E-05) KIN (p=1.09E-04) NPEPPS (p=1.07E-04) Hypermethylated DMR2 (RNF5P1, RNF5, AGPAT1) (p=0.0004), DMR4 (LOC151174, LOC643387) (p=0.0006), DMR5 (VTRNA2-1) (p=0.0009) DMR6 (SPEF2) (p=0.0013) DMR7 (TYW3, CRYZ) (p=0.0014) DMR17 (KLF14) (p=0.0057) DMR16 (PM20D1) (p=0.0065) DMR22 (GPR75, LOC100202652) (p=0.0068) DMR19 (ARHGAP22) (p=0.0074)</p>	<p>Differentially expressed genes were involved in transcription & mitochondrial function</p> <p>PD methylation profiles were readily distinguishable from healthy controls.</p> <p>Differentially methylated regions (DMRs) were functionally varied, including near transcription factor nuclear transcription factor Y subunit alpha (NFYA), receptor tyrosine kinase DDR1, RING finger ubiquitin ligase (RNF5), acetyltransferase AGPAT1, and vault RNA VTRNA2-1. Expression quantitative trait methylation sites were found at long non-coding RNA PAX8-AS1 & transcription regulator ZFP57 among others. Functional epigenetic modules were highlighted by IL18R1, PTPRC, and ITGB2.</p>

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					DMR20 (DUSP19) (p=0.0078) DMR25(SMC1B, RIBC2) (p=0.0151), DMR28 (UBLCP1) (p=0.0158), DMR1 (NFYA) (p=0.0003) DMR8 (RNF39) (p=0.0005) DMR10 (C6orf25) (p=0.0018), DMR10 (C1orf65) (p=0.0025) DMR9 (DDX43) (p=0.0025) DMR13 (HOXA4) (p=0.00031) DMR14 (HLA-DPB2) (p=0.00031) Hypomethylated DMR15 (CYP1A1) (p=0.00052) DMR18 (DDR1) (p=0.00075) DMR21 (KCNAB3) (p=0.00081) DMR23 (C3orf24) (p=0.0105) DMR24 (PSMA8) (p=0.0140) DMR31 (C1orf11) (p=0.0168) DMR27 (NAPRT1) (p=0.0178) DMR29 (AKR1E2) (p=0.0205) DMR30 (TILL10) (p=0.0227) cis-eQTM (CpG) (PAX8-AS1): cg19083407 (p=1.53E-10),cg23564664 (p=5.13E-10),cg07594247 (p=9.29E-10) cg17445212 (p=1.10E-09), cg12889195 (p=1.93E-09),cg07772999 (p=7.87E-09),cg11763394 (p=9.34E-09),cg21550016 (p=9.97E-09),cg02675527 (p=1.10E-08), cg21482265 (p=1.69E-08) (ZFP57): cg15708526 (p=3.34E-09), cg07134666 (p=5.11E-09), cg15570556 (p=6.24E-09), cg16885113 (p=1.29E-08),	

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					cg08022281 (p=1.69E-08), cg004071440 (p=3.43E-08), cg11383134 (p=5.22E-08), cg03449857 (p=5.68E-08), cg20228636 (p=7.76E-08). trans-eQTM (CLEC11A) : cg13291296 (p=6.34E-11), (SIPA1L2) : cg11460641 (p=8.30E-12), cg26287080, (p=2.58E-11), cg21622464 (p=5.13E-11), cg24297509 (p=1.42E-10),cg26914392 (p=1.76E-10) (TRBV19) : cg11199182 (p=8.30E-11), cg25335258 (p=1.22E-10), cg11342941 (p=2.03E-10), cg17153055 (p=2.12E-10) (RPL29) : cg26835568 (p=4.52E-12) cg01772663 (p=2.13E-11), cg02810976 (p=1.04E-10), g21475003 (p=1.16E-10),cp08272591 (p= 1.19E-10), cg06312137 ,cg00266592 (p=5.70E-10),cg25593954 (p=1.49E-10),cg12067423 (p=1.53E-10),cg02942845 (p=2.40E-10) (TRBV11-2) : cg16515546 (p=1.40E-13),cg13291296 (p=7.40E-12),cg21950182 (p=4.00E-11), cg17731973 (p=6.65E-11), cg156614872 (p=7.48E-11), cg06809285 (p=1.31E-10), cg21028260 (p=2.02E-10), cg18696632 (p=3.40E-12), cg18803655 (p=4.96E-12), cg21475544 (p=6.74E-12), cg21300072 (p=2.44E-10), cg01840459 (p=2.26E-10) (RPL26L1) : cg08029281 (p=2.22E-10) (GEMIN8) : cg22128645 (p=1.41E-10), (HSPB11): cg08029281 (p=4.83E-11) (PCSK1N) : cg25751895 (p=1.64E-10) (ACOT11) : cg24512544 (p=5.29E-11)	

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					(TOMM7): cg08029281 (p=3.71E-10) (TTN-AS1): cg22793142 (p=1.94E-10) (DND1P1): cg12609785 (p=1.95E-10)	
Hill-Burns et al., 2016	PD =431 Replication PD =737	-	-	-	LHFPL2 (rs344650) (p=1.00E-11) TRPS1 (rs74335301) (p=3.00E-06) KLHDC1 (rs79503702) (p=5.00E-08) TPM1 (rs117267308) (p=9.00E-11)	LHFPL2 was associated with earlier onset by 12.33 years. NGRC, 8.03 years in replication & 9.79 years in the combined data. TPM1 variant was associated with earlier onset by 15.30 years in NGRC, 9.29 years in replication, & 12.42 [years in the combined data. Neither LHFPL2 nor TPM1 was associated with age-at-onset in non-familial PD.
Jian et al., 2022	GSE7621 PD =16 HC =9, GSE20141 PD =10 HC=8 GSE49036 PD =15 HC =9 GSE20164 PD =6 HC =5 GSE20163 PD =8 HC =9 GSE20292 PD =11 HC =18 GSE34865 PD=0 HC =57 GSE166024 PD =14	-	-	-	16 classifiers, including <i>MAP4K4</i> , <i>LRP10</i> , <i>UCHL1</i> , <i>PAM</i> , <i>RIT2</i> , <i>SNCA</i> , <i>GCH1</i> , <i>DDIT4</i> , <i>RGS4</i> , <i>MAPK9</i> , <i>CAV1</i> , <i>RELA</i> , <i>DUSP1</i> , <i>ATP6V1G2</i> , <i>ATF4</i> & <i>ISCU</i> , greater than (AUC=0.6), indicating that their featured genes had a promising potential to characterize PD. MAP4K4, LRP10 and UCHL1 (AUC=0.7) the classifiers featured by ferroptosis-related genes DDIT4, RGS4, MAPK9 and RELA (AUC=0.7). Hazards ratio: DDIT4 (p=0.02) RGS4 (p=0.011) RELA (p=0.045) SNCA (p=0.475) CAV1 (p=0.006) GCH1 (p=0.094) UCHL1 (p=0.178) LRP10 (p=0.068)	16 DEGs were singled out due to comparable AUC (>0.6) in random forest classifiers, including seven PD-related genes (MAP4K4, LRP10, UCHL1, PAM, RIT2, SNCA, GCH1) & nine ferroptosis-related genes (GCH1, DDIT4, RGS4, MAPK9, CAV1, RELA, DUSP1, ATP6V1G2, ATF4 and ISCU). Cox model featured by an eight-gene signature, including four PD-related genes (SNCA, UCHL1, LRP10, and GCH1) & four ferroptosis-related genes (DDIT4, RGS4, RELA, and CAV1), & validated it successful in an independent dataset, indicating

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	HC =0 GSE114517 PD =17 HC =12					that it would be an effective tool for clinical research to predict PD progression. Ferroptosis-related DEGs were closely correlated with the known PD-related genes, revealing the involvement of ferroptosis in the development of PD.
Koros et al., 2021	PPMI Data: GBA-PD =120 de novo sporadic PD =369 HC =195	Longitudinal 2-year/ Year 1 and Year 2	GBA PD: 4.47 (±4.13) Sporadic PD: 0.54(±0.6)	-	Adjustment for age, sex & BMI: GBA-PD cohort exhibited lower 2-year longitudinal uric acid level as compared to the controls (p = 0.016). Baseline uric acid measurements: A marginal difference (p = 0.119), but year 2 uric acid levels were lower in the GBA-PD cohort (p < 0.001). No difference in baseline (p = 0.664) Year 2 (p = 0.117) & 2-year longitudinal serum uric acid (p = 0.315) in the GBA-PD cohort as compared to sporadic PD	Low serum uric acid might be a progression biomarker in GBA-PD. Serum uric acid did not differ between GBA-PD vs sporadic PD. A gradual decrease of uric acid levels in both PD cohorts.
Latourelle et al., 2009	Familial PD =857 Idiopathic PD =440, Replication PD Idiopathic PD 747	-	-	-	DSG3 (rs1941184) (p=4.00E-06) OCA2 (rs17565841) (p=3.00E-06) QSER1, PRRG4 (rs10767971) (p=5.00E-07)	rs10767971, is associated with a later age of onset under a recessive model. SNP showing the strongest association to PD onset across the three populations under both the additive & dominant models is OCA2
Li et al., 2019	PD =418 HC =426	3 years	-	-	rs4698412 (BST1) (p=0.004307) rs4538475 (BST1) (p=0.01923) rs11060180 (CCDC620) (p=0.02327) rs199498 (MAPT) (p=0.0363) rs6532194 (SNCA) (p=5.87x10-7) rs11931074 (SNCA) (p=4.84x10-6) rs3857059 (SNCA) (p=9.57x10-6)	Only 13 of the 46 SNPs identified in other populations had significant correlations with PD & the PRSs based on these 13 SNPs were associated with the PD risk & age at onset in our Chinese cohort.

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					rs356220 (SNCA) (p=1.86x10 ⁻⁵) rs356165 (SNCA) (p=1.87x10 ⁻⁵) rs356219 (SNCA) (p=2.31x10 ⁻⁵) rs356182 (SNCA) (p=7.2x10 ⁻⁵) rs2736990 (SNCA) (p=0.000108) rs894278 (SNCA) (p=0.0472) Model 1 SNPs associated with PD (p < 0.05) in cohort were selected to generate the PRS model (p<0.001) Model 2 SNPs with a P value threshold of 0.01 in the logistic regression analysis (p<0.001) Model 3 All selected SNPs located in SNCA loci (p<0.001) Correlations between PRSs & CSF α-synuclein levels were analysed in the control group (n = 262) no significant relationships were found (model 1: p = 0.80, Spearman ρ = -0.016; model 2: p = 0.77, Spearman ρ = -0.018; model 3: p = 0.64, Spearman ρ = -0.029). No significant relationship between the PRSs & CSF α-synuclein levels (model 1, β = 0.07, p = 0.37; model 2, β = 0.08, p = 0.29; model 3, β = 0.09, p = 0.25)	The CSF α-synuclein level had no correlation with the PRS in normal subjects.
Li et al., 2021	PD =3456 Replication PD =1490	-	-	-	NDN, PWRN4 (rs978373) (p=3.00E-09) SNCA (p=1.00E-06)	These findings improve the current understanding of the genetic etiology of AAO of PD in different ethnic groups. GWAS on AAO of PD

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						<p>in a large Chinese PD cohort and identified a significant novel locus near NDN, as well as a suggestive locus in SNCA. Demonstrate genetic similarity & heterogeneity affecting AAO of PD in Asians & Europeans</p>
Liang et al., 2022	PD =53 HC =49	2 years/Not provided	-	324.78±37.92	<p>Serum sNogo-B levels: PD vs HC (p=0.0001) α-Syn levels: PD vs HC: (p < 0.0001) serum sNogo-B level: Early vs advanced: (n.s). Serum sNogo-B (AUC = 0.801, p < 0.0001) serum α-Syn (AUC = 0.93, (p < 0.0001), combination of them (AUC = 0.9534, p < 0.0001) sNogo-B level was mildly negatively correlated with UPDRS III scores (p = 0.049) & negatively correlated with the H&Y stage (p = 0.0001) serum sNogo-B & NMSS scores (n.s), levodopa equivalent dose (n.s)</p>	<p>Serum sNogo-B levels lower in PD compared to HC. Decreased serum sNogo-B may be a potential biomarker for PD. The lower Nogo-B level reflects worse motor function of PD. Serum sNogo-B is of added value to serum α-Syn panel in distinguishing PD from controls.</p>
Liu et al., 2021	European & unknown ancestry individuals	-	-	-	<p>Survival analysis: RIMS2: HR: 3.37 [2.24-5.06], (p=5.21X10-9), TMEM108: HR: 3.40 [2.21-5.24], (p=2.69x10-8), WWOX: HR: 2.31 [1.73-3.10], (p=1.98x10-8). Adjusted mean MMSE scores across time. RIMS2: (p=0.003), TMEM108: (p=0.0019), WWOX (p=0.009),</p>	<p>Polygenic progression scores exhibit a substantial aggregate association with dementia risk, while polygenic susceptibility scores are not predictive. This study identified a</p>

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	= 2,650, Replication =1,171 individuals					novel synaptic locus and polygenic score for cognitive disease progression in PD and proposes diverging genetic architectures of progression and susceptibility
Martinez-Carrasco et al., 2023	N=2784, Tracing PD =1478 OPDC =705 PPMI =283 PD STAT =77 PDBP =241	-	10 years	Baseline PPMI: 217 (197) OPDC: 280 (205) PPMI: 0 (0) PD STAT: NA PDBP: 414 (207)	rs72673189 (p=1.53x10-8) rs189093213 (p=2.81x10-9) rs180924818 (p= 6.27x10-9) rs1641433611 (p=4x10-4) rs113276175 (p= 4x10-4) rs6265 (p=4.95x10-2) rs1800497 (p=8.89x10-3)	Increased probability of developing LiD (females & younger age at onset). PRS significantly associated with an increase of LiD. rs72673189, rs189093213 & rs180924818 significantly associated with time to LiD onset.
Ortega et al., 2021	N=1193, GBA PD: =128 LRRK2 PD =155 LRRK2/GBA PD =21, Idiopathic PD =889	15 years	GBA PD: 6.9 (5.9) LRRK2 PD: 8.3 (6.5) LRRK2/GBA PD: 6.0 (6.7), Idiopathic PD: 5.5 (4.9)	GBA PD: 692.7 (551.1) LRRK2 PD: 747.4 (545.1) LRRK2/GBA PD: 283.2 (262.2) Idiopathic PD: 580.7 (489.7)	Mild: N370S & R496H (p=0.001) Variant: E326K, E326K/E326K, T369M (p=0.001) GBA PD & cognitive decline compared to (p= <0.001) LRRK2/GBA PD (p= <0.001), LRRK2 PD: (p=0.001), Idiopathic PD: (p=0.005), LRRK2 G2019S × GBA interaction in MoCA decline (p= 0.04). GBA PD motor progression compared with those with idiopathic PD (p=0.03) or LRRK2 PD (p=0.004).	GBA PD faster decline in MoCA than those with LRRK2/GBA PD, LRRK2 PD, Idiopathic PD LRRK2 G2019S × GBA interaction in MoCA decline GBA PD had worse motor progression compared with idiopathic PD or LRRK2 PD
Paul et al., 2018	PD =285	5 years	2.0 (1.4)	-	(p=0.049)	Susceptibility SNPs for PD combined with cumulative PRS

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						were associated with faster motor and cognitive decline in patients. Thus, these genetic markers may be associated with not only PD susceptibility but also disease progression in multiple domains.
Pihlstrøm et al., 2016	PD =336	-	-	-	(p = 0.010)	Cumulative genetic risk to a motor outcome in Parkinson's disease
Pihlstrøm et al., 2022	Reference data (IPDGC) PD =11693 HC = 9841 Test data (NeuroX dbGAP) PD= 5112 HC= 5372 PPMI PD= 360, HC= 160	-	-	-	(p<10E-15)	Feasibility of a polygenic hazard approach in PD, integrating the genetic effects on disease risk & age at onset in a single model. The approach holds promise for risk stratification in future clinical trials of disease-modifying therapies, which aim to postpone the onset of PD.
Real et al., 2023	PD=3923	-	-	-	LRRC66 (rs140229141 (p= 6.03E-08) MGST1 (rs137899695) (p= 6.09E-08) DMBT1P1 (rs1175592627) (p= 1.10E-07) MYT1L (rs76738835) (p= 1.23E-07) ROS1 (rs142457969) (p=1.26E-07) OCIAD1 (rs148443315) (p=1.47E-07) AVL9 (rs112302765) (p=1.58E-07) SSR1 (rs60707664) (p=1.60E-07) SLC6A3	APOE ε4 allele as a major risk factor for the conversion to Parkinson's disease dementia as well as a new locus within the ApoE and APP receptor LRP1B gene. GBA variants were also identified to be associated with higher risk of progression to dementia.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(rs28363070) (p=1.62E-07) LINC01572 (rs72791159) (p=2.29E-07) ZNF706 (rs74495475) (p=2.36E-07) PLCL2 (rs137926116) (p=2.43E-07) SQRDL (rs62008270) (p=3.00E-07) UGGT2 (rs79734852) (p=3.18E-07) MDFIC (rs1011449) (p=3.37E-07) CCDC57 (rs116965562) (p=3.56E-07) GRID2 (rs144839542) (p=3.59E-07), GUCY1A2 (rs150641600) (p=3.73E-07) LINC01006 (rs56037079) (p=4.31E-07) LINC01581 (rs10438450) LINC01572 (rs147491123) (p=5.11E-07) PLD5 (rs148758425) (p=2.98E-07) FAR2 (rs34331981) (p=5.60E-07), CCDC27 (rs56079032) (p=6.43E-07) (rs117950086) (p=6.86E-07) NUP188 (rs143101418) (p=6.88E-07) LINC02302 (rs117900786)(p=6.94E-07) (rs150616043) (p=6.95E-07) (rs17460578) (p=7.37E-07) PTPRD (rs111575815) (p=8.56E-07) DDB1 (rs28720292) (p=8.93E-07) MSI2 (rs78754514) (p=9.03E-07) VTI1A (rs137890797) (p=9.71E-07), (rs429358) (p=2.00E-15) (rs80306347) (p=7.00E-09) (rs78294974) (p=4.00E-08)	
Redensek 2022	PD =231 HC = 161	Treatment duration 7.3 years (3.6-13.5)	Not provided	LED enrollment: 975mg/day (600-1,363.15)	VDR rs2228570 (p<0.001). VDR rs1544410 (GG vs. GA+ AA) (p=0.005) associated with visual hallucinations, VDR rs739837 (TT vs. GG) (p=0.036) VDR rs731236 (TT vs. TC +CC) (p=0.011) (TT vs. TC) (p=0.028)	VDR rs2228570 is associated with PD risk Associations of specific VDR genotypes with adverse events of dopaminergic treatment

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(TT vs. CC) (p=0.035), rs1544410 (GG vs. GA) (P=0.014) with occurrence of orthostatic hypotension	
Ryu et al., 2020	PD =172 HC =569	-	10.8 ± 4.5 (5–31)	-	8.00E-09	FAM129B (rs10760490) was associated with the occurrence of motor fluctuations at 5 years after the onset of PD. GALNT14 (rs144125291) was significantly associated with the occurrence of LID.
Tan et al., 2021	=3364, Tracking PD =1966, Oxford Discovery =985 PPMI =413	Length of follow-up Tracking PD 3.8 (1.4), Oxford Discovery 4.3 (1.7), PPMI 5.4 (1.2)	Tracking PD 3.2 (3.0) Oxford Discovery 2.9 (1.9) PPMI 2.0(2.0).	-	APOE, TOMM40, APOCA (p=2.8x10-6) ATP8B2 (p=5.3x10-6) AQP10 (p=5.0x10-6)	APOE ε4 allele carriers had more severe cognitive progression. ATP8B2 was associated with motor progression
Tsiouris et al., 2020	New diagnosed & untreated PD patients =423	5-13 years (depending on cohort)/ 3rd/6th/9th/12 months	New diagnosed and untreated PD patients	-	2-year follow-up: Rapid progression (top 20%) vs Slower progression (Rest): rs823118 (p=0.415) rs329648 (p=0.191). Rapid progression (top 10%) vs Slower progression (Rest): rs11060180 (p=0.001) rs823118 (p=0.042)	Improvement when a longer follow-up period is considered in the estimation of the progression rate. Moving from 2-4 years the classification accuracy increased in all cases tested, better outcome in identifying rapid progression phenotype. Prolonged patient evaluation can provide better outcomes in identifying rapid progression phenotype.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Wallen et al., 2018	PD=1950, Replication PD =726	-	-	-	LPPR1 (rs73656147) (p=9.00E-09)	Through association with age at diagnosis, we uncovered LPPR1 as a modifier gene for PD
Wang et al., 2022	N=389, PPMI dataset =346, Controls =171 Huashan dataset (Validation cohort) PD =43, Controls =23	Followed up to 5 years (every 3 months during first year & every 6 months during subsequent 4 years)	New diagnosed PD patients	-	SNCA in relation to UPDRS II PAP (p=0.023) SNCA in relation to ADL PAP (p=0.0048).	Patients with low subcortical DBM values are associated with faster progression of motor symptoms across the 2 datasets. Structural measurements of BR affect the clinical progression of motor symptoms in PD patients. PD patients with greater brain resources (higher deformation-based morphometry values) had a greater compensatory capacity, which was associated with slower rates of clinical progression.
Zheng et al., 2023	PD =314998	-	-	-	rs10797576 (T/C) (p=1.76x10-10), rs10906923 (C/A) (p=2.37x10-8), rs11060180 (G/A) (p=3.08x10-11), rs11158026 (T/C) (p=2.88x10-10), rs11343 (T/G) (p=1.46x10-9), rs115185635 (C/G) (p=2.2x10-8), rs11724635 (C/A) (p=4.26x10-17), rs117896735 (A/G) (p=1.21x10-11), rs12456492 (G/A) (p=2.15x10-11), rs12497850 (G/T) (p=6.8x10-8), rs12637471 (A/G) (p=5.38x10-22), rs13294100 (T/G) (p=1.99x10-12), rs14235 (A/G) (p=3.63x10-12), rs143918452 (G/A) (p=2.25x10-7), rs1474055 (C/T) (p=7.11x10-16), rs1555399 (T/A) (p=5.7x10-16), rs17649553 (T/C) (p=6.11x10-49), rs199347 (G/A) (p=5.62x10-14), rs2280104 (T/C) (p=9.06x10-7), rs2414739 (G/A)	Physical prefrailty and frailty were associated with incident PD independent of sociodemographic factors, lifestyles, multiple morbidities, and genetic background. These findings may have implications for the assessment and management of frailty for PD prevention.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(p=3.59x10 ⁻¹²), rs2694528 (C/A) (p=1.69x10 ⁻¹¹), rs2740594 (A/G) (p=9.545x10 ⁻¹¹), rs329648 (T/C) (p=8.05x10 ⁻¹²), rs34043159 (C/T) (p=3.83x10 ⁻⁸), rs34311866 (C/T) (p=6x10 ⁻⁴¹), rs353116 (T/C) (p=9.73x10 ⁻⁷), rs356182 (G/A) (p=1.85x10 ⁻⁸²), rs35749011 (G/A) (p=6.1x10 ⁻²³), rs3793947 (A/G) (p=2.59x10 ⁻⁸), rs4073221 (G/T) (p=3.02x10 ⁻⁹), rs4653767 (C/T) (p=2.3x10 ⁻¹⁰), rs4784227 (T/C) (p=8.29x10 ⁻⁸), rs591323 (A/G) (p=3.17x10 ⁻⁸), rs601999 (C/T) (p=8.03x10 ⁻⁹), rs62120679 (T/C) (p=2.52x10 ⁻⁹), rs6430538 (T/C) (p=3.35x10 ⁻¹⁹), rs6812193 (T/C) (p=1.85x10 ⁻¹¹), rs76904798 (T/C) (p=4.86x10 ⁻¹⁴), rs78738012 (C/T) (p=2.1x10 ⁻⁹), rs8005172 (T/C) (p=1.2x10 ⁻⁹), rs8118008 (A/G) (p=2.32x10 ⁻⁸), rs823118 (C/T) (p=1.96x10 ⁻¹⁶), rs9275326 (T/C) (p=5.81x10 ⁻¹³), rs9468199 (A/G) (p=3.44x10 ⁻¹³)	

Abbreviations: AAO: Age of onset, ESS: Epworth Sleepiness Scale, GBA: Glucosylceramidase, GPiP: Genotype-Phenotype Correlation in PRKN-PD, GWAS: Genome-Wide Association Analysis, HC: Healthy Control, H&Y: Hoehn & Yahr Scale, LID: Levodopa Induced Dyskinesia, MAGMA: Multi-markers Analysis of Genome Annotation, MDR-UPDRS: Modified Unified Parkinson's Rating Scale, MMSE: Mini-Mental State Examination, MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment, NET: Norepinephrine, NGC/NS-PARK: Noyaux Gris Centraux (NGC)/NS-Park database, Non-LID: Non-Levodopa Induced Dyskinesia, NR: Not Reported, PD: Parkinson's Disease, PDBP: National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program, PPMI: Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative, PRS: Polygenic Risk Score, RBDSQ: Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder Screening Questionnaire, REM: Rapid Eye Movement, SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms, UPDRS: Unified Parkinson's Rating Scale.

General discussion

The review aimed to identify and evaluate the clinical genetic markers regarding Levodopa response, progression and longitudinal outcomes in relation to PD. The findings highlight the extent of studies and research conducted on genetic markers and PD. This updated version of the systematic review/search focuses on the studies published between January 1st, 2024 and February 1st, 2025 that report statistically significant associations of genetic variants with PD progression and medication response. A surge in the analysis of publicly available data and bioinformatics analysis in PD was observed. A study by Hwang et al., 2024, reported that SNPs rs2134545 and rs4366309 influence the age at onset (AAO) in PD. SNP rs2134545 reduces the average AAO by 3.47 years, while the SNP rs4366309 delayed AAO by 3.05 years. Another study by Menon et al., 2024 identified that the presence of a frameshift or structural *PRKN* variant is associated with a 3.4 ± 1.6 years or 4.7 ± 1.6 years earlier AAO of *PRKN*-PD, respectively. A study by Torshiz et al., 2024, identified various SNPs and genes e.g., rs2230288 (*EFNA*), rs10847839 (*HIP1R*) and rs2183982 (*LGALS3*) that become altered and dysfunction in PD. These genes, *LGALS3*, *CSNK2A1*, *SMPD3*, *STX4*, *APOA2*, *PAFAH1B3*, *LDLR*, *HSPB1*, *BRK1* play a key role in disease pathogenesis. Numerous SNPs were identified, through the previous review some of these were associated with faster cognitive progression as observed studies conducted by (Hayete et al., 2017; Fischer et al., 2022; Cao et al., 2021; Li et al., 2019). A study by (Hayete et al., 2017) identified that certain SNPs may lower DAT uptake at baseline in the caudate nuclei and therefore contribute to worse long-term cognitive outcomes. Moreover, some SNPs were associated with slower rate of PD progression in unmedicated state, while faster motor deterioration in PD was observed in patients with certain SNPs (Hayete et al., 2017; Martinez-Carrasco et al., 2023 and Ortega et al., 2021). One study, by Ortega et al., (2021) showed GBA-PD patients had worse motor progression in comparison with idiopathic PD or *LRRK2* PD (Ortega et al., 2021). The included studies within the following review, have shed light on genes and SNPs that influence diverse aspects of PD onset, progression and drug response, clinical and longitudinal outcome measures and potential disease biomarkers.

2.3.5 AI-driven approaches for PD progression modelling

Study selection

In the Rayyan bibliographic searches and using the software, we selected the keywords machine learning”, “artificial intelligence”, “sensitivity”, “specificity”, “area under the curve”, “AUC” AND “progression” and “longitudinal,” and identified 79 records. We then reviewed the titles and abstracts of these records to identify studies that utilized AI-driven approaches for modelling the progression of PD, excluding review studies and those focused on remote disease monitoring, symptom assessment and classification, and prediction and classification of PD. This process yielded 8 relevant records. An extra number of five papers were identified through extra search of the list of references of the eight initially included papers. Thus, the final number of records included until 2023 was 13.

This updated version of the systematic review/search focuses on studies published between January 1st, 2024 and February 1st, 2025. We applied the same search strategy, keywords, and inclusion/exclusion criteria as the original review. An additional 5 eligible studies were identified bringing the total number of included records to 18.

Table 18 outlines the criteria for determining study eligibility. In summary, a study was deemed eligible if it met the following conditions:

Researching the progression of PD in a cohort of individuals diagnosed with PD,

AND

The analysis of the study data was conducted using ML tools. This includes the application of ML models that incorporate training/testing or training/validation datasets and provide metrics indicating the performance of the ML model in predicting or understanding the progression of PD.

We particularly focused on study designs that incorporated longitudinal data and employed AI-driven approaches to predict the progression of the disease at future time points.

Table 18 Selection criteria for AI-driven methodologies and PD progression

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Analysis	AI-driven approach for PD progression
Results	At least one model performance metric

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	79	66	145
Articles included in literature table	13	5	18

Study characteristics

Among the reviewed studies (**Table 19**), at the input level, three studies integrated gait features such as step width and step length for their models (Varrecchia et al., 2021; Rehman et al., 2021; Sotirakis et al., 2023). Four additional studies employed acoustic features like Jitter and Shimmer (Naranjo et al., 2021; Raza et al., 2020; Wan et al., 2018; Nilashi et al., 2017). Furthermore, three studies employed a blend of clinical, imaging and medication data (Severson et al., 2021; Velseboer, 2016; Simuni, 2016). Another study focused on measuring serum cytokine levels (Rastegar, 2019). Additionally, one study utilized a combination of genetic, imaging, clinical and demographic variables (Latourelle, 2017). Whereas another study did not specify the input features used in its model.

New studies added in this update have expanded the diversity of input modalities. One study used deep radiomic features from DAT-SPECT imaging alongside 17 clinical variables (Gorji & Jouzdani, 2024), while another employed a transcriptomic dataset comprising over 58,000 gene expression features (Fabrizio et al., 2025). Other recent work combined digital gait features, clinical assessments, DaTSCAN imaging, CSF biomarkers, and demographics across three multicenter cohorts (Hähnel et al., 2024), or utilized standard cognitive, demographic, and motor subtype features (Bernal et al., 2024). Additionally, MRI/PET imaging data with voxel-based and ROI features were incorporated into a deep learning pipeline (Patil et al., 2024).

At the level of the model, different approaches were utilized. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) have been employed (Varrecchia et al., 2021), while other ML algorithms, including Random Forest Regressor and extreme gradient boosting (XGB), have also been adopted (Sotirakis et al., 2023; Raza et al., 2020). Advanced models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with rectified linear activation function (ReLU) were utilized by Rehman et al. (2021); and more specialized methods like the Hypergraph partitioning algorithm and Incremental Support Vector Regression were implemented by Nilashi et al. (2022) and Nilashi et al. (2017). A personalized input-output hidden Markov model was applied by Severson et al. (2021), and a Hidden Markov model by Naranjo et al. (2021). Ensemble methods were also explored, including a combination of DMLP, logistic regression, Random Forests, k-nearest neighbours,

and M5P in Wan et al. (2018), and other ensemble utilized using the REFS platform in Latourelle (2017). Other studies like those by Velseboer (2016) and Simuni (2016) have used statistical approaches with multivariable logistic regression analysis and a combination of random survival forests with a Cox model for prognostic indexing, respectively. Additionally, Rastegar (2019) employed Random Forest and elastic-net algorithms to enhance the predictive performance.

The recent literature further broadened the modelling landscape. Methods included Markov models, LSTM networks, and Temporal Fusion Transformers for sequential prediction (Bernal et al., 2024); hierarchical XGBoost classifiers for subtype detection (Fabrizio et al., 2025); recursive feature elimination and multi-model evaluation (Gorji & Jouzdani, 2024); deep neural networks trained on imaging with Grey Wolf Optimizer feature selection (Patil et al., 2024); and a combination of latent time joint mixed-effects models and clustering-based progression subtyping (Hähnel et al., 2024). In many of these, feature selection techniques such as ANOVA filtering, SHAP values, PCA, and Random Forest importance ranking were applied.

Table 19 Studies about AI-driven approaches and PD progression

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
Bernal et al., 2024	917 (53% PD, 30% at risk, 17% HC)	Cognitive status (NC, MCI, Dementia) via MoCA and others	Age, education, sex, MoCA, MDS-UPDRS Q1.1, BMI, BP, diabetes history, Schwab & England scale	Manual selection based on availability and prior evidence	Markov, LSTM, Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT), Ensemble	Best IPW-F1: 0.502 (Ensemble); TFT: 0.468; LSTM: 0.414; Markov: 0.349	TFT performed best overall; LSTM excelled short-term; Markov was interpretable. Ensemble model had highest IPW-F1; APOE4 did not improve performance.
Fabrizio et al., 2025	600 (407 PD, 193 HC)	MDS-UPDRS, PD subtype classification (S1-S3)	Transcriptomics (58,780 genes), MDS-UPDRS I-III, HVL, Benton, DaTSCAN, age, sex, sleep	ANOVA with FDR, correlation filtering ($ r > 0.8$)	Hierarchical XGBoost (S3 vs others, then S1 vs S2)	S3 vs others: AUROC 0.877, F1 0.828; S1 vs S2: AUROC 0.576, F1 0.77	Transcriptomic subtypes were biologically distinct. Gene data was less predictive than clinical/DaTSCAN; SHAP used for feature importance.
Gorji & Jouzdani, 2024	330 PD patients	MoCA, MDS-UPDRS-I (cognitive decline over 5 years)	17 clinical + 1024 imaging DFs (from DAT SPECT)	Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)	LRC, SVC, KNN, RFC, GBC, ADDB, BGC, MLP, DTC	Year 4 MoCA: AUC 89.28% (CV), 89.8% (external, GBC); MDS-UPDRS-I: AUC 81.34% (CV, RFC)	MoCA outperformed MDS-UPDRS-I; deep radiomics best predictors. Combining clinical + imaging did not improve over radiomics alone.
Hähnel et al., 2024	1124 PD patients (PPMI, ICEBERG, LuxPARK)	MDS-UPDRS I-IV, MoCA, SCOPA, PIGD	Clinical scales, digital gait, DaTSCAN, CSF biomarkers, demographics, comorbidities	Not explicitly stated; all features used in models	LTJMM + VaDER (subtyping); Logistic Regression, RF, XGBoost (prediction)	ROC-AUC up to 0.79 (1-year data); 0.68 with baseline only	Two robust subtypes: fast vs slow progression. Subtype predictions aid trial design; 30-43% sample size reduction possible.
Patil et al., 2024	Not specified	Not explicitly defined	MRI/PET imaging features: VBA, ROI, functional connectivity	Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO)	Deep Neural Network (DNN)	Not provided (focused on methodology)	GWO effectively reduced high-dimensional data. Method supports early detection and personalized PD treatment.

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
Latourelle et al., 2017	117 controls and 312 PD cases from the PPMI database, with additional validation in an independent cohort (LABS-PD) of 317 PD patients	MDS-UPDRS Parts II and III scores	genetic SNPs, CSF protein biomarkers, DaTscan imaging variables, and clinical and demographic variables.	Bayesian machine-learning techniques (REFS platform) were used to select features and construct predictive models.	An ensemble of models was constructed using the REFS™ platform	In the PPMI sample, the model ensemble exhibited strong performance (R ² =41%, 95% CI: 35% – 47%) but showed reduced performance in the LABS-PD cohort (R ² =9%, 95% CI: 4% – 16%).	The study confirmed established predictors and identified novel predictors of PD motor progression, including a significant epistatic genetic interaction specific to PD. Genetic variation was found to be the most useful predictive marker.
Naranjo et al., 2021	36 PwPD	Hoehn and Yahr scale	Hypokinetic dysarthria Cepstral peak prominence Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients Vocal fold vibration Gender	N/A	Hidden Markov model	Global accuracy rate 78.29% MAE 0.035449(0.005178) RMSE 0.080724(0.012229)	The performance result of the HMM model was promising and showed that acoustic features may be useful in tracking the progression of PD
Nilashi et al., 2017	5875 records	Total UPDRS Motor UPDRS	Jitter, Shimmer, HNR, RPDE, DFA, PPE	non-linear iterative partial least squares (NIPALS)	Incremental Support Vector Regression	MAE and R ² for the Total-UPDRS were respectively MAE = 0.4656 and R ² = 0.885, and for Motor-UPDRS were respectively MAE = 0.4967 and R ² = 0.868.	the prediction method is integrated with dimensionality reduction and clustering techniques improved the accuracy prediction of PD and reduced the computation time.
Nilashi et al., 2022	-	motor UPDRS, overall UPDRS	Specific data features analysed were not mentioned.	PCA	Hypergraph partitioning algorithm Neural network Multiple linear regression Support vector regression Adaptive	Best results for the HGPA+SOM+SVR ensemble: Motor-UPDRS (MAE: 0.5540, RMSE: 0.4116, R ² : 0.9139) Total-UPDRS(MAE: 0.5565, RMSE: 0.4179, R ² : 0.9058)	The study concludes that expectation-maximization with support vector regression ensembles can improve prediction accuracy for Motor-UPDRS and Total-UPDRS scores compared to other techniques

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
					neuro-fuzzy inference system Self-organizing map Deep belief network Expectation-maximization		
Rastegar et al., 2019	160 PD patients at baseline	UPDRS III and H-Y staging system	Serum cytokine levels were measured, including 27 inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, using a magnetic human cytokine multiplex assay.	For each algorithm the variables that contributed the most to the predictive performance are listed	Random Forest and elastic-net algorithms	The Random Forest model achieved an NRMSE of 0.1123 for the Hoehn and Yahr scale and 0.1193 for UPDRS III	Peripheral cytokines, particularly MIP1 α and MCP1, significantly contributed to predicting PD progression, suggesting their potential utility in developing refined models for patient stratification and clinical trial endpoints.
Raza et al., 2020	42 PwPD	MDS-UPDRS-III	A total of 16 dysphonia measures extracted from the voice recording obtained through the AHTD device		extreme gradient boosting (XGB) is used as a regression method	MAE of 2.97 \pm 0.05 and 6.45 \pm 0.21 in the training and testing datasets respectively to predict the overall UPDRS score.	they stated that the IoT framework and machine learning algorithm efficiently predict PD progression, outperforming state-of-the-art techniques
Rehman et al., 2021	119 PwPD	MDS-UPDRS-III	Magnitude of the three axes of the raw gait data signals	In the deep learning model, a 1D convolutional bloc extracted features from the magnitude of the raw gait data	Convolutional Neural Network (rectified linear activation function (ReLU))	Pearson correlation of 0.82, ICC of 0.76, and mean absolute error of 6.29	The DL-CNN model trained on baseline gait data can accurately predict MDS-UPDRS-III scores after 3 years, showing potential for assessing PD motor severity and supporting clinical management.
Severson et al., 2021	423 PwPD and 196 HC from PPMI.	Mild cognitive impairment, dementia, dyskinesia,	Clinical, imaging, and medication data were analysed.	latent variable model for dimensionality reduction and	A personalized input-output hidden Markov model was	For the PPMI testing set: HMM: Average likelihood of -346 with a standard deviation (SD)	The model discovered eight disease states with non-sequential, overlapping progression trajectories,

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
	610 patients PDBP	presence of motor fluctuations, functional impairment from motor fluctuations, H-Y score, and death.		feature selection.	applied for disease progression modelling.	of 120. PIOHMM: Average likelihood of -330 with an SD of 105. For the PDBP set: HMM: Average likelihood of -127 with an SD of 114. PIOHMM: Average likelihood of -123 with an SD of 107.	highlighting the heterogeneity of PD progression and the ineffectiveness of static subtype assignment
Simuni et al., 2016	423 PD participants and 196 healthy controls were enrolled.	MDS-UPDRS total score	Data included biofluids and imaging biomarkers, notably dopamine transporter (DAT) imaging striatal binding ratios.	N/A	The study employed random survival forests for the analysis and developed a prognostic index based on a Cox model.	For the RSF model with the three top predictors, C = 0.70 and pseudo-R2 = 0.13.	The study found that a subset of three predictors—disease duration, the modified Schwab and England activities of daily living scale, and the MDS-UPDRS total score—modestly predicted time to initiation of symptomatic therapy (C = 0.70, pseudo-R2 = 0.13). Biological variables did not increase prediction accuracy. A prognostic index was created for indicating the risk of initiation of symptomatic therapy in PD patients.
Sotirakis et al., 2023	91 PwPD	MDS-UPDRS-III	29 features identified as significantly progressing	During model development using forward feature selection and PCA	Random Forest Regressor Multivariate linear regression	Best model (Random Forest) had an RMSE of 10.02 (against UPDRS-III score)	the study's machine learning model could detect PD motor symptom progression earlier and more accurately than clinical assessments
Varrecch et al., 2021	76 PwPD and 67 HC	UPDRS III and H-Y staging system	Time distance: walking speed (m/s), cadence (step/s), step width (m), step length (m), stance, swing, and double support phase durations.	PCA	ANN	Performance ranged from 82–98% for distinguishing PD from controls, and 66.16–77.2% for staging classification.	the numerical sum of knee and trunk rotation angles, showed a good ability to discriminate PwPD from HCs. Two combinations of four features showed good ability

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
			Kinematic data: The anatomical joint angles of the hip, knee, ankle, trunk, and pelvis and the corresponding ranges of motion of the joints				to classify PD stages according to the H-Y scale
Velseboer et al., 2016	The CARPA cohort included 111 patients, and the CamPaIGN cohort included 108 patients for the validation set.	A composite outcome measure was created, classifying patients as having an unfavourable prognosis based on the presence of postural instability, dementia at the 5-year assessment, or earlier death.	Candidate predictor variables included demographic information, clinical characteristics, and specific assessments like the UPDRS-ME axial score and animal fluency score.	N/A	multivariable logistic regression analysis	AUC = 0.85	The study developed a reliable model for predicting 5-year outcomes in newly diagnosed Parkinson's disease patients, which can be useful for clinical trial selection and patient counselling.
Wan et al., 2018	20 PwPD and 20 HC	UPDRS scores	23 feature parameters extracted from voice samples: movement data from smartphones	N/A	DMLP, along with logistic regression, Random Forests, k-nearest neighbours, and M5P	DMLP classifier produces the best performance	DMLP classifier effectively distinguishes between Parkinson's patients and healthy controls, offering a promising tool for non-invasive monitoring and severity estimation of Parkinson's disease

General discussion

There was a wide diversity in modelling approaches which reflects the complex nature of PD disease progression and the interdisciplinary effort by previous studies to understand and predict it effectively. Most research studies target predictions of progression outcomes at a single future time point rather than examining multiple future intervals. One study predicts the time to initiation of symptomatic treatment using measurements of serum cytokine levels (Simuni et al., 2016). Another study developed a model for predicting 5-year outcomes (e.g., postural instability, dementia, death) in newly diagnosed PD patients (Velseboer, 2016). Gait and acoustic features are well investigated in the prediction of the severity of PD, highlighting the importance of these features. The UPDRS-III and H-Stages are frequently employed as metrics to quantify disease progression. These scales are pivotal for evaluating the severity and progression of motor symptoms. Research focuses on the ON state (when medication is effective) of PD, often overlooking the OFF state (when medication effects are negligible). Replication of existing models across cohorts remains limited, and translation of the results into clinical practice has not yet been achieved. With a few recent exceptions, most of the models rely only on cross-sectional data and assume that each PD subtype follows a fixed progression trajectory, without considering positive or negative medication effects.

Recent studies have begun to address some of these gaps by shifting toward longitudinal modelling strategies. Rather than relying solely on baseline or single-visit data, several studies now incorporate repeated clinical assessments over time, allowing for sequential prediction of cognitive decline, identification of motor subtypes based on progression trajectories, and multivariate modelling of UPDRS-III changes.

2.3.6 Digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

Since self-reporting of tremor and dyskinesia symptoms at clinical assessments are less accurate, digital means are increasingly used for systematically capturing, assessing, and monitoring these symptoms daily. This literature review aims to investigate proposed approaches for assessing tremor and dyskinesia with wearable sensors, smartphones attached to hands or custom-made devices to monitor these motor symptoms. The most popular sensors used are accelerometers, measuring linear acceleration, while gyroscopes, measuring angular velocity can also be used, as human motion mainly consists of rotations about joints. Furthermore, additional sensors, such as magnetometers may be used to provide measurements for correcting accelerometer or gyroscope data (Foxlin et al., 2002). In this way, continuous monitoring of these motor symptoms is achieved, leading to improved disease management.

Study selection

Within the literature search on wearable sensors, with the Rayyan software we used the keywords “tremor” and “dyskinesia” for both bibliographic searches described in Section 2.1. This search was conducted across two time periods: the original review (2013–2023) and the update (2023–2025). The initial search yielded 317 records for tremor and 60 for dyskinesia, totalling 362 unique entries. In the updated search (2023–2025), we retrieved an additional 249 unique entries, comprising 223 related to tremor and 37 related to dyskinesia. A set of exclusion criteria were used, including a) Review articles, b) Articles focusing on other motor symptoms, such as balance, posture or gait, c) Articles focusing on “tremor” that do not include rest tremor data assessment (Rest tremors occur when sitting or lying down and relaxed). Subsequently, three independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Where appropriate, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. This filtering resulted in 40 records (compared to 29 in the initial review). We identified two other important articles through other references (Powers et al., 2021; Ziogas et al., 2023) and added them for review.

Table 20 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Inclusion criteria included the following:

<p>Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Methods and data for rest tremor or dyskinesia assessment were provided,</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Use of data from accelerometer or gyroscope sensors in wearable or smart devices that enable monitoring of symptoms throughout the day OR use of data from video sensors for rest tremor and dyskinesia assessment.</p>

Table 20 Selection criteria for digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Measurement	Rest tremor and/or dyskinesia data available
Sensors	Wearable/video sensors and/or smart devices appropriate for daily use.

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	362	249	611
Articles included in literature table	29	11	40

Study characteristics

Among the 40 included studies (initial: 29; updated: 11), as shown in **Table 21**, 36 addressed rest tremor (initial: 25; updated: 11), while 7 included dyskinesia assessment (initial: 5; updated: 2). MDS-UPDRS-III Items 3.17 (rest tremor amplitude) and 3.18 (rest tremor constancy) are mainly used as clinical outcome for the quantification of tremor symptoms. Dyskinesia assessment using accelerometer data mainly focuses on chorea symptoms (abnormal involuntary movements), as dystonia symptoms involve pose/posture and do not involve movement. Most included studies recruited participants with a mean age ranging from 58 to 85 years; the percentage of male participants ranged from 36 to 87.5%.

The main objective of this review was to assess the feasibility and efficiency of digital solutions for capturing tremor and dyskinesia of upper limbs. The main objective of AI-PROGNOSIS is to design and develop passive capturing solutions for remote monitoring of tremor and dyskinesia related to PD, outside the clinical setting, using non-obtrusive hardware, such as IMU data from consumer smartwatches. Regarding tremor effects, AI-PROGNOSIS focuses on estimating rest tremor, i.e., tremor occurring when voluntary muscle activity is absent (e.g., when resting on the arm of a chair), where the person is relaxed and completely supported against gravity. Dyskinesia (i.e., involuntary, erratic, writhing movements) will also be detected using IMU data from consumer smartwatches, and emphasis is given to a particular type of dyskinesia, namely chorea, that involves abrupt and unpredictable movements that can be detected using IMU data. We thus excluded papers that do not meet these criteria, e.g. focus on tests in the clinical setting or active tests or do not assess rest tremor or dyskinesia. A notable exception is the use of video sensors for assessing tremor or dyskinesia, where a limited number of some innovative solutions have been included.

Table 21 Studies about digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Channa, A. et al. 2024	28 PD	61.5 ± 9 years	68%	Triaxial accelerometer (Shimmer3 device and A-WEAR bracelet).	Time-frequency (TF) maps generated using Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT)	Severity scores (0–4) for tremor labeled by clinicians during ON/OFF medication states.	AlexNet transfer learning (deep convolutional neural network)	Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity.	Tremor: 90.9% accuracy.	The A-WEAR bracelet combined with CWT and AlexNet effectively estimated PD symptom severity, enabling remote monitoring and potential optimization of Levodopa dosage.
Crowe, C. et al. 2024	24 PD	70.71 ± 8.50 years	67%	IMUs (ActiGraph GT3X+; ActiGraph Corporation, USA) - accelerometer & gyroscope	Tremor: Frequency spectra (3–8 Hz) from 3s windows, Dyskinesia: 78 features (statistical, spectral, entropy) from 6s windows, focusing on 1–4 Hz erratic movements.	MDS-UPDRS limb-specific scores (0–4) for tremor, dyskinesia	CNN, Gradient Boosted Trees, LSTM	Balanced Accuracy	Balanced accuracy ranging from 63% to 67% in Unscripted home monitoring, 75% to 83% accuracy in controlled laboratory settings	Wearable sensors (primarily wrist-based) combined with AI can objectively monitor PD symptoms in real-world settings, labeling challenges (e.g., unreliable diaries), and symptom overlap limit clinical readiness—requiring improved models, better validation, and larger studies for broader adoption.
Dattola, S. et al. 2025	17 PD + 17 age-matched HC	PD: 66.4 ± 11.3 years, HCs = 64.0 ± 9.9 years	PD: 58.8%, HCs = 23.5%	MC10 BioStamp RC sensors (MC10 Inc., Lexington, MA, USA) - accelerometer	-	MDS-UPDRS 3.17 item (0-4)	K-means	Accuracy, Recall, Precision, F1-score	Binary classification: Accuracy: 76%, precision: 1.00, recall: 0.57, F1 score: 0.73, Multi-class	Unsupervised k-means clustering can classify Parkinson's tremor vs. non-tremor states (76% accuracy) using wearable sensor data, offering a label-free, objective approach, though

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
									classification:Accuracy:57.1%, precision:0.56,recall:0.53,F1 score:0.51.	multiclass severity distinction remains challenging (57-71% accuracy).
Evers, L.J.W. et al. 2025	48 participants: 8 PD with tremor, 16 PD without tremor, 24 controls	61–67.5 years	50%	Wrist-worn Physilog 4 accelerometers	45 features per window: time and frequency domain (e.g., PSD, entropy).	Binary tremor/non-tremor labels via video annotation.	Single-layer and two-layer Prototypical RBF Networks; baselines: logistic regression, random forest.	Sensitivity, specificity, AUROC.	Two-layer model: Sensitivity 66%, Specificity 95%, AUROC 87%.	Two-layer prototype model showed better and more robust tremor detection performance, especially in low-data settings and across diverse real-life activities.
Jin, X.H. et al. 2024	59 PD	62.97 ± 11.44 years	59.3 %	Wearable IMU (RuiPing device with accelerometer and gyroscope)	Hybrid: 20 prior-driven (time/frequency domain) + data-driven (tsfresh library)	Tremor (1) / Non-tremor (0) based on expert-rated timestamps	Logistic Regression, SVM, Random Forest	Tremor (1) / Non-tremor (0) based on expert-rated timestamps	Upper limb: 96.44% accuracy, 93.35% F1, Kappa 0.908	Hybrid features outperformed prior-only methods; detected both upper/lower limb tremors; identified inter-limb tremor differences
Jorge, J. et al. 2024	28 PD	61.5 ± 9 years	68%	Pebble smartwatch, a GeneActiv wearable sensor, and a Samsung smartphone	-	MDS UPDRS III sub-items scale [0, 4] & upper-limb and lower-limb presence/absence of dyskinesia	FedAvg + CNNLSTM / InceptionTime	F1-score, balanced accuracy, precision, and recall.	Centralized (CNN-LSTM): F1-score 0.734, Centralized (InceptionTime): F1-score 0.718, Federated (CNN-	Both CNN-LSTM and InceptionTime models effectively detect Parkinson's tremors using wearable data. While performance is similar in centralized and federated setups, the InceptionTime model is

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
									LSTM): F1-score 0.618, Federated (InceptionTime): F1-score 0.660	better suited for wearables due to its lighter architecture.
Khanom, S. et al. 2024	14 (7 PD patients, 7 healthy)	55 ± 7 years	50%	ADXL345 triaxial accelerometer	15 features including RMS, MAV, Entropy, Zero Crossing, etc	Tremor (L1) and No Tremor (L0) based on real-time observation	KNN, SVM, DT, Discriminant Analysis, NB, NN	F1-score, accuracy, precision, recall	Best (F-KNN): Accuracy: 98.3%, F1: 98.9% Lowest (LD): Accuracy: 89.5%, F1: 90.4%	KNN achieved near-perfect classification of tremor vs no-tremor; wearable leg-band sensors are highly effective for PD tremor detection.
Reardon, S. et al. 2024	24 PD	58.8 ± 9.5 years	58%	IMU sensors (accelerometer + gyroscope) on most affected wrist and ankle	78 features (e.g., signal power in 0.5–15 Hz band, Y-Z cross-correlation)	UPDRS-III Tremor sub-scores (0–16 scale).	XGBoost	Pearson correlation (r), Mean Absolute Error (MAE).	Best: r = 0.92 (total tremor, wrist + ankle, 64 Hz); r = 0.84–0.87 (rest tremor, wrist only). MAE for rest tremor as low as 0.41.	The XGBoost model using wrist accelerometer data at 32 Hz provided reliable, cost-effective, and consistent estimations of Parkinson's tremor sub-scores, offering practical potential for continuous daily monitoring via wearables.
Rodriguez, F. et al. 2024	24 PD	64.3 ± 8.8 years	50%	IMUs (ZurichMOVE) - triaxial accelerometers and gyroscopes	Time-domain statistics, Frequency-domain features, Non	MDS UPDRS III & 3.15R, L; 3.16R, L; 3.17UR, UL, LR, LL; 3.18	Support vector machine (SVM) with radial basis	Accuracy, Sensitivity	Accuracy: 0.88, Sensitivity: 0.9	A wearable-based SVM system for continuous Parkinson's tremor monitoring in free-living patients shows promise

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
					linear features		functions (RBFs)			but faces challenges in distinguishing mild tremors and relies on resampling techniques to address dataset imbalance.
Wu, H. et al. 2024	28 PD	61.5 ± 9 years	68%	Pebble smartwatch, a GeneActiv wearable sensor, and a Samsung smartphone	117 features for each window, including Energy Threshold, Common Baseline Features, Welch's One-Sided Power Spectral Density (PSD), Acceleration Correlation Coefficients, and FFT of Acceleration Correlation Coefficients	MDS UPDRS III sub-items scale [0, 4] & upper-limb and lower-limb presence/absence of dyskinesia	Learnable Discriminative Instance Pool	Accuracy. Recall. Precision. F1-score	Accuracy: 0.727, Recall: 0.711, Precision: 0.910 F1-score: 0.798	The proposed Learnable Discriminative Instance Pool (LDIP) algorithm enhances sample separability in bag-mapped feature spaces
Zhou C. et al., 2024	35 PD	44- 84 years	54.3 %	Inertial sensors (triaxial accelerations and angular velocities) and	Sensor data: Velocity, acceleration. Video data: Pose estimation	Severity scores from 12 PD rating scales.	Logistic Regression, K-Neighbors (KNN), Bayesian Regression,	Accuracy, precision.	Hybrid model: ~94% average accuracy across all 12 scales. Sensor	The hybrid model outperformed single-modality models, demonstrating that combining motion sensor data and video data

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
				video recordings.	(velocity, gait parameters).		Random Forest.		model: ~91% accuracy. Video model: ~89% accuracy.	enhances Parkinson's disease detection.
Adams et al., 2023	82 PD, 50 HC. For tremor specifically, 44 PD, 22 HC	PD cohort (n = 82): 63.3 +/- 9.4 HC (n = 50): 60.2 +/- 9.9	PD cohort : 56% HC: 36%	Accelerometry data and tremor scores were collected from the smartwatch via Apple's Movement Disorders API	Tremor classification from Apple's movement disorder application	The relationship between the passive tremor fraction and tremor res from the MDS-UPDRS was estimated using linear regression.			Tremor fraction measured correlated moderately with self-reported tremor severity (MDS-UPDRS part II, item 10, $r = 0.43$, $p = 0.003$), very strongly with clinician-reported upper extremity rest tremor amplitude (MDS-UPDRS part III, item 17, $r = 0.86$, $p < 0.001$), and strongly with rest tremor constancy (MDSUPDRS part III, item 18, $r = 0.79$, $p < 0.001$)	The smartwatch was worn on only one wrist. The side worn by PD participants (more affected side) and controls (individual preference) differed and at times was inconsistent with actual use. Standardizing wear for all participants to one side may be simpler and provide more consistent data.

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Aghanav esi et al., 2020	19 PD	71.4 ± 6.3 years	73.6%	Accelerometers and gyroscopes on each leg	24 features for each foot	UPDRS scale [0, 4], TRS scale [-4,0], dyskinesia scale [0,4]	SVM, Decision Trees, Linear Regression	Pearson correlation coefficients and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)	correlation coefficient (RMSE)of: TRS:0.81, UPDRS #31: 0.83, SUMUPDRS: 0.78, dyskinesia: 0.67	The best combination of feature selection and machine learning methods was stepwise regression and SVM, leg agility data is less suitable for capturing dyskinesias compared to motion sensor data during walking tests
Bazgir et al., 2018	52 PD (36 Training /16 testing)	PD: 54±13 HC: 53±7	Train: 55% Test: 62.5%	Smartphone attached to hands	F0 (fundamental frequency), MaxPSD, MeanPSD, SF50, F50, F50-F0	UPDRS scale [0, 4]	4 classifiers: Naive Bayesian/KN N/ANN/SVM	Test accuracy	Naive Bayesian 89% KNN 52% ANN 81% SVM 60%	Of the four tested classifiers, the Naive Bayesian approach was the most accurate one.
Duque et al., 2020	19 PD, 20 ET and 12 HS			Gyroscope providing angular velocities	Eight kinematic features in the frequency domain	PD(4-6Hz)/ET(1-16Hz)	Many classification algorithms are evaluated. Best: Linear SVM	Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity	Average accuracy 77.8 9.9% (75.7% sensitivity, 80.0% specificity)	Accuracy of the tremor differentiation using a gyroscope sensor is comparable to the performance obtained using a mobile phone's built-in accelerometer
Hssayeni et al., 2019	24 PD	58.9 ± 9.3 y	58.33 %	Accelerometer and gyroscope	78		XGBoost, LSTM	total tremor sub-score [0–28], Resting and Action Tremor sub-score [0-8]	XGBoost: MAE: 1.56, r (p):0.96 (<1×10 ⁻⁴)	XGBoost surpassed LSTM, effectively capturing tremor fluctuations linked to medication intake, However, it exhibited lower specificity for non-tremor-dominant cases, indicating room for enhancement with a larger dataset covering higher tremor sub-scores

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Hssayeni et al., 2021		58 ± 10 y	60%	Gyroscope, two sensors were mounted on the wrist and ankle. (Great Lakes NeuroTechnologies Inc., Cleveland, OH at 64Hz	13 temporal and spectral features	mAIMS score. In mAIMS, a severity score between 0 and 4 (no dyskinesia to severe dyskinesia) is given for each one of the four extremities, head/neck, trunk and global. The total mAIMS is the sum of all these sub-scores resulting in a range between 0 and 28.	LSTM	Pearson correlation (r) and mean absolute error (MAE)	r = 0.87 (p < 0.001) and MAE = 1.74 (6.2% of the maximum mAIMS score)	LSTM demonstrated good performance
Jeon et al., 2017	85 PD	65.96 ± 9.19	48%	Accelerometer and a gyroscope	13 features from each of four signals (acceleration, angular velocity, displacement, and angle)		Decision tree (DT), SVM, discriminant analysis (DA), RF, and kNN	Accuracy, Recall, Precision, AUC	85.5% using Decision Tree classifier	Very efficient approach for the development of an automatic scoring system for tremors in PD using machine-learning algorithms
Kim et al., 2018	92 PD	67.1 ± 9.0 y	48.91 %	Accelerometer and gyroscope			CNN	accuracy, kappa, correlation, RMSE	accuracy = 0.85, linear weighted kappa = 0.85, correlation = 0.93, RMSE = 0.35	CNN can automatically learn concepts using minimally processed raw data without the use of a manual feature extraction process.
Kostikis et al., 2015	25 PD/20 Controls	PD: 70.91 ± 11.78 HC: 67.20 ± 6.25	49%	i-Phone phone's accelerometer and gyroscope	16 classification features	PD/HC discrimination	Six ML algorithms tested	Sensitivity (TP), specificity (TN), and AUC	AUC between 0.80 and 0.94	Proposed method for quantifying upper limb Parkinsonian tremor can be used both in a clinical and home settings
Legaria-Santiago	PT: 354 (PD) 40(HC)	PD: 66 ±9.7	PD: 38%	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer	Five biomechanical indicators	MDS-UPDRS scale (0, 4)	Fuzzy inference model	Recall, Precision	Normal 0.90(R) .89 (P) / Slight 0.81(R) .82(P) /	Expert system based on biomechanical

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
et al., 2022	/ RT 200 (PD) 20 (HC)	HC:31.28 ±14.1	HC: 75%	(only for static acceleration cancellation)	based on time, frequency, and energy				Mild 1(R) 1(P) / Moderate 1(R) 1(P)	measurements and explainable inference rules
Li et al., 2018	9 PD	64 y	55%	Video at 30fps + Open pose 2D skeleton	32 for each joint. 15 kinematic, 16 spectral, last convex hull of the area that a joint moved within.	Sum of the seven highest impairment scores for each body part (face, neck, right arm/shoulder, left arm/shoulder, trunk, right leg/hip, left leg/hip) across 3 tasks (communication, drinking, ambulation), [0, 28].		Area under ROC (AUC)	The best AUC for detecting onset of dyskinesia was 0.822 and for remission of dyskinesia was 0.958, compared to 0.826 and 0.802 for the UPDRS.	Features achieved similar or superior performance to the UPDRS for detecting the onset and remission of dyskinesia.
Li et al., 2022	93 PD, 27 HC	N/A	N/A	Smartphone camera@30 fps	Hand joints from media pipe to measure speed and distance between thumb and index fingers	MDS-UPDRS finger tapping score (0, 4)	CNN	accuracy	accuracy: 79.7	Better to use extracted joints as input data rather than the video (with a 3DCNN model). Range of motion (i.e. distance between joints) might be a better feature than speed
Lin et al., 2023	84 PD, 80 ET	PD:58.13 ± 10.4, ET:58.7 ± 13.9	PD 54.76 % ET 46.25 %	Accelerometer and gyroscope			Random Forest, SVM	accuracy, Kappa, sensitivity, specificity, AUC	accuracy of 84%, Kappa of 0.68, sensitivity of 85.9%, specificity of 82.1%, and AUC of 0.912	Wearable sensor data paired with machine learning can differentiate early-stage PD from ET based on gait and postural transition parameters.
Liu et al., 2023	130 PD	N/A	N/A	Sony camera 1920×1280@30fps	Eulerian Video Magnification (EVM)	modified MDS-UPDRS [0,1,2,3+]	Resnet50 + Global Temporal Shift Module	AUC, precision, recall, F1 score	mean Precision of 0.92, mean recall of 90%, and F1 score	EVM pre-processing of video and temporal differences as input, along with ResNet

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
					processed video to enhance temporal differences between frames		(based on TSM)		of 0.91 for hand rest tremors.	embedded with a novel module, namely Global Shift Module (GSM), seems to be able to capture rest and postural tremor from videos
Lo et al., 2019	237 PD	N/A	N/A	Voice, touchscreen, accelerometer	998 (top 30)		Random Forest	AUC	For all outcome predictions AUC>0.9 (all features), AUC>0.75 (top30 features)	Allows for early prediction of key clinical outcomes in Parkinson's disease, potentially enabling personalized care and timely interventions based on predictive assessments using a smartphone test
Lones et al., 2017	Study 1: 6, Study 2:17	Study 1: 71±8.9 Study 2: 65±7.3	Study 1: 66.6% Study 2: 64.7%	Six degrees of freedom wearable accelerometer and gyroscope sensor modules	Acceleration time series	UPDRS (0-4)	Genetic Programming : Implicit context representation Cartesian GP (IRCGP)	ROC curve, or AUC, when discriminating samples of Grade 3 and 4 dyskinesia from movement samples with no dyskinesia	AUC up to 0.9	Time domain classifiers have significantly higher AUCs than spectral classifiers, reaching AUCs more than 0.9 on the test set. More accurate classifiers can be built from accelerometry (than gyro) data. Good ability to separate samples with Grades 3 and 4 dyskinesia from samples with no dyskinesia
Mahadevan et al., 2020	PD: 31 HC:50	PD: 68.1 ± 8.13 HC: 43.9 ± 10.02	PD: 64% HC: 46%	Accelerometer	time and frequency domain features	tremor constancy (MDS-UPDRS III.18) and amplitude (MDS-UPDRS III.17)	Detection: binary resting tremor classifier (RF)	Detection: leave one-subject-out	Tremor Detection: accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score / Resting	Tremor detection: 83% accuracy Rest tremor: good agreement with clinical ratings of resting tremor constancy (Kruskal-Wallis chi-

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
									tremor: Kruskal–Wallis chi-squared, p	squared = 27.52, p < 0.0001) and resting tremor amplitude (Kruskal–Wallis chi-squared = 18.14, p = 0.0004).
Pan et al., 2015	40 PD	44-84y	87.5%	For hand rest tremor user attaches the smartphone to the back of the hand and leaves the hand hanging for 20 seconds	Five power spectrum features and the average acceleration of motion of hand resting tremor.	UPDRS III Item 20 (1-3)	SVM	sensitivity/specificity	sensitivity was .77 and specificity was .82	Cost, size, unobtrusiveness, and ease of use are all factors impacting usefulness of such a system.
Pierleon et al., 2019	40 PD/15 Controls	PD: 65-80 HC: 53-67	56%	Custom wearable device with accelerometer and gyroscope	FFT, F0, PSD estimation	UPDRS scale [0, 4]	Thresholding based two parameters (K,H) calculated from PSD	accuracy	Accuracy = 97.7%	Completely unobtrusive approach based on a custom-made wearable using accelerometer and gyroscope.
Powers et al., 2021	PD: 343 HC: 171	PD cohort1: 68.1± 9.1 y / PD cohort2: 71.4± 8.9 y / HC: 74.7± 5.4 y	PD: 69% HC: 49%	Raw accelerometer and gyroscope data from Apple Watch	Tremor detection: Sharp peaks in FFT within the 3-7Hz bins. Tremor assessment: Measuring displacement either in time or frequency domain. Dyskinesia: a) motion strength and	a) Tremor detection (0/1), b) tremor classification into 4 classes: slight/mild/moderate/severe displacements	N/A	Validation of displacement using Motion capture tests	rank correlation coefficient	Tremor: Computed displacement correlated with expert MDS-UPDRS tremor amplitude ratings, with a rank correlation coefficient of 0.80 Dyskinesia: CMS showed significant differences (P<0.001) for all pairwise comparisons using a Wilcoxon rank sum test

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
					b) spectral entropy/Calculation of a Choreiform Movement Score					
Samadi et al., 2020	50 PD	58±7.4 y	N/A	Accelerometer, Sony Xperia SP Android smartphone	Mean PSD, Side Frequency (SF)	UPDRS scale [0, 4]	Naive bayes classifier	Accuracy, specificity, sensitivity	accuracy = 95.91±1.51 specificity = 95.8±1.21 sensitivity = 93.87±0.95	ML models that use frequency domain features from STFT can classify patients to their UPDRS scores
San-Segundo et al., 2020	12 PD	62-85 y	N/A	Accelerometer from Axivity AX3 at 100Hz	Original spectrum, Tremor spectrum, non-tremor spectrum for x, y, z in accelerometer	Tremor detection, i.e., Tremor/No tremor	1DCNN-MLP	LAB: Area Under the Curve (AUC) and False Positive Rate (FPR) at a 0.90 True Positive Rate (TPR). WILD: Spearman's r between percentage of tremor constancy and weak labels (<33%, 33–66%, and >66% tremor to	LAB: AUC=0.887 FPR=0.30 at 0.90 TPR WILD: weakLAB labels + WILD training /WILD = ~0.3 Spearman's r	When developing a real system, use MFCCs-T/NT when the amount of available data is not sufficient to train a deep neural network. In this situation, handcrafted features with traditional machine learning algorithms, like Random Forest, provide a reasonable performance. Additionally, the method for tremor spectrum extraction proposed in this paper contributes to increase this performance independently of the amount of available data. On the other hand, if there are enough data for training, the CNN-T/NT approach is preferred because this approach

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
								Almost none, Half the time, and almost always)		can learn relevant features for tremor detection"
Sigcha et al., 2021	18 PD	64.9 ± 7.6	44%	Triaxial accelerometer data from smartwatch	Multiple time and frequency characteristics	UPDRS III Item 17 and 18 (rest tremor)	multitask CNN trained with FFT	AUC, sensitivity, specificity	sensitivity: 86.1% specificity: 86.1% AUC: 0.93	Studies the use of consumer smartwatches and their embedded accelerometers for monitoring and evaluating resting tremor in PD patients. Includes a Table of highlighted research articles for tremor analysis using wearable sensors (Table 1).
Sun et al., 2023	30 PD	67.43 y	60%	Accelerometers and gyroscopes on both wrists	6 * 14 features from both the time and frequency domains (selection of hand-crafted features based on domain knowledge)	Tremor/No tremor	Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbours, Support Vector Machines, Convolutional Neural Networks	accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score	SVM: accuracy: 92.28%, precision: 92.40%, recall: 92.13%, F1-score: 92.26%	The performance of models using hand-crafted features surpasses CNN data-driven features, providing more specific boundaries in 2-D t-SNE feature visualization
Teng et al., 2023	48 PD, 60 HC	PD 58.6 ± 5.9 y, HC 64.9 ± 4.8 y	N/A	Touchscreen gestures and IMU signals	56 features of 4 categories (finger dexterity, posture stiffness, trajectory	Healthy/PD	XGBoost, Decision Tree, Random Forest	accuracy, precision, recall	accuracy: 91.6% (±1.5), recall: 84.85% (±4.7), recall: 85.2% (±2.7) (averaged on tap, swipe)	Integration of data from various sources (e.g., wearables, electrode patches, customized sensors) provides richer information for predicting PD onset, certain features such as finger dexterity

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
					information, and pressure information)					and tremor are more important in predicting PD onset
Varghese et al., 2016	192 PD, 75 other movement disorders, 51 HC	65.71 ± 9.61 y, 60.88 ± 15.58 y, 60.45 ± 14.22 y	62.57 %	Accelerometer			Fully Connected Network, Random Forest, SVM	accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score	Fully Connected Network (task1): accuracy: 89%, precision: 94%, recall: 92%, F1-score: 93%, SVM (task2): accuracy: 79%, precision: 81%, recall: 89%, F1-score: 85%	Mobile system only requires self-generated data from a 15-minute examination, not dependent on further patient data or external information systems, Machine Learning classifiers show high accuracy for distinguishing relevant diagnoses classes
Wang et al., 2021	55 PD	N/A	N/A	Microsoft Kinect TM v2, specifically 1920×1080 RGB at 30fps	21 hand key-points using media pipe. Then, use those to calculate a) frequency of motion direction changes and b) change in distance of hand movement	Bain and Findley Tremor Clinical Rating Scale [0, 10]	1D CNN - LSTM	Average accuracy, Average precision, Average recall, Average F1 score	accuracy = 0.81, precision = 0.81, recall = 0.79, F1= 0.80	hand tremor could be automatically detected despite a cluttered background
Yuan et al., 2021	20 PD	60.7 ± 8.6	75%	Wrist accelerometers	Mean amplitude, Sample entropy, Dominant	Tremor detection (0-1)	KNN / RF / AdaBoost / SVM	Sensitivity (%), Specificity (%), Accuracy	Best classification(detection) model is RF: Sensitivity	Balance data before classification using the SMOTE algorithm, A new indicator, namely Tremor timing ratio (TTR), was

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
					frequency, Energy, Spectrum concentration around dominant frequency			(%) F1 score (%)	95.18 Specificity 94.44 Accuracy 94.81 F1 score 94.83	designed and calculated to quantify tremor severity.
Ziogas et al., 2023	16 PD rest tremor dataset introduced by Beuter.	HAT: 58.5 ± 9.78yrs; LAT: 52.7 ± 10.19yrs	N/A	IMU data from a velocity-transducing laser	Set of proposed features that are drawn from the Bispectrum/Bicoherence domains	LAT/HAT (Low/High Amplitude Tremor)	Four classifiers are evaluated: RBF-SVM, Linear SVN, k-NN and Logistic Regression	Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO)	AUC	AUC score of 0.94 for the Medication treatment classification, 0.71 for the DBS treatment and 0.83 for LAT/HAT prediction.

Papers including results on dyskinesia assessment are designated with (D) in the Notes column. The rest focus only on tremor assessment.

General discussion

Passive solutions for rest tremor monitoring based on Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data are increasingly popular in the literature, while similar approaches for dyskinesia have been less studied. Most papers use features in the time or frequency domain derived from either a) a single accelerometer sensor or b) accelerometer and gyroscope sensors. As noted in Powers et al. (2021), frequency domain approaches have limitations in accuracy due to a) the sinusoidal approximation performed and b) Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) frequency resolution limits; however, they are generally preferable as they are more robust than the time domain methods.

For the estimation of PD rest tremor, studies have reported the resting tremor (RT) of PD occurs at frequencies between 3-7 Hz, so in most cases, features are designed to detect sharp peaks within this range from the FFT or Power Spectral Density. Recent works have confirmed strong tremor detection performance even in real-world settings using wearable sensors and hybrid features. Regarding dyskinesia detection, motion strength and spectral entropy features can be employed. However, despite some promising results using deep learning and federated models, dyskinesia detection continues to be more challenging due to symptom overlap and labelling difficulties.

Also noteworthy are approaches detecting rest tremor from video by using Eulerian magnification to amplify changes in video pixels over time, so that very small motions can become visible to the human eye (Liu et al., 2023).

As evidenced by correlation analysis between digital and clinical measures, efficient rest tremor detection and assessment is possible based on data from a single accelerometer. On the other hand, dyskinesia seems to be much harder to identify.

2.3.7 Digital assessments of rigidity and bradykinesia

Digital technology is becoming increasingly popular in capturing specific motor symptoms in movement disorders. This literature review aims to investigate digital methods for assessing bradykinesia and rigidity. We primarily focused on studies leveraging wearable sensors and smart devices to monitor these motor symptoms. Utilising such technology enables the continuous monitoring of bradykinesia and rigidity, outside the clinic, albeit complementing clinical decision and personalising disease management.

Study selection

Within the Rayyan software, the following keywords were used: “bradykinesia”, “slowness”, “rigidity”, “limb”. For the initial literature search spanning between 2013 and 2023, 265 unique records were found and 32 of them were excluded as they were reviews. When the same search was performed for papers published for the updated search (spanning between 2023 and 2025), 182 papers were identified, 37 of them were reviews and thus removed. We particularly focused on study designs that can be conducted remotely, at the comfort of people’s homes. Thus, studies involving lab-based equipment were excluded during the screening process. We also dropped studies presenting exclusively active tests. Subsequently, two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Where appropriate, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. This filtering returned a total of six records.

Table 22 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Briefly, a paper was considered eligible if:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,

AND

Clinical data of upper limb bradykinesia and/or rigidity assessment were provided,

AND

Use of experimental apparatus consisted of either wearable or smart devices. Use of devices for passive data recording.

Table 22 Selection criteria for digital assessments of rigidity and bradykinesia

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Measurement	Upper limb bradykinesia and/or rigidity
Apparatus	Wearable sensors and/or smart devices. Passive testing.

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	233	145	378
Articles included in literature table	5	1	6

Study characteristics

All six studies (**Table 23**) provided upper limb bradykinesia estimations, with two also estimating upper limb rigidity. MDS-UPDRS-III or the older version, UPDRS-III, were used as the clinical outcome for the quantification of motor symptoms. Interestingly, only two studies recruited a control group.

Noteworthy, the included studies covered a wide range of disease duration and severity. They recruited participants with a mean age ranging from 61 to 70.7 years; the percentage of male participants ranged from 45 to 78%. Mean disease duration varied from 2.5 to 12.5 years. The average motor severity score, in terms of MDS-UPDRS-III or UPDRS-III ranged from 16.9 to 68.8.

Digital assessments

Features derived from accelerometry, wearable electromyography (EMG) and keystroke dynamics can estimate the clinically assessed symptoms of bradykinesia and rigidity as evidenced by correlation analysis between digital and clinical measures. The included studies present diverse techniques for capturing rigidity and bradykinesia. Four studies utilized movement sensors such as accelerometers and gyroscopes, one study employed wearable EMG sensors alongside accelerometry, and one study utilised a touchscreen keyboard on smartphones to quantify keystroke dynamics.

Table 23 Studies about digital assessments of rigidity and bradykinesia

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male%	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Crowe et al., 2024	24 PD	70,7±8,5	67	3 different IMU sensors	132 statistical features (for b/k)	MDS-UPDRS	LR, SVM, Decision Tree, RF, GBTrees, Extra Trees, Bagging ensemble + feature selection (k highest scores)	Accuracy, recall, precision, AUC	Acc=63±17, Recall=62, Precision=69, AUC=65	Wrist accelerometry promises accurate tracking of b/k while an additional ankle sensor did not improve results
Iakovakis et al., 2018	PD=18, HC=15	PD=61, HC=57	78 for PD, 54 for HC	Custom smartphone keyboard	Statistical features of key hold time, Normalized flight time	UPDRS-III bradykinesia and rigidity features	RF	Pearson's correlation	Rigidity r=0.83, MAE=0.39 Upper Body bradykinesia r=0.69, MAE=0.41 Finger taps r=0.68, MAE= 0.55	Keystroke dynamics can accurately capture clinical rigidity and bradykinesia.
Mahadevan et al., 2020	PD=31, HC=50	PD=68.1, HC=43.9	64 for PD, 46 for HC	Inertial sensor (accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer) on wrist (side: most affected for PD, dominant for HC; sampling rate: 128Hz)	Bradykinesia (4), Optimal feature: amplitude of hand movements	MDS-UPDRS finger tapping, hand movements, hand pronation-sup.	Mixed effects model	Pearson correlation	R=0.67	Bradykinesia feature of amplitude of hand movement for the windows that passed the chained assessments is strongly negatively correlated (R=-0.69) with bradykinesia score. Mixed effect model predicts relatively well the b/k hand UPDRS score.

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male%	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Oyama et al., 2023	PD=96	62.3	45.8	Smartwatch (side: most convenient; sampling rate N/A)	features for: bradykinesia (8), tremor(8), gait(4), overall motor(21)	MDS-UPDRS-III consensus scores	LASSO	Spearman rank correlation	Bradykinesia r=0.63,	Good correlation and test-retest reliability (ICC=0.72) and excellent effect size for medication effects.
Rissanen et al., 2021	PD=16	62.75	56	Biceps brachii EMG and Accelerometer (side: most affected; sampling rate: EMG=1000Hz, Accelerometer=50Hz)	for EMG and ACC: kurtosis, burst frequency, correlation dimension, recurrence rate, signal power and sample entropy	UPDRS-III relevant items	PCA to identify the first factor and correlate it with the patients condition	Spearman rank correlation	The first Principal component was correlated with UPDRS-III	The first PC composed by both acceleration and EMG, was correlated with upper limb rigidity. EMG burst frequency was correlated with upper limb rigidity. EMG burst frequency, correlation Dimension, recurrence rate and ACC power (.2-4Hz) were correlated with upper limb bradykinesia
Shawen et al., 2020	PD=13	62.1	69	Movement sensor and Apple watch (side: most affected; sampling rate: 62.5 and 50Hz respectively)	74 kinematic features from each sensor	MDS-UPDRS tremor and bradykinesia scores	RF	AUROC	bradykinesia binary classification (have/not have) = 0.68 multiclass classification = 0,65	Combining accelerometer with gyroscope data yielded better performance compared to accelerometer alone. Sampling rates between 5 and 60Hz did not affect the bradykinesia classification accuracy, but 30Hz are needed to classify tremor.

General discussion

The aim of this review was to assess the effectiveness of digital tools in capturing bradykinesia and rigidity of upper limbs. Despite the abundance of studies conducting data collection in clinical settings, the objective of AI-PROGNOSIS is to assess these motor symptoms remotely and only six published studies to date were thus relevant.

The findings highlight the usefulness of digital tools such as wearable sensors (IMUs and EMG sensors) and sensors embedded into smart devices (i.e., smartwatches and smartphones) in accurately capturing rigidity and bradykinesia.

Studies by Iakovakis, Oyama, Mahadevan, Shawen and Crowe, collectively demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of using digital tools to capture features associated with upper limb rigidity and bradykinesia. These features range from keystroke dynamics to kinematic features extracted from wearable sensors during everyday activities. One study (Oyama et al., 2023) additionally demonstrated the robustness of such technologies to capture motor symptoms as evidenced by good test-retest reliability. Gyroscope data, alongside accelerometry can enhance the bradykinesia classification accuracy.

The updated version of our search identified a single publication. Crowe et al., (2024) used 3 IMU sensors to capture bradykinesia. Notable, they confirmed the utility of upper limb kinematics to track PD related bradykinesia. However, adding an ankle IMU sensor to the standard configuration (wrist worn sensors) did not improve the model performance.

This review presents crucial methodological insights into the data collection parameters that are essential for conducting experiments to assess motor symptoms in PD. One critical aspect is the sampling rate of the sensors used in the included studies which impacts the granularity, and effectively the quality of the data. Additionally, since PD is associated with asymmetrical motor symptoms the choice of the side at which participants wear the smartwatch constitutes an additional issue to be decided. Careful consideration of those parameters is paramount for designing data collection in such populations.

2.3.8 Digital assessments of posture and balance

Study selection

Our selection strategy for posture/balance digital assessment research focuses on selecting relevant publications within the Rayyan digital sensor literature search using specific keywords, such as fall(s), posture, balance, gait, and freezing of gait (fog). We excluded technological interventions that were not intended or effective for PD posture/balance evaluation, research unrelated to PD, and studies that examined platforms/services other than mobile applications. Furthermore, research that did not use mobile applications or mobile technology as supplementary tools was omitted. We thoroughly reviewed the titles and abstracts, followed by full-text screening for possibly relevant papers. **Table 24** summarizes the criteria for study inclusion for posture and balance digital assessment of PD. Inclusion criteria included the following:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,

AND

Methods and data for posture and balance assessment were provided,

AND

Use of data from wearable sensors and/or smart devices that enable monitoring of PD symptoms OR use of data from videos for posture and balance assessment.

Table 24 Selection criteria for digital assessments of posture and balance

Item	Definition
Population	PD patients
Keywords	Balance, posture, FOG, freezing, gait, fall
Outcomes	Motor assessment, postural abnormalities, gait dynamics, gait disorders, walking abnormalities, MDS-UPDRS scores, FOG detection, balance evaluation, arm swing analysis, and classification of PD based on gait information.
Apparatus	Wearable sensors (such as ankle, chest, and waist sensors), depth cameras (e.g., Kinect), noise-cancelling headband microphones, smart pillboxes, smartphones (Huawei P40), RGB-D cameras (Kinect v2.0), MS Kinect sensors, video recording devices, marker-less motion tracking tools (e.g., AlphaPose, OpenPose), and specialized systems for gait analysis (e.g., e-Motion Capture System, DensePose)

Initial Literature search

Using the Rayyan bibliographic searches, 383 articles were considered relevant for posture and balance digital assessment. These articles were carefully chosen based on specific keywords, including balance (26 articles), gait (209 articles), posture (29 articles), freezing of gait (85 articles), and falls (11 articles). Following a meticulous screening process, which involved assessing 68 articles for eligibility, a total of 25 articles were ultimately selected for inclusion in the analysis. The reasons for exclusion varied and encompassed factors such as the use of inappropriate sensor types (e.g., wearable sensors lacking a smartphone app), impractical system architectures, absence of ML or DL models, articles falling outside the scope of the study, use of inappropriate samples (e.g., healthy individuals instead of PD patients), review articles, focus solely on feasibility and usability metrics, study protocols, PD detection using speech or acoustic analysis, and usability studies.

Updated Literature Search

Using the Rayyan automated tool for filtering articles relevant to this domain, 271 records were identified concerning posture and balance (including gait, freezing, and falls) assessment. After removing 16 duplicates, the remaining 255 records were screened based on title and abstract. At this stage, 216 records were excluded due to the following reasons: wrong outcome ($n = 73$), wrong study design ($n = 67$), no video assessment ($n = 65$), or wrong population ($n = 11$). Then, 39 reports were sought for retrieval, but since one report could not be retrieved, 38 reports were assessed for eligibility. Following full-text screening, 24 reports were excluded due to the following reasons: no video assessment ($n = 16$), wrong population ($n = 5$), or lack of data ($n = 3$). Therefore, 14 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final review.

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	383	271	654
Articles included in literature table	25	14	39

Study characteristics of the initial literature search

The average age range recorded in studies such as Dias et al. (2020) and Hong et al. (2022) was between 50 and 70 years old, which is in line with the usual onset age of PD. Nonetheless, not all studies consistently reported on certain age groups. Furthermore, there was variation in the inclusion criteria for the severity of the condition; several studies focused on individuals with more advanced disease progression (Hong et al., 2022; Ferraris et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019), while other studies included individuals at different stages of the disease (Dias et al., 2020; Dranca et al., 2018). Several studies included control patients (Connie et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Abe et al., 2022; Procházka et al., 2015; Buongiorno et al., 2019; Muñoz-Ospina et al., 2022; Guayacán et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2021; Urcuqui et al., 2018).

Important clinico-demographic data was missing from some studies (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020), reported motor severity scores (Aldegheri et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2020; Dranca et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Procházka et al., 2015; Erfianto et al., 2023; Li et al., 2016; Tupa et al., 2015). Additionally, some studies did not include information about sex (Procházka et al., 2015; Li et al., 2016; Erfianto et al., 2023). Some studies (Aldegheri et al., 2023; Guayacán et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2021; Urcuqui et al., 2018; Buongiorno et al., 2019; Abe et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2022; Connie et al., 2022) also did not provide information on sex, disease duration, PD subtypes, and motor severity scores.

Study characteristics of the updated literature search

All included studies employed an observational design, with most adopting a cross-sectional approach, except for (Zhou, 2024), which conducted three sessions over a month period. Most studies incorporated control groups, typically comprising healthy controls (HC) or comparative groups such as PD subgroups (Russo et al., 2024), and other neurological disorders such as cerebellar ataxia and spinocerebellar ataxia (Sundari et al., 2024). However, a few studies did not include control groups (Moon et al., 2024; Stergioulas et al., 2024; Zhou, 2024). Sample sizes varied widely across studies, ranging from smaller cohorts of 14 participants per group (Ferraris et al., 2024) to larger datasets of up to 294 participants (Connie et al., 2025). The primary aims of the studies were diverse, including developing ML or video-based frameworks to predict motor symptom severity (Moon et al., 2024), investigating gait characteristics and postural stability (Stergioulas et al., 2024), and exploring differences between PD subgroups, such as those with sarcopenia (Kim et al., 2024) or mild cognitive impairment (MCI) (Russo et al., 2024), and PD detection (Hui et al., 2024; Sundari et al., 2024). Several clinical outcome measures were used as gold-standard PD assessment. The MDS-UPDRS Part III was the most frequently employed tool for evaluating motor severity, while the Hoehn and Yahr (H&Y) scale was used to classify disease stages. Cognitive assessments such as the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) and Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) were also applied. Additionally, specific scales such as the PIGD subscale for postural stability (Ferraris et al., 2024) and the Asian Working Group for Sarcopenia (AWGS) 2019 criteria for sarcopenia assessment (Kim et al., 2024) were used in some studies.

Regarding participant characteristics, the mean age of study populations varied, mostly ranging from the mid-60s to early 70s, with disease duration spanning from a few years to over a decade. Several studies categorized participants into subgroups based on clinical

criteria or comorbidities. For instance, (Deng et al., 2024) divided participants into low and high motor impairment groups, while (Kim et al., 2024) compared individuals with and without sarcopenia. Similarly, (Russo et al., 2024) explored differences in gait kinematics between PwPD with and without Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). Several technologies were used for data collection, namely standard video cameras (e.g., tablets, smartphones) (Deng et al., 2024; Hui et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2024; Stergioulas et al., 2024) and RGB-Depth sensors (Ellrich et al., 2024; Ferraris et al., 2024). Subsequently, the data were analysed using computer vision algorithms including MediaPipe, Alpha Pose, and BlazePose for pose estimation (Connie et al., 2025; Hui et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2024; Pappas et al., 2024; Sundari et al., 2024).

Depending on the complexity of the data and the study aim, these studies used various approaches to data analysis. Most studies used ML models such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), and Decision Trees (DT), which were frequently employed for classification tasks (Connie et al., 2025; Deng et al., 2024; Ferraris et al., 2024; Hui et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2024; Kour et al., 2024; Pappas et al., 2024; Russo et al., 2024; Stergioulas et al., 2024; Yin et al., 2024; Zhou, 2024). Ensemble methods such Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) and Gradient Boosted Tree (GBT) were applied to improve in some studies, aiming to enhance predictive accuracy (Deng et al., 2024; Russo et al., 2024). DL models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), were applied in scenarios requiring complex feature extraction, particularly for kinematic data analysis and automated scoring systems. (Moon et al., 2024) utilized a 2D-CNN combined with gradient-weighted class activation mapping (Grad-CAM) for explainable predictions based on gait kinematics. Moreover, several studies compared multiple classifiers to identify optimal approaches for specific assessment tasks. In certain cases, standard statistical methods were used for simpler analyses such as the pull test assessment (Ellrich et al., 2024).

Digital assessments of posture and balance

In the Initial Literature search, various sensors were employed across studies for posture and balance digital assessment. Studies explored automated systems for remote monitoring and assessment (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020; Aldegheri et al., 2023), proposing automated caretaking, balance evaluation, and posture analysis software, respectively. Additionally, motor assessment tools and Kinect-based systems for differentiating PD stages were developed (Dias et al., 2020; Dranca et al., 2018). Depth sensors and skeleton tracking in three-dimensional space were employed, as demonstrated by some studies (Procházka et al., 2015; Ferraris et al., 2019; Abe et al., 2022) while body motion was captured using kinetic sensors in others (Li et al., 2016; Dranca et al., 2018). Video recording, coupled with pose estimation tools such as AlphaPose, was used for extracting human joint coordinates (Guo et al., 2022; Abe et al., 2022). Similarly, video recording combined with OpenPose for analysis was employed (Liu et al., 2022). Additionally, a combination of Wii balance boards and Kinect sensors was used for balance evaluation (Wei et al., 2020). Standard video recording equipment was utilized for analysis in another study (Eguchi et al., 2023). Automatic recognition of Freezing of Gait (FOG) in PD patients (Li et al., 2022) and detection of abnormal gait transitions (Erfianto et al., 2023) were also explored. A mobile decision support system for PD management (Buongiorno et al., 2019) and a machine learning algorithm for PD classification (Muñoz-Ospina et al., 2022) were proposed. Further, regional kinematic analysis to identify potential digital biomarkers of PD was conducted (Guayacán et al., 2022). Lastly, a neural network for estimating MDS-UPDRS scores (Lu et al., 2021) and a machine learning classifier for PD analysis based on gait data (Urcuqui et al., 2018) were introduced.

Collectively, these studies showcase innovative technological advancements for improved PD monitoring and assessment. **Table 25** provides an overview of study characteristics, methodologies, and results in balance and posture digital assessment of PD.

In the updated literature search several studies have focused specifically on video-based posture and balance assessment. (Ellrich et al., 2024) applied vision-based assessment to the clinical pull test, demonstrating excellent accuracy and concurrent validity with gold standard motion capture systems, while effectively distinguishing healthy performance from varying degrees of postural impairment in PD. (Ferraris et al., 2024) presented a system for automatic evaluation of postural stability suitable for home use, utilizing an RGB-Depth camera to assess centre of mass parameters during three balance tasks. Their system achieved high accuracy (89.2-96.4%) and successfully detected stability differences between PD subjects and controls, particularly during dual-task conditions. (Stergioulas et al., 2024) employed smartphone-based video analysis for balance and posture assessment, finding that KNN classifiers performed best for most assessment items, though noting that gait assessment results indicated room for improvement.

Moreover, video-based gait assessment has been reported in the literature. (Kim et al., 2024) investigated gait patterns in PwPD with and without sarcopenia, identifying key predictive features including knee-ankle angle differences during walking and minimum hip angle. The RF model achieved excellent performance on the test set (precision: 1.0, accuracy: 0.949). (Yin et al., 2024) investigated a non-contact gait assessment system that demonstrated excellent performance in distinguishing early-stage PD from HC (accuracy: 91.43%, AUC: 0.99). Moreover, early-stage PwPD exhibited reduced stride length, decreased gait speed, slower stride and swing speeds, extended turning time, and reduced cadence. (Connie et al., 2025) proposed FuGaPS, combining point cloud and silhouette data for gait analysis, achieving AUC up to 0.87 and F1-scores up to 0.82. They established that silhouette-based methods are particularly promising for clinical settings where background subtraction is feasible. Lastly, (Zhou, 2024) developed a hybrid ML system combining videos of freezing of gait with numerical sensor data, achieving approximately 94% accuracy across multiple clinical scales—outperforming models using either video (89%) or sensor data (91%) alone. Some studies have also focused on developing explainable and interpretable models based on kinematic data. (Deng et al., 2024) developed a framework using kinematic data extracted from clinical videos, achieving promising results with combined body and hand features (AUC: 0.79, accuracy: 0.72). This approach emphasized interpretability by incorporating pre-defined digital features, a combination of vi/domain kinematic features, and sparsity-inducing ML analysis. (Moon et al., 2024) proposed an explainable AI-driven approach to predict MDS-UPDRS Part III scores based on kinematic gait data, achieving very low loss values (MSE: 0.0161 for training, 0.1673 for validation). Their approach identified significant correlations between single-leg support phase, swing phase, and Parkinsonian gait characteristics.

In addition, two studies employing marker-based motion capture systems were also included in this review, aiming to enhance the robustness of the analysis. In particular, (Russo et al., 2024) conducted a cross-sectional study comparing gait kinematics and kinetics in PwPD with and without mild cognitive impairment (MCI). A 3D optoelectronic system with six cameras and 22 passive retro-reflective markers complemented by force platforms embedded in a walkway was used during single-task and dual-task walking. Key findings revealed distinct movement patterns between groups, with kinematic analysis identifying greater symptom severity in PD-MCI, where cognitive impairment coexisted with more severe posture and gait dysfunction. These findings align with those of several previous studies, while providing additional insights on the interaction between motor impairment and cognitive status. Furthermore, (Kour et al., 2024) developed a vision-based hybrid ensemble learning approach

for distinguishing pathological and normal gait patterns among people with knee osteoarthritis, PwPD, and HC, based on the analysis of standardized walking and turning tasks. Using a marker-based dataset, the main parameters comprised linear kinematics (e.g., displacement, acceleration, speed, velocity) and spatial-temporal gait features (e.g., stride length, step length, stride period, step period). The use of an innovative segmentation method (i.e., Color Segmentation based Fractional Order Darwinian Particle Swarm Optimization (CS-FODPSO)) with the hybrid ensemble-based classifier (i.e., KNN, DT, and NB) held superior accuracy in differentiating between sample subgroups (i.e., classification according with disease severity), when compared with traditional approaches.

Table 25 provides an overview of study characteristics, methodologies, and results in balance and posture digital assessment of PD.

Table 25 Studies about digital assessments of posture and balance.

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
Connie et al., 2025	n = 294 (PD/HC = 144/150)	To propose FuGaPS (Fusion of Gait Point Cloud and Silhouette), a vision-based approach to diagnosing PD using both model-free and model-based gait.	n/a	Mean age = 68 ± 5.83 years; Gender (% M/F) = 67.1/32.9; PD duration and UPDRS-III data not available.	Online video recordings were selected where the subject is walking, and their full body is visible in the video (AlphaPose).	Fusion of point cloud and silhouette features.	Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest Classifier, Extra Trees Classifier, Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Decision Trees achieved an AUC of up to 0.87 and F1-Scores of up to 0.82, with precision reaching 0.85 and recall at 0.80.	A fusion of model-free and model-based gait features offers great improvement over model-based gait for PD screening. Using silhouettes in gait tests is very promising since most clinical gait tests are performed in indoor settings where background subtraction is not a challenge. Moreover, silhouettes will capture most posture-based features, while model-based descriptors will capture more

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
								kinematic features.
Deng et al., 2024	n=58 (low motor impairment / high motor impairment = 33/25). (low motor impairment: PD=3, PSP=0, PUCS=1; high motor impairment: PD=17, PSP=7, PUCS=1)	Developing a video-based framework to automatically predict PD motor symptom high versus low severity according to the MDS-UPDRS Part III metrics (total score).	MDS-UPDRS, Hoehn and Yahr, MoCA	Age—67.1 ± 7.4 (low imp) / 71.4 ± 6.2 (high imp); Gender (% M/F)—60.6/39.4 (low imp) / 60.0/40.0 (high imp); PD duration—7.4 ± 4.0 years (low imp) / 5.9 ± 3.0 years (high imp); UPDRS-III Score—18.5 ± 10.3 (low imp) / 43.4 ± 8.2 (high imp).	Video kinematic data were retrospectively extracted from the individual subject's clinical videos. The video clips were collected with a single tablet camera, which is mounted on a fixed stand.	Neck angle, Arm-body lateral angle, Left/right wrist-shoulder distance, Left/right ankle-hip distance, Ankle separation, Knee separation, Body sway, Leg raise, Shoulder tilt, Hip tilt, Finger tapping, Middle finger movement, Ring finger movement, Pinky finger movement.	Models: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Adaptive-Boosted Trees (AdaBoost, AB), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB). Performance scores: Body Features—AUC: 0.76 (LR), Accuracy: 0.71 (SVM); Hand Features—AUC: 0.68 (AB), Accuracy: 0.67	The study highlights three key aspects: (1) automated, data-driven kinematic metric evaluation guided by predefined digital movement features, (2) integration of bi-domain kinematic features encompassing both body and hand movements, and (3) a sparsity-inducing, stability-driven machine learning approach designed for interpretability and robust analysis.

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
							(LR, RF, AB); Combined Features— AUC: 0.79 (LR), Accuracy: 0.72 (SVM, LR).	
Ellrich et al., 2024	HC/PD/am_HC = 15/15	To explore the potential for objective, vision-based assessment of the pull test (vPull) using 3D pose tracking applied to single-sensor RGB-Depth recordings of clinical assessments.	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, LEED	HC/PD/am_HC groups had mean ages of 32.2 ± 7.0 , 70.1 ± 8.8 , and 69.9 ± 8.3 years, respectively, with gender (% M/F of 46.67/53.33 (HC), 46.67/53.33 (PD), and 53.33/46.67 (am_HC); PD duration and UPDRS-III data were not available.	The RGB-Depth sensor (Azure Kinect) was mounted on a tripod at a height of one meter and positioned two meters in front of the participant undergoing the pull test. Each recording had a fixed duration of 10 seconds.	Bilateral body landmarks of the shoulders, hips, and ankles were utilized to analyze the pulling movement, subsequent stepping, and truncal response.	Standard statistical analysis was applied, demonstrating excellent accuracy and concurrent validity in assessing both the magnitude of the pull and the spatiotemporal aspects of stepping and postural responses.	The inter-rater reliability of vPull and analyzed PD-related impairments in postural response were evaluated, including pull-to-step latency, number of steps, and retropulsion angle. These metrics effectively distinguish healthy performance from varying degrees of postural impairment in PD, offering valuable insights

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
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								into disease progression.
Ferraris et al., 2024	HC/PD = 14/14	To present a system for the automatic evaluation of postural stability that is suitable for self-managing by people with motor impairment directly at home	PIGD subscale, MMSE, H&Y	PD group had a mean age of 67.8 years (range: 54–75) and a mean PD duration of 6.7 years (range: 3–9); gender distribution and UPDRS-III data were not available.	Optical RGB-Depth camera (Kinect). Three tasks have been designed as derived directly from the Berg balance scale: Up-Stand-Down (USD), Tandem-Standing (TS), Reaching-Standing (RS).	Center of Mass of the body (CoMBody), calculated as the weighted average of the center of mass (CoMi) of six body segments (head, trunk, legs, and arms) whose lengths were evaluated from the corresponding joint segments of the skeletal model.	Support Vector Machine (SVM) achieved an accuracy of 89.2% for PD vs. HC in USD, 92.8% in RS, and 96.4% in TS, with stability severity classification scores of 64.3% (USD), 67.8% (RS), and 71.4% (TS).	CoM parameters successfully detect the expected worsening of the stability that occurs in PD subjects for the DT condition. CoM parameters are also more sensitive in discriminating the worsening of the postural stability in PD subjects than in CG subjects.
Hui et al., 2024	n/a (Healthy controls / PD)	To apply camera-based data collection to analyze gait patterns that can identify a risk of PD.	n/a	n/a	Camera-based data collection to analyze gait patterns (TUG test) that can identify a risk of PD; computer vision and AlphaPose to	Stance time, swing time, step length, step time, stride length, stride time, cadence	Support Vector Machines (SVM) and CatBoost both achieved an accuracy, precision, and recall of	The combination of advanced data analysis methods and medical knowledge offers new possibilities to develop targeted

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					analyze video data.		0.8333, with an F1 score of 0.78, demonstrating equal performance across metrics.	treatments that improve patient outcomes, demonstrating the potential of ML in effectively managing and treating PD.
Kim et al., 2024	PD_sarc / PD_n/sarc = 9 / 29	To investigate the gait patterns of PwPD with and without sarcopenia using an app-derived program, and explored if gait parameters could be utilized to predict sarcopenia based on ML.	H&Y, handgrip strength, 6m walking, MDS-UPDRS-III, LEDD, AWGS 2019 (sarcopenia assessment)	Age— N/A; Gender (% M/F)— 11.11/88.89 (PD_sarc), 37.93/62.07 (PD_n/sarc); PD Duration—5.3 ± 3.3 years (PD_sarc), 5.9 ± 4.4 years (PD_n/sarc); UPDRS-III Score—28.3 ± 10.7 (PD_sarc), 31.7 ± 9.3 (PD_n/sarc).	Participants walked a 6-meter linear path twice at a self-selected pace, without any imposed velocity limit. Smartphone cameras were strategically positioned at 1-meter intervals along the central axis of the path to capture motion data. using BlazePose.	Angles at the hip, knee, ankle and shoulder.	Random Forest model performance: Training set— precision: 0.981, recall: 0.680, specificity: 0.995, accuracy: 0.911, F1-Score: 0.803; Test set— perfect precision and specificity, recall: 0.667, accuracy: 0.949, F1-Score: 0.800.	The top three features for predicting sarcopenia include: (1) Kneeankle_diff—the combined difference in knee and ankle angles from standing still to the maximum angle during walking; (2) Ankle_dif—the difference between the ankle angle while standing still and its maximum angle during walking; and (3)

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								Hip_min—the minimum angle of the hip joint. These features demonstrated the strongest predictive capability for sarcopenia.
Kour et al., 2024	KOA / PD / HC = 50 / 20 / 30	To predict the pathological and normal (NM) gait based on the marker based (MB) vision-based (VB) platform.	n/a	n/a	Participants walked at a self-selected pace for 4.5 meters, turned around, and returned to the start. The study utilized a marker-based (MB) dataset for motion tracking and analysis.	Linear kinematics: displacement, acceleration, speed, and velocity during gait. Spatial-temporal gait features: stride length, step length, stride period, step period.	The DT-KNN-NB (DKN) hybrid model demonstrated strong classification performance across PD severity levels, achieving high accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and precision. Moderate vs severe PD classification reached 90.36% accuracy, while severe vs mild PD	The proposed CS-FODPSO-based segmentation method showed the highest results accuracy thus outperforming other techniques such as Otsu's and GMM. An efficient hybrid ensemble-based classifier is applied to predict whether a person has KOA, PD, or no disease

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							achieved 90.10% accuracy. Overall PD classification showed robust results with 90.90% accuracy, 91.34% sensitivity, 93.01% specificity, and 89.32% precision, highlighting its effectiveness in distinguishing disease severity.	including disease severity.
Moon et al., 2024	PD = 30	To propose an explainable ML approach to automate PD diagnosis by predicting the total MDS-UPDRS Part III score based on a	MDS-UPDRS III	Male PD participants had a mean age of 69 ± 7 years, while female PD participants averaged 63 ± 8 years; gender distribution was 50% male and	PD patient wearing the Optitrack motion capture system walked a six-meter straight line in four trials.	Ankle, knee, and hip joint angles during each gait cycle.	A two-dimensional convolutional neural network (2D-CNN) with gradient-weighted class activation mapping (Grad-CAM)	The proposed approach effectively predicts the total MDS-UPDRS Part III score, while highlighting key features associated with Parkinsonian

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		patient's kinematic data during gait.		50% female; PD duration and UPDRS-III data were not available.			was used. The prediction model achieved very low loss values, with MSE of 0.0161 for training and 0.1673 for validation. The final mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of the validation set was 10.47%.	gait. Notably, significant predictors are linked to both the single leg support phase and the swing phase, providing valuable insights into disease-related motor impairments.
Pappas et al., 2024	HC_validation /// HC/PD = 32 / 17/17	To introduce a method utilizing ML algorithms for video-based clinical gait analysis of frontal plane videos recorded with readily available devices.	UPDRS gait item	HC and PD groups had mean ages of 64 ± 9 and 62 ± 8 years, respectively; gender distribution was 47.85% male / 52.95% female for HC and 58.82% male / 41.18% female for PD; PD duration averaged 30 ± 17	Open-source body pose (Google's MediaPipe) and metric depth (ZoeDepth) estimators to calculate spatiotemporal parameters (STP) of gait from videos.	MoCap joint trajectories were analyzed by identifying heel strikes by plotting the vertical trajectories of the left and right ankles throughout the sequence. Right and left	Logistic regression achieved an average AUC of 0.79, precision of 0.68, and sensitivity of 0.75.	The proposed methodology was applied to gait videos of healthy controls and individuals with PD, demonstrating strong alignment with high-end instrumental gait analysis techniques. The

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				months; UPDRS-III data were not available.		heel strikes, gait speed, step time, step length, cadence.		results support the effectiveness of using gait videos for detecting PD, highlighting its potential for accessible and reliable assessment.
Russo et al., 2024	PD-noMCI / PD-MCI = 50 / 30	To explore the difference in gait kinematics and kinetics during single-task and dual-task walking between PwPD with and without MCI.	MDS-UPDRS, H&Y, LEED	PD-noMCI and PD-MCI groups had mean ages of 61.35 ± 8.11 and 67.02 ± 9.03 years, respectively; gender distribution data were not available; PD duration averaged 4.4 ± 2.6 years for PD-noMCI and 4.94 ± 2.41 years for PD-MCI; UPDRS-III scores were 22.43 ± 10.04 for PD-noMCI and 24.68 ± 8.02 for PD-MCI.	Kinematic data were collected using 3D an optoelectronic system with 6 cameras and 22 passive retro-reflective markers with a 14mm diameter. Kinetic data were measured by means of two platforms embedded in the middle of a 3m walkway.	Spatiotemporal, kinematic, and kinetic data were computed.	Multiple machine learning models—including DT, RF, GBT, SVM, KNN, LDA, and NB—were evaluated for kinematic and kinetic data. In kinematics, DT achieved the highest specificity (90.0%) with an AUROC of 0.856, while KNN had a sensitivity of	Kinematic features distinguishing PD-MCI from PD-noMCI indicate a more severe disease phenotype, where cognitive impairment is accompanied by pronounced posture and gait dysfunction. Additionally, kinetic findings suggest that certain cortical areas involved in cognitive processes may

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							80.0% and AUROC of 0.817. For kinetics, GBT recorded the highest AUROC (0.863), while RF and KNN exhibited balanced performance across accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and precision.	play a specific role in force scaling in Parkinson's disease.
Stergioulas et al., 2024	PD = 17	Using smartphone-based video analysis to assess balance and posture, PwPD, by evaluating video data captured during a Comprehensive Motor Function Test.	MDS-UPDRS-III	Male PD participants had a mean age of 72.1 ± 8.9 years, while female PD participants had a mean age of 71.4 ± 5 years; gender distribution was 70.59% male and 29.41% female; PD duration averaged 9.2 years for males	A smartphone was used as a sensor to capture and analyze movement data	Features that are computed from each angle time series (27 in total).	K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), PCA+KNN, and Supervised PCA (sPCA)+KNN	The KNN approach yielded the best results across most assessment items, with optimal K values typically set at 2 or 3. However, gait assessment results indicate potential areas for further

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				and 17.4 years for females; UPDRS-III data were not available.			were evaluated using Leave-One-Out cross-validation, with weighted F1 scores calculated for all assessment items and machine learning classifiers.	refinement and improvement.
Sundari et al., 2024	n/a [Cerebellar Ataxia (CA), Spinocerebellar Ataxia (SCA), and Parkinson's disease]	To apply MediaPipe for real-time disease recognition in videos.	n/a	n/a	Real-time video analysis was used to predict human activity, leveraging BlazePose GHUM 3D—a CNN architecture optimized for 3D pose estimation of the human body.	Stance, swing, step length, speed, hip, knee, ankle, cadence.	Logistic Regression (LR) achieved 100% accuracy for normal cases and 98.53% accuracy for affected cases.	This research proposes the video as a means to differentiate between the symptoms of these diseases.
Yin et al., 2024	PD/HC = 63/65	To use a non-contact gait	H&Y, MMSE,	Age—66.90 ± 8.43 (PD) / 67.40 ±	Gait parameters were assessed	Stride length, step height,	The LightGBM and Random	Early-stage PwPD

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		assessment system to investigate gait characteristics between PwPD and HC, with a focus on early-stage PD. To differentiate early-stage PD from HC and to predict MDS-UPDRS III.	MDS-UPDRS-III	7.17 (HC); Gender (% M/F)—52.85/57.15 (PD), 53.85/46.15 (HC); PD Duration—Range: 1–10 years; UPDRS-III Score—25.50 (17.00, 39.00) (PD)	using the ReadyGo system, utilizing a set of integrated cameras, including one RGB camera and a single depth camera, to capture and analyze 3D motion data.	step width, gait speed, stride speed, swing speed, turning time, cadence, swing phase, stance phase, double support	Forest models achieved an accuracy of 91.43%, sensitivity of 93.33%, specificity of 90.0%, and AUC of 0.99, effectively distinguishing 91.43% of early-stage PD from HC based on gait parameters. The model demonstrated strong explanatory power for MDS-UPDRS III score ($R^2 = 0.897$), with a MAE of 4.015 and a MAPE of 0.198.	demonstrated reduced stride length, decreased gait speed, slower stride and swing speeds, extended turning time, and reduced cadence compared to controls. Our model, after an integrated analysis of gait parameters, accurately identified early-stage PwPD. Moreover, the model indicated that gait parameters could predict the MDS-UPDRS III score using a ML regression approach.

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Zhou, 2024	PD = 35	To propose a novel hybrid ML detection system to detect PD using a combination of both videos of freezing of gait and numerical sensor data.	Mini-Mental, NFOG-Q, H&Y, UPDRS-II, UPDRS-III, PIGD, Dyskinesia, HADS, HADS-A, HADS-D, FES-I, mini-BESTest	Participants' ages ranged from 44 to 84 years, with a PD group gender distribution of 54.3% male and 45.7% female; PD duration and UPDRS-III data were not available.	Digital camera: videos of patients experiencing freezing of gait while turning in place in circles.	AI pose estimation techniques were employed to analyze the videos, extracting key motion attributes (velocity, acceleration, and gait parameters).	Logistic Regression, K-Neighbors, Bayesian Regression, and Random Forest were used. The hybrid model achieved an average accuracy of approximately 94% across all twelve rating scales, while the sensor model reached 91% accuracy and the video model attained 89% accuracy.	The hybrid model demonstrates high accuracy and precision while ensuring reliability by integrating two sets of clinical data to make a final decision, enhancing its robustness in assessment.
Abe et al., 2022	PD/HC = 19/9	To compare the arm swing data of PwPD during gait with the numerical values of the MDS-UPDRS	MDS-UPDRS II (2.12, 2.13), III (3.3, 3.10, 3.11): score 0 to 30, sum	N/A	DensePose, video recordings	Velocity, acceleration, curvature	Mask R-CNN framework, RF, SVM	Accuracy = 99.62% for lower limbs and head regions.

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			of values of gait (SVG)					
Aldegheri et al., 2023	PD = 55	To present a software that augments the human skeleton extrapolated by HPE software from RGB pictures with exact bone points for posture evaluation through computer vision post-processing primitives	N/A	PD = 62, male PD = 66.7	AutoPosturePD software	Axial postural abnormalities	Pearson correlation, CNN; Significance analysis	AutoPosturePD provides low-cost, portable evaluation of postural abnormalities in PD
Buongiorno et al., 2019	PD/HC = 16/14	To design and test a mobile low-cost decision support system (DSS) that can be easily used both in specialized hospitals and at home	MDS-UPDRS	PD/HC = 63.18/61.52, male PD/HC = 58.82/45.83, PD = 4, MDS-UPDRS III: PD = 34.56 (H&Y I-II); 46.62 (H&Y III-IV)	Microsoft Kinect v2 (RGB-D camera)	Gait: temporal, spatial, angular features	SVM, ANN with 5-fold cross-validation	ANN achieved best results for PD diagnosis (accuracy = 89.4%, sensitivity = 87.0%, specificity = 91.8%). Accuracy for PD severity rating was 95.0% with fewer features. Vision system supports gait assessment.

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Connie et al., 2022	PD/HC = 74/93	To extract PD-discriminative gait features from raw videos of subjects and demonstrate the potential of marker-less motion capture for PD prediction	N/A	PD/HC = 68.9/56.3, male PD/HC = 68.75/65.54, PD = 8.9, UPDRS = 34.0	Microsoft Kinect v2	Gait features	SVM, ANN, cross-validation	ANN: 89.4% accuracy for PD diagnosis. Vision system for gait assessment.
Dias et al., 2020	early PD / moderate PD = 10/17	To present a motor assessment tool in the context of the iPROGNOSIS project	H&Y, UPDRS part III 8 (items 23, 24, 25, 26 and 28), MoCA	N/A	Depth sensor system	Statistical features	Pearson correlation, linear regression; r, r ²	Tests useful for monitoring PD progression
Dranca et al., 2018	early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 8/11/11	To build a Kinect-based system that can distinguish between different PD stages	H&Y, FOG-Q	All subjects (23-81) y, All male subjects = 63.41	Kinetic sensor, smartphone	Limb angles	Decision trees, Bayesian networks, neural networks, K-nearest neighbours	Bayesian Network: 93.40% accuracy, 7 relevant features.
Eguchi et al., 2023	PD = 74	to assess the feasibility of predicting the UPDRS score from gait videos using a convolutional neural network (CNN) model	Total UPDRS part III score and 4 sub-scores of axial symptoms (27, 28, 29, 30), bradykinesia (23, 24, 25,	N/A	MS Kinect, e-Motion Capture	Gait features	LR, NB, RF, DT	RF: 82% accuracy. Low-cost gait information capture system

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			26, 31), rigidity (22), tremor (20, 21), MMSE, LEDD, H&Y					
Erfianto et al., 2023	HC/ Gait impairments / PD = 4/7/3	To detect abnormalities in walking transitions using the EMD and Hilbert spectra	N/A	PD/HC = 66/66, male PD/HC = 57/63, PD = 5.8, MDS-UPDRS III: PD = 39.06	Video recording, AlphaPose	Spatial-temporal features	Convolutional network	Accuracy = 65.66. Deep supervision enhances robustness.
Ferraris et al., 2019	PD/HC = 14/12	To present a self-managed, home-based system for the automated assessment of a selected set of PD motor symptoms	UPDRS tasks 3.8, 3.9, 3.10, 3.12 and 3.13, MMSE, H&Y	PD/HC = 68.0/66.2, male PD/HC = 68.57/43.33, PwPA / PwtPA = 5.9/4.0, MDS-UPDRS III. PwPA / PwtPA = 43.6/30.9	Optical RGB-Depth device	Posture, lower limb movements	Elastic Net, kNN, MLR, SVM; Significance, accuracy	System feasible for objective, automated assessment of PD at home
Ferraris et al., 2022	PD/HC = 16/13	To present a system for gait analysis.	MMSE, UPDRS, H&Y	PD/ HC/ young HC = 73.8/52.9/23.8	OpenPose, smartphone	Gait features	Random Forest	Accuracy = 93%. Front and side views show discriminative features.
Guayacán et al., 2022	PD/HC = 11/11	To perform a robust regional kinematic characterization, which may result in a potential digital biomarker of PD	H&Y	PD/HC = 73.6/55.0, male PD/HC = 66.67/38.89	DensePose, video recordings	Velocity, acceleration, curvature features	Mask R-CNN, RF, SVM	High accuracy achieved for lower-limbs and head regions (99.62%) and head and trunk (94.73%). Ability to recover kinematic

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								patterns in different body segments.
Guo et al., 2022	PD = 142 (+ test dataset, PD = 42)	To propose a two-stream multi-scale sparse spatial-temporal attention-aware graph convolutional network (GCN) under deep supervision for gait assessment in PwD.	MDS-UPDRS Gait score	N/A	Video recording	Gait features	Convolutional neural network	Predicts UPDRS III with MAE±SD = 6.9±5.2, R2 = 0.59.
Hong et al., 2022	PD/HC = 70/30. Within PD, PwPA (postural abnormalities) = 36; PwtPA = 34	To propose a summary index for postural abnormalities (IPA) based on Kinect depth camera and explored its clinical value	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, NMSS, CSI, HADS, PDQ-39, MMSE, BBE, PSQI	N/A	Kinect motion analysis device	Posture assessment	Kolmogorov–Smirnov, Mann–Whitney U, Spearman; Sensitivity, specificity, AUC	Significant correlations between IPA and PD severity measures
Li et al., 2016	HC/Hemiplegic/PD = 15	To present an algorithm for classification of gait disorders arising from neuro-degenerative diseases	N/A	PD = 71.44, male PD = 58, PD = 7.0	MS Kinect	Stride length, velocity, age	Neural networks, radial basis function network	Accuracy = 97.2%. MS Kinect for gait disorder recognition.

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Li et al., 2022	PD = 50	To automatically recognize FOG in PD patients through videos taken by mobile phone	MMSE, FOG-Q, UPDRS III (3.10+3.11), LEDD	PD = 71, male PD = 70.9	Azure Kinect, smartphone	Gait parameters	XGBoost algorithm	LOSO method: sensitivity = 87.5%, specificity = 79.82%.
Liu et al., 2022	PD/HC = 68/48	To assess the differences in gait characteristics between patients with PD and HCs using 2D video and explore the diagnostic value of 2D video for early-stage PD.	H&Y, MoCA	PD / HC / young HC = 73.6/55/23.7	Kinect Motion (RGB-D)	Arm and leg variables	LR, SVM, DT, NB, RF	RF: 81.8% to 84.5% accuracy. ML useful for PD classification.
Lu et al., 2021	PD = 55	To introduce an ordinal focal neural network to estimate the MDS-UPDRS scores, to leverage the ordinal nature of MDS-UPDRS scores and combat class imbalance	MDS-UPDRS III (3.10)	PD = 63.4, male PD = 41, PD = 11.3, PD 0 23.7	Video recordings of gait	Joint Collection Distances, two-scale motion features	OF-DDNet with RCE	Effective method to predict MDS-UPDRS gait scores despite noisy data.
Muñoz-Ospina et al., 2022	PD/HC = 30/30	To propose a ML technique algorithm using the variables from upper and lower limbs, to classify PwPD from HC	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS III, FOG-Q, MoCA	PD/HC (range): 40s to 70s / 20s to 50s, male PD/HC = 68.42/55.56	Kinectr Motion (RGB-D camera)	Arm and leg variables	LR, SVM, DT, NB, RF	RF model performed best across all datasets (Dataset A: 81.8%, Dataset B: 83.6%, Dataset C: 84.5%). ML

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								techniques accurately classify PwPD.
Ospina et al., 2019	PD/HC = 30/30	To assess differences in gait dynamics between PwPD and HC and to investigate the effects of aging on these differences	MDS-UPDRS III, FOG-Q, DGI, MoCA	PD = 69, male PD = 70.9, PD = 5.8	Kinetic sensor, depth camera	Joint motion data	Proposed method, Covariance, Lie relative, Joint methods	Proposed method: avg. accuracy 79.0%, best accuracy 91.1%.
Procházka et al., 2015	PD/ HC/ young HC	To present a novel method of Bayesian gait recognition	N/A	early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 68.73/70.56/72.57, male early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 62.5/100/81.81, early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 3.08/7.04/11.15	Video analysis	Knee joint kinematics	OpenPose, K-Nearest Neighbours	TPR reached 100% for some cases. Potential for elderly home rehab.
Procházka et al., 2015	P/HC = 18/18	To present a novel method of gait recognition using the image and depth sensors of MS Kinect to track the skeleton of a moving body	N/A	N/A	Video recordings, 3D skeleton	Joint distances, motion features	OF-DDNet with RCE	AUC = 0.84, F1 = 0.67. Predicts MDS-UPDRS gait scores despite noise.
Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022	Anomaly detection dataset available on Kaggle; PD = 25	Developing an automated caretaking system	N/A	N/A	Wearable sensors, depth camera	Fall detection system	Random Forest, XGBoost, CatBoost, MMET;	Eye-Tact accurately predicts falls in PD patients

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		to enable remote monitoring					Precision, recall, F1, accuracy	
Tupa et al., 2015	PD / HC / young HC = 18/18/15	To detect selected gait attributes by Microsoft (MS) Kinect image and depth sensors	H&Y	(range) HC/Hemiplegic/PD = 46-75 / 50-83 / 60-85	MS Kinect (image and depth)	Gait features	Skeletal tracking, Bayesian classification	Accuracy = 91.7% at optimal threshold. MS Kinect for gait disorders.
Urcuqui et al., 2018	PD/HC = 30/30	To propose and evaluate a ML classifier for the analysis of PwPD through their gait information	N/A	PD/HC = 74.9/73.5, male PD/HC = 81.25/71.43	MS Kinect, e-Motion Capture System	18 features	LR, NB, RF, DT	RF model identified as best classifier, offering low-cost gait information capture.
Wei et al., 2020	PD/HC = 20/21	To propose an automated balance evaluation system for home and clinical use	N/A	N/A	Wii balance board, Kinect	Centre of mass/pressure	Convolutional Neural Network; Sensitivity, specificity	Balance evaluation model correlates with traditional assessments of balance in PD patients

General discussion

Overall, the aim of this systematic review was to evaluate the efficacy of digital assessments in accurately capturing balance and posture. While several studies have undertaken data collection in clinical settings, the objective of AI-PROGNOSIS project is to assess these motor symptoms using smartphone camera-enabled body tracking and active motor tests. Therefore, our focus was on methodological designs that are aligned with this objective.

Studies identified in the initial literature search have employed a variety of sensors to gather data, including cameras (RGB, depth), wearable sensors (accelerometers, gyroscopes), and specialized equipment such as Kinect (Microsoft) (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022). Common assessment tasks include gait analysis (looking at factors such as walking speed and stride length), posture assessment, fall detection, and monitoring PD progression (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020).

Various ML/Deep Learning (DL) models have been used to analyse sensor data. Some common models include Random Forest, XGBoost, Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Ferraris et al., 2019; Dranca et al., 2018). Feature selection techniques are often used to identify the most relevant data for training the models (Ferraris et al., 2019; Dranca et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022). To evaluate how well the models perform, researchers use metrics, such as accuracy, AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and recall (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020). Many studies report promising results, with accuracy exceeding 80% (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Ferraris et al., 2019; Procházka et al., 2015).

Overall, this review suggests that ML-based systems using various sensors can effectively assess movement disorders such as PD (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022). These systems have the potential to provide objective and quantitative measures for gait analysis, posture assessment, and fall risk prediction (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022). The use of inexpensive sensors such as cameras and smartphones makes these technologies potentially suitable for home-based monitoring (Dias et al., 2020; Erfianto et al., 2023). However, there are some limitations to this area of research. Some studies acknowledge limitations such as small sample sizes or the need for further validation in larger populations (Li et al., 2022; Erfianto et al., 2023). Additionally, generalizability to different patient populations or disease severities needs to be investigated.

In conclusion, ML-based systems using diverse sensors offer significant promise in objectively assessing movement disorders. Despite certain limitations, these technologies hold significant potential to offer valuable assistance in diagnosing, assessing, monitoring, and managing PD.

Overall, the updated literature search studies showed that video-based analysis of posture and balance in PwPD holds potential to: i) accurately distinguish PwPD from HC and other clinical conditions; ii) predict clinical scores (i.e., MDS-UPDRS-III); iii) effectively classify motor symptoms (e.g., gait impairments and postural instability); iv) enable home-based assessment and symptom monitoring, and v) support early detection of PD.

Furthermore, studies using marker-based sensors (Kour et al., 2024; Russo et al., 2024) provide gold-standard motion capture data, supporting the development of more precise markerless systems while establishing reliable benchmarks for accuracy evaluation. Moreover, these findings highlight the potential for hybrid approaches by combining the precision of marker-based systems with the accessibility of video-based assessments. Lastly,

several studies excluded from the primary analysis, due to limited data availability or their exclusive focus on PD detection in non-PD populations, are also discussed in this section to further expand our understanding of video-based assessments for PD detection and monitoring.

Studies with limited data. Diraco et al. (2024) used a single RGB-D camera for gait analysis across a diverse cohort (elderly people with Migraine, Huntington's, Fibromyalgia, PD, and HC). The Long Short-Term Memory model achieved 98% accuracy in binary classification between PD and HC, focusing on body symmetry and forward/backward imbalance features. Kaur et al. (2024) investigated both voice analysis and gait patterns for PD detection using XGBoost, achieving 73.8% accuracy. Sindhu et al. (2024) presented a comprehensive system integrating gait analysis, yoga therapy, and fall detection using MediaPipe and OpenPose for video analysis.

Studies focused on PD detection. Gunaratne et al. (2024) automated the Timed Up and Go (TUG) test using a vision-attentive model with BlazePose, achieving 90.02% accuracy with 89.0% precision in detecting PD. Akshaya & Joy et.al (2025) developed "ParkinSense," a multimodal methodology combining spiral drawings, gait analysis, and MRI for PD detection. The proposed model held a 93% accuracy, which supports the integration of multiple assessment modalities to improve diagnostic performance. Islam et al. (2024) aimed to evaluate Parkinsonism severity in patients with a diagnosis of dementia, employing MediaPipe for feature extraction, and analyzing joint angles (hip-knee, shoulder-elbow, knee, elbow-wrist) to. The best performance was obtained with a KNN model, achieving 92% precision and recall. Alazeb et al. (2024) presented an AI approach for physical rehabilitation that incorporated RGB, depth, and inertial sensors using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The Long Short-term Memory-recurrent Neural Networks (LSTM-RNN) classifier achieved 97% accuracy.

Overall, these studies highlight recent advancements in video-based assessment technologies for PwPD, with most studies demonstrating relatively high accuracy and clinical relevance. The integration of ML/DL models with accessible recording devices (i.e., smartphones and standard cameras) offers promising avenues for precise and objective assessments that could add value to established clinical outcome measures, enable remote monitoring, and improve early detection of PD.

2.3.9 Digital assessments of cognitive decline

Study selection

Our selection strategy for cognitive decline focused on selecting relevant publications within the Rayyan digital biomarkers literature search. Based on the articles identified using the specified keywords, our focus for digitally assessing cognitive decline centered on terms such as "cognition" and "cognitive". Although we searched for additional keywords such as "dementia", "dysexecutive", "amnesia", or "memory", we found no relevant results within the scope of the study. Therefore, we focused solely on cognition and cognitive aspects. This narrowed the scope to articles addressing cognitive decline in PD patients. Studies involving participants with mental disorders were excluded, along with reviews, posters, letters, and expert opinion publications. Additionally, technological interventions not targeting or useful for PD cognitive assessment, those unrelated to PD, or those examining platforms/services other than mobile apps were also excluded. The titles and abstracts of all records were examined, and full-text screening was performed for potentially relevant studies. Duplicates were removed during the screening process.

Moreover, several articles were excluded after full-text screening due to various reasons, including complexity of assessment setups not aligning with the AI-PROGNOSIS project's

scope or methods, and the lack of digital assessment of cognition. These exclusions were vital to maintaining the relevance and consistency of the studies included within the scope of the present review. Some studies required further verification regarding the suitability of assessment methodologies, such as the use of a microphone and laptop. In addition, exclusions occurred when articles primarily focused on motor symptoms rather than cognitive assessment. The criteria for study inclusion are provided in **Table 26**. Inclusion criteria were the following:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,
AND
Methods and data for cognitive decline assessment were provided,
AND
Use of data from wearable sensors and/or smart devices that enable monitoring of PD symptoms.

Table 26 Selection criteria for digital assessments of cognitive decline

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Keywords	cognitive, cognition
Outcomes	Clinical measures such as H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, PDQ-39, GDS, REM SBDQ, ESC, SOPDAS, TMT-A, TMT-B, WAIS, RCFT, WMS, MASQ, CFQ, PD-CFRS, ESS, IFS, RBDSQ, DAT-SBR, BJLOT, SFT, SDMT, HVLIT, LNS, MSE-ADL, QUIP A-E, STAI, CDR-SB, K-MoCA, K-MMSE, K-IADL, Berg Balance Scale, TUG, Sit to Stand, 6MWT, Falls
Apparatus	wearable sensors, smartphones, smartwatches, computers, tablets, pens, wrist sensors (Microsoft Band), sensor insoles (Moticon), smart pillboxes (SimpleMed+), noise-canceling headband microphones (Genius HS-04SU) connected to laptops.

Initial Literature search

In the Rayyan bibliographic searches, the keywords cognition and cognitive were considered. This refined the pool to 61 articles, which were subsequently screened for their title, abstract, and full text. During the title screening phase, 34 articles were deemed relevant and included for further examination, while 23 articles were excluded. Moving to abstract screening, 26 articles met the criteria for inclusion, with only 3 articles being excluded. Subsequently, during full text screening, 13 articles were found to meet all criteria and were included in the final analysis, while 12 articles were excluded. Finally, out of the initial pool of 61 articles, only 13 met the inclusion criteria. These selected articles showcased a diverse range of digital assessment tools and methodologies, including mobile applications, AI-driven approaches, wearable electronic devices, and digital biomarkers.

Updated Literature Search

In the Rayyan bibliographic searches, the keywords cognition, cognitive, memory, amnesia, dementia were considered. This refined the pool to 82 articles from the first literature text and 357 from the second literature search, which were subsequently screened for their title, abstract, and full text. During the title and abstract screening phase, 6 (10) articles were deemed relevant and included for further examination, while 76 (347) articles were excluded from the first (second) literature search. Subsequently, during full text screening, 1(3) articles were found to meet all criteria and were included in the final analysis, while 5(7) articles were excluded from the first (second) literature search. Finally, out of the initial pool of 439 articles, only 4 met the inclusion criteria. These selected articles showcased a diverse range of digital assessment tools and methodologies, including mobile applications, wearable electronic devices (e.g. for eye-tracking), AI-driven approaches, and digital biomarkers.

	First report (D2.3)	Updated report (D2.4)	Total
Records screened	61	439	500
Articles included in literature table	13	4	17

Study characteristics for the initial literature search

Participants recruited across the included studies had a mean age ranging from 50 to 85 years. However, three studies did not report age directly but stratified participants into 10-30 years range bands (Lo et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2022; Templeton et al., 2022). Additionally, some studies lacked reporting crucial clinico-demographic information. For instance, one study omitted reporting sex information (Tsiouris et al., 2017), seven studies did not include data on disease duration (Holmes et al., 2022; Templeton et al., 2022; Weizenbaum et al., 2021, Tsiouris et al., 2017; Ryu et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; and Prince et al., 2019), and five studies failed to provide information regarding the reported motor severity score (MDS-UPDRS-III) (Tsiouris et al., 2017; Templeton et al., 2022; Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Prince et al., 2019).

Several studies included control groups (Adams et al., 2023; Garcia et al., 2022; Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Ryu et al., 2022; Templeton et al., 2022; Prince et al., 2019). The nature of the control groups varies across studies (e.g., healthy controls, non-movement disorder patients). The duration of the studies varied considerably, for instance, some studies were cross-sectional, meaning data was collected at a single point in time (Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Ryu et al., 2022; Garcia et al., 2022; Prince et al., 2019; Templeton et al., 2022; Rosenblum et al., 2021). Others involved longitudinal monitoring, with data collection occurring over weeks or months (Adams et al., 2023; Motlese et al., 2020; Alberts et al., 2021; Lo et al., 2019). The frequency of monitoring also differed (e.g., daily, weekly, monthly). Details on specific monitoring schedules are not provided for all studies.

Study characteristics for the updated literature search

Participants recruited across the included studies had a mean age ranging from 63 to 66 years. Study durations are not reported in 3 studies, while the (Khalil et al, 2024) study lasted for 5 years. Three studies included control groups (Khalil et al, 2024, Koch et al, 2024, Huang et al, 2025), while the fourth one (Tang et al, 2024) included only PD patients. The duration of (Khalil et al, 2024) study was 5 years (2015-2020), while the duration of the others was reported.

Digital assessments of cognitive decline

Several studies identified in the initial literature research (Adams et al., 2023; Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Motlese et al., 2020; Rosenblum et al., 2021) followed patients for

five to ten years. Three other studies (Prince et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2022; Tsiouris et al., 2017) examined individuals with a weakened sense of smell (idiopathic hyposmia) to find very early signs (prodromal symptoms) of PD. Two of the studies focused on individuals with REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD), a condition that is occasionally linked to PD (Prince et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2022).

More specifically, Adams et al. (2023) compared PD patients and controls using conventional cognitive measures such as the Symbol Digit Modalities Test (SDMT) and the Trail Making Test-A (TMT-A). They discovered that PD patients performed significantly worse on these tasks. Exploring innovative techniques, a novel strategy was investigated by Holmes et al. (2022) who used novel approaches for cognitive assessment by investigating keyboard patterns. Their study revealed moderate correlations between specific cognitive categories and keyboard usage.

Overall, smartphone technology emerges as a promising platform for cognitive assessment in PD. Weizenbaum et al. (2021) investigated the viability and efficacy of cognitive tests administered via smartphones and discovered associations with conventional neuropsychological assessments. This makes smartphones useful instruments for evaluating cognitive performance in people with PD. Simultaneously, tablet-based tests offer intriguing opportunities for cognitive assessment. Prince used tablet technology for neurocognitive evaluation and multi-source ensemble learning to improve classification accuracy in PD. Similarly, Templeton showed the promise of digital biomarkers and tablet sensors in cognitive assessment by quantifying neurocognitive performance using ensemble learning approaches and tablet-based exams. Technology-driven interventions aim to improve cognitive performance in people with PD beyond evaluation approaches. To promote cognitive health, Ryu concentrated on creating entertaining tablet-based workouts specifically designed for those with PD. Lauritis investigated deep learning and AI algorithms for self-administered cognitive evaluations on smartphones concurrently, suggesting a move toward customized and adaptive assessment techniques.

Smartphone-based remote monitoring presents a fundamental shift in disease management overall. There are links between smartphone-based measures and cognitive function, according to research by Motlese (2020) et al. and Tsiouris (2017) on smartphone applications for remote monitoring of PD patients. This takes advantage of the widespread use of smartphones in daily life to create opportunities for long-term monitoring and early cognitive decline detection.

In the updated literature search, Huang et al. (2025) proposes two novel digital biomarkers for recognizing early cognitive decline in PD-MCI through an independently designed maze decision-making digital assessment paradigm (Khalil et al, 2024) proposes and evaluates a simplified wearable-sensor-based mobility test for PD diagnosis. Improved accuracy is shown using a dual task paradigm (cognitive plus mobility task). In (Koch et al, 2024), the ability of oculomotor measures captured from tablet-based eye-tracking to assess various cognitive abilities and disease severity in PD patients. Finally, (Tang et al, 2024) use gait and eye-tracking devices to assess motor and cognitive dysfunction in patients with PD, to evaluate the effect of the controversial rTMS treatment (i.e. high-frequency repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation).

Table 27 provides an overview of study characteristics, methodologies, and results in PD cognitive decline digital assessment.

Table 27 Studies about digital assessments of cognitive decline

Study characteristics				Study Populati on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
Huang et al, 2025	PD/PD-NC(Normal cognitive) /PD-MCI	Exploring cognitive deficits in decision-making in the PD-MCI population by using a maze decision-making digital assessment paradigm, and novel digital biomarkers for early cognitive decline.	Identification of digital decision-making biomarkers for differentiating between the PD-MCI, PD-NC (normal cognitive) and HC groups.	65/53M 54F/ HC:4.00 (2.25) PD-NC:15.00 (4.00) PD-MCI:18.50 (11.00)	PD maze decision-making digital evaluation paradigm using a computer, a touchable monitor and and a HCI front-end with Unity3D	Global decision-making (Total decision time (TDT), Decision process time (DPT)), decision-making planning process digital biomarkers (2 parameters) and decision-making performance process digital biomarkers (7 parameters)	Binary logistic regression model	AUC	HC vs PD-MCI groups: Total decision making time (TDT)=0.783, Decision-making process time (DPT)=0.798, Performance average speed (PAS)=0.818, Performance speed variability (PSV)=0.746, Performance average acceleration (PAA)=0.933. Combination of the 5 digital biomarkers= 0.949.	Performance average acceleration (PAA) and Total decision-making time (TDT), were retained in the PD-MCI group vs PD-NC group, and in the PD-MCI group versus the HC group, and their combined screening efficacy AUC was 0.909 and 0.942 respectively.
Khalil et al, 2024	PD/HC	Simplify sensor-based mobility	Cumulative Illness Rating Scale-	65 / 181M 131F/	Portable Biosensor Device	Accelerometry data	Ensemble model, Super	Overall accuracy, area under the	Overall accuracy of 92.6%	Effectiveness of analyzing wearable sensor data to distinguish PD

Study characteristics				Study Populati on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
		testing in diagnosing PD	Geriatrics (CIRS-G), Older Americans Resource and Services (OARS) Disability Subscale, activities of daily living (ADLs) and instrumental activities of daily living (IADLs), MoCA, UPDRS (Total and Motor (Part III))	22.2 ± 11.8			learner creating a linear combination of 327 base models: 11 GLM models, 100 DRF models, 100 GBM models, 16 XGBoost models, and 100 neural network models	receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC), sensitivity, and F1 score	(confidence interval [CI] 88.8%, 94.9%) in distinguishing all-PD from HC and 89.4% (CI 84.3%, 92.3%) in distinguishing mild PD from HC	participants from controls using the proposed machine learning pipeline for five mobility tasks. The dual task paradigm (cognitive plus mobility task) achieves superior diagnostic performance in identifying participants in the early stages of PD.
Koch et al, 2024	PD/HC	Use of oculomotor measures from tablet-based eye-tracking to inform on various cognitive abilities and disease	UPDRS total score, UPDRS part III score, Cognitive: MoCA27, TMT A/B28, HVLT29 (immediate recall only), COWAT-CFL	64 /43M 22F/ 28.98 ± 13.43	Eye-tracking tests were performed using a 12.9-inch iPad Pro tablet with the ETNA™ gaze-tracking software.	A large set of eye-tracking parameters , from where a subset with largest correlation with outcomes is selected.	Partial least squares (PLS) regression	Mean absolute error (MAE), non-adjusted and adjusted coefficient of determination (R2 and Adj. R2) as well as the F-statistic and associated p-value for each outcome.	Mean absolute error for the UPDRS and UPDRS-III PLS regressions are 9.66 and 4.37 respective	Several oculomotor parameters strongly correlate with measures of disease stage, severity such as the UPDRS-III score and various measures of cognitive function in individuals with PD. Using a novel mobile tablet-based eye tracking system has the potential

Study characteristics				Study Population on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
		severity in PD patients								to optimize clinical care of PD patients and provide an affordable and scalable solution to help characterize disease status, monitor disease progression, and track changes in cognitive ability.
Tang et al, 2024	PD	Studying the effect of high-frequency Transcranial magnetic stimulation on gait and cognitive functions in PD patients using data from wearable devices and eye-tracking	Tinetti Balance Scale, Tinetti Gait Scale, Berg Balance Scale score, MMSE, total MoCA score, MoCA sub-items	66/93M 66F / N/A	Eyeknow wearable sensor and a wearable motion and gait quantification assessment system (GYENNO MATRIX).	Mini-Mental State Examination (MMS), Berg Balance Scale (BBS), MoCA, MoCA sub-items (Visual-spatial and executive, Naming, Attention, Language, Abstraction, Delayed recall, Orientation)	N/A	N/A	No model was used, but statistical analysis (t-test and p-values) before and after treatment support the main finding.	After rTMS treatment, the Tinetti Balance Scale, Tinetti Gait Scale, and Berg Balance Scale scores increased; after rTMS treatment, the MMSE and MoCA scores increased; and the MoCA sub-items improved in visual-spatial and executive function, language, abstraction, delayed recall, and orientation.

Study characteristics				Study Populati on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
Adams et al., 2023	PD/HC	Early PD features	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, etc.	63.3 / 56M 36F / 24.1 (PD), 2.7 (HC)	Wearables, smartphone	Gait, tremor, cognitive tests	Stat Anal	Correlations, AUC	P < 0.05 for TMT-A, fewer correct responses in PD vs HC; MoCA weakly correlated with cognitive and motor tasks	Differences in arm swing, tremor time, and finger tapping were observed between early PD and controls, correlating variably with traditional assessments. Various devices highlighted slower finger tapping, increased tremor, worse cognition, and speech changes in PD.
Alberts et al., 2021	PD	Smartphone app feasibility	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, TUG, etc.	68.4 / 65.2M / 23.65	Smartphone sensors	Finger tapping, processing speed tests	Stats	Descriptive stats, t-tests, correlations	Smartphone tech characterizes PD symptoms, e.g., bradykinesia, akinesia, nonmotor function	Smartphone assessments effectively characterized bradykinesia, akinesia, and nonmotor function in PD.
Garcia et al., 2022	PD/HC	Action-concept markers	H&Y, UPDRS-III, IFS, etc.	62.25 / 62.5M 62.5F / 31	Headband mic, laptop	Retelling tasks	SVM, etc.	Accuracy, Sens, Spec, F-score	Acc/sens/spec/ F-score: PD/HC = 72.5/80.0/65.0/ 72.2; PD-nMCI/PD-MCI =	Discrimination between patients and controls was effective using action-concept markers, particularly with action-laden text scores.

Study characteristics				Study Population Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
									69.5/75.0/65.0/67.6;	
Holmes et al., 2022	NC/CI	Cognitive performance	ADLQ, DRS-2, FAB, MoCA, etc.	71.1 / 51M 60F / N/A	Computer, smartphone	Keystroke patterns	ML, DL	Correlations, R2, MSE	Moderate correlations with cognitive subdomains; typing patterns reflect neurodegeneration in MCI and Alzheimer's	Utilizing a subdomain framework improved ML model performance, reflecting neurodegeneration in MCI and Alzheimer's.
Lauraitis et al., 2020	ND/HC	Digitization of SAGE	SAGE methodology	42.6 / 86M 50F / N/A	Smartphone	Tremor, cognitive, speech	ML, DL	TPR, FPR, Precision, Recall, AUC, MCC	Hybrid model achieved 87.5% accuracy; best results with fusion of 13 classifiers and BiLSTM for speech analysis	Best results were achieved with a fusion of 13 classifiers for finger tapping and SAGE features (96.12% accuracy) and BiLSTM for speech analysis (94.29% accuracy).
Lo et al., 2019	PD-MCI/PD-nMCI	Predict future PD outcomes with smartphone	Falls, Freezing, Postural instability, Cognitive impairment, Difficulty doing hobbies,	70.0 / 64M 54F / 27.6 (PD-MCI), 24.3 (PD-nMCI)	Smartphone (Accelerometer, microphone, screen)	998 features	RF	AUC	Falls: > 0.90, Freezing: > 0.90, Postural instability: > 0.90, Cognitive impairment: > 0.90, Difficulty doing hobbies: > 0.90, Need	The ability to predict key future clinical outcomes using a simple smartphone test

Study characteristics				Study Population Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
			Need for help at home						for help at home: > 0.90	
Motlese et al., 2020	PD	Smartphone monitoring	H&Y, UPDRS, etc.	66.5 / 67M / 22	Smartphone	Gait, tapping, tremor, cognitive tests	Stats	Descriptive stats, Wilcoxon, Chi-square	Adherence related to therapy modifications, motor fluctuations; NMSQ symptoms related to adherence	Gait, tapping, tremor, and cognitive outcomes correlated with disease duration, UPDRS-III, and H&Y.
Prince et al., 2019	PD/HC = 62.6	Method for handling missing data using ensemble	Memory task	62.6 / N/A / N/A	Smartphone	Memory	LR, RF, Ensemble, CNN	Accuracy, F1	Developed method for handling missing data in memory task	Multi-source ensemble learning improved PD classification accuracy compared to traditional techniques.
Rosenblum et al., 2021	PD	Smartphone MCI detection	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, etc.	63.6 / 64.7M / 26.2	Smartphone	Motor tasks, self-report scales	Descriptive	p-values	No differences between high and low MoCA scores positive usability outcomes	Usability outcomes were positive, with users able to navigate the app easily.
Ryu et al., 2022	PD/AMP	Digitized cognitive tests	UPDRS, H&Y	72.7 / 72.7M / 20F / 23.1	Tablet	Drawing and memory tasks	Stats	Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, correlations	PwPD: lower drawing scores, higher pen speed stochasticity; voice changes	Voice characteristics differed stochastically between PwPD and NT, suggesting potential utility in cognitive tests.

Study characteristics				Study Populati on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
									in PwPD: higher SNR	
Templeton et al., 2022	PD/HC	ML classification	PDQ-39, Berg Scale, etc.	50-85 / 48M 52F / N/A	Tablet sensors	14 neurocognitive tests, 208 biomarkers	Decision tree	Accuracy, precision, recall	Acc: PD vs HC = 92.6%; early PD vs advanced PD = 73.7%; higher than gold standard tools	Early-stage PD showed lower sensor-based scores, while advanced-stage individuals had elevated perceptions of executive and behavioural functions.
Tsiouris et al., 2017	PD	PD_Manager framework	MDS-UPDRS	N/A	Wrist sensor, smartphone	Gait, tremor, cognition	N/A	Accuracy	Gait impairment, tremor, dyskinesia detection accurately estimated	Gait, fog, tremor, dyskinesia, and bradykinesia were assessed, with no focus on cognitive assessment.
Weizenbaum et al., 2021	PD	Smartphone cognitive test	H&Y, UPDRS, MoCA, etc.	63.2 / 51.9M / 27	Smartphone	Mobile games of memory and executive function	Stats	Descriptive stats, Pearson correlations	Age negatively associated with memory task; UPDRS total score negatively associated with Trails-B task	Smartphone tests predicted spatial span performance but not Trails-B task accuracy, potentially due to limited variability.

General discussion

In general, this systematic review aimed to assess the effectiveness of digital assessments in capturing cognitive deficits. In particular, the aim of AI-PROGNOSIS project is to assess the cognitive function via passive interactions between users and smartphones, alongside active cognitive tests. From this perspective, our attention was directed towards methodological approaches that align with this objective.

Among the selected studies, there were 6 out of 13 studies that utilized ML or DL approaches. Kinematic data from wearable devices played a significant role in several studies, encompassing complementary measurements related to gait, tapping, tremor, cognitive function, drawing tasks, and speech segments. These measurements were captured using sensors integrated into smartphones, smartwatches, tablets, or wristbands. Specifically, some studies (Lauraitis et al., 2020; Tsiouris et al., 2017; Templeton et al., 2022; Prince et al., 2019; and Lo et al., 2019) incorporated kinematic data in their analyses. Among the selected studies, various ML models were employed, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naive Bayes Classifiers (NB), and Decision Trees. Notably, the studies by Holmes et al. (2022) and Lauraitis et al. (2020) employed ML/DL approaches.

The remaining seven studies in the analysis explored various aspects of PD using different methodologies. Adams et al. (2023), focused on measuring features of early PD without utilizing ML or Random Forests, but extensively analysing kinematic data from wearable sensors. Motlese et al. (2020), assessed the feasibility of smartphone remote monitoring for PD, relying on statistical analyses for data evaluation. Rosenblum et al. (2021), developed a smartphone app for detecting mild cognitive impairment (MCI) in PD patients, primarily employing descriptive statistics for analysis. Weizenbaum et al. (2021), investigated smartphone cognitive assessment feasibility without ML/DL approaches, utilizing statistical modelling and correlation analyses. Garcia et al. (2022), captured action-concept markers in speech to assess PD patients' cognitive function, employing ML classifiers alongside statistical analyses. Alberts et al. (2021), characterized PD symptoms using a smartphone app, employing statistical analyses for evaluation. Ryu et al. (2022), digitized traditional cognitive tests for PD patients, employing data-driven stochastic analyses and non-parametric statistical tests for data analysis.

In conclusion, this review underlines the diverse methodologies employed in digital cognitive assessment, showcasing the potential of ML alongside alternative statistical approaches in detecting cognitive deficits in diseases such as Parkinson's.

2.3.10 Summary, unmet needs, and research opportunities

Within the scope of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, we focused on PD progression and response to medication with regards to clinical, demographic, lifestyle and genetic factors. We also reviewed the potential role of AI driven approaches and digital sensors in determining the progression of symptoms in PD as well as the response to dopaminergic medication. The results of the updated review alongside the derived unmet needs and arisen research opportunities are outlined in **Table 28**.

Ongoing population research has established a set of demographic and lifestyle factors that influence PD progression. There are also clearly defined PD clinical subtypes characterised by distinct clinical features that progress in temporally distinct patterns across motor, cognitive and psychiatric domains. Genetic studies delving into PD progression are attempting to find genetic markers regarding levodopa response and disease progression in terms of clinical, neuroimaging and fluid biomarkers. The review identified numerous SNPs associated with a faster decline, and others that may be protective. AI-driven approaches have proven useful in predicting PD progression and the majority of research studies target predictions of

progression outcomes at a single future time point rather than examining multiple future intervals.

Digital solutions for capturing PD symptoms in the home setting such as rest tremor, bradykinesia and rigidity, balance and cognitive decline is a fast-growing field that has demonstrated its potential role in monitoring PD progression and response to treatment.

Table 28 Unmet needs and research opportunities in PD progression and response to dopaminergic medication

Unmet needs	Research opportunities
Prediction of clinical progression and medication response	
<p>PD is a complex disease and predicting the disease course at disease onset is challenging since PD subtyping is clinical and depends on the development of symptoms along the disease course.</p>	<p>ML/DL approaches hold the future of transforming our understanding of the complexities of PD as numerous amounts of data can be fed into the models to delineate dynamic PD subtypes</p>
<p>The exponential increase PD incidence and lack of studies predicting response to medication is producing an overburden of consultations that most healthcare systems cannot. There is thus an unmet need for increasing the efficiency of patient care</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project will use machine and deep learning approaches to predict PD progression and response to dopaminergic treatment</p>
<p>The field of genetic research in PD is growing but an in depth understanding of the how identified gene mutations and SNPs influence PD progression and particularly response to levodopa is lacking.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project includes genetic studies for subjects that will be followed clinically and through DAT imaging</p>
AI-driven approaches	
<p>Replication of existing ML models across cohorts remains limited.</p>	<p>In the AI prognosis project, the designed ML/DL models will be replicated in open-source cohorts as well as original data derived from three clinical trials</p>
<p>Currently, most of the ML models use cross-sectional data and assume each PD subtype follows a fixed progression trajectory, without considering positive or negative medication effects.</p>	<p>In the AI prognosis project, the designed AI models will use longitudinal data and consider medication changes</p>
<p>There is a need for more ML studies that target continuous future time frames and particularly for the translation of these models into clinical practice.</p>	<p>In the AI prognosis AI-PMP clinical trial, the ML models will be used to predict when a patient needs a clinical visit with their neurologist to improve efficiency.</p>
Digital assessment of tremor, dyskinesia, bradykinesia, rigidity, balance and cognitive decline	
<p>There is a need for objective and continuous monitorization of PD motor and non-motor symptoms that can facilitate and personalize patient care.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project plans to design and develop passive capturing solutions for remote objective and continuous monitoring of PD patients in the home setting, using non-obtrusive hardware, such as IMU data from consumer smartwatches.</p>
<p>The performance of PD patients changes dramatically in the clinic so real-life assessment</p>	

in the home environment is important for PD monitoring	
Efficient rest tremor detection and assessment is possible based on data from a single accelerometer. However, dyskinesia is technically harder to capture.	The mAI-Care app designed by the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium through a collaborative effort of movement disorder specialists, engineers and patient panels will be designed to passively capture tremor, dyskinesia, bradykinesia, rigidity, balance and cognitive decline through a smartwatch.
Studies on digital tools for the assessment of bradykinesia and rigidity in the home setting are sparse.	
The interpretation of information from wearables and body sensors in daily clinical practice is still limited and guidelines on their scope and how to use them are lacking (Fabbri et al., 2023).	In the AI-PMP clinical study, patients will be assessed by bodily sensors as well as routine clinical practice to start establishing bridges from investigative efforts to clinical practice and thus provide guidelines for future use.
Studies investigating the effect of treatment modifications based on wearable sensors versus or complimentary to clinician-based decision are lacking. The threshold to medication response and what this really means is lacking and continuous variables such as those provided by digital assessments may use the patient as his/her own control and thus establish a personalized threshold response.	

3 Certified technologies for PD management

This section presents the currently approved devices for monitoring PD progression and medication response (**Table 29**). The devices listed below are based on recent published reports from members of the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium (Fabbri et al., 2023) as well as more recent technologies found through an updated search. Further, to inform the study procedures on usability and acceptability, AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts have shared their patients’ experience using these devices, where applicable. Two new technologies have been approved in the past months and added to the 9 devices previously included in D2.3.

Table 29 FDA Approved and CE-marked (as medical device) technologies for PD management. FDA: U.S. Food and Drug Administration.

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
NeuroRPM (NeuroRPM Inc.)	AI-powered monitoring with connection to Apple Watch. Captures real-time detection and visualization of bradykinesia, tremor, and dyskinesia. Presents data on iPhone. Also enables	FDA approved CE-marked	<p>Positive: Allows patients to view and track their data. User-friendly in the sense that it is connected to one’s (potentially familiar) Apple Watch and does not require learning to use a new technology</p> <p>Negative: requires iOS devices. Only available in USA</p>	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
	medication tracking.			
NUSHU Smart Shoes (Zurich - Magnes AG)	Shoes with built-in sensors that provide real-time vibrotactile feedback to analyse gait. Allow clinicians to monitor gait.	FDA approved CE-marked class IIa	Positive: guides PD patients and warns them of predicted events such as falls. Real-time feedback as well as longitudinal monitoring. User-friendly Negative: requires constant use of shoes (e.g. indoors)	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
PDMonitor (PD Neurotechnologies)	Bradykinesia, gait impairment and medicine compliance monitoring via 5 wearable IMU sensors in different body parts	CE marked, NICE recommendation	Positive: User friendly, phone app in sync with sensors where good and bad days are recorded Negative: Proprietary device; Number of sensors (5)	In use at KCL for last 4N years. Good support to detect bradykinesia, dyskinesias, gait impairment and treatment compliance. Good overall impression of device acceptance and usefulness.
PKG (PKG Health)	Tremor, bradykinesia, immobility, sleep, dyskinesia and medicine compliance monitoring through a wrist-worn sensor	CE marked and Nice recommended for PD patient monitoring, FDA cleared	Positive: User friendly as it is wearable sensor worn as watch for 6-10 days at home. Negative: Proprietary device	In use at KCL for the last 9 years. Clinically useful prior to initiation of treatment, adjusting treatment, and to monitor patients remotely and supervise any motor and non-motor fluctuations.
STAT-ON (Sense4Care)	Waist-worn device (Holter) which monitors tremor, ON, OFF, dyskinesia and freezing of gait	Class 2a medical device. Only for motor fluctuation. Only certified for EU countries	Positive: User-friendly homebased monitoring Negative: Proprietary device; transfer data from internal device memory to server may burden patients	In use in Spain in many centres and patient associations. Provides detailed information on fluctuations. Lower sensitivity for limb dyskinesias and tremor than for axial symptoms.
Kinesia 360 (Great Lakes NeuroTechnologies)	Wrist-worn sensor monitoring tremor, bradykinesia, dyskinesia and	Clinically validated for PD motor symptoms	Positive: Low-burden continuous remote monitoring Negative: Proprietary device	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
	medicine compliance			
DynaPort (Mcroberts)	Waist-worn sensor for motor symptom monitoring such as gait	Clinically validated, CE marked Class 1 medical device, FDA approved	Positive: Usefulness for detecting any issue with their gait. Negative: Requires clinical supervision; hospital assessment only.	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
FeetMe Monitor Insoles (FeetMe)	Insole with pressure and motion sensor used for gait analysis by a spatio-temporal gait parameters algorithm	Clinically validated	Positive: Usefulness for detecting any issue with their gait. Negative: Requires clinical supervision; hospital assessment only.	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
Opal and Mobility Lab (APDM Wearable technologies)	Wearable movement sensors (in several body parts) capturing gait and balance analysis, fall risk calculation	Produced by company listed here and approved in USA	Positive: Can be used at home and is user friendly Negative: Proprietary device; number of sensors	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
Strive PD (Rune Labs) powered by Apple Movement Disorders API ¹	Free iOS disease management application passively collects tremor and dyskinesia data via Apple's movement disorder API – requires a compatible Apple Watch.	FDA cleared and validated for symptom tracking	Positive: User friendly, phone app in sync with an off-the-self smartwatch (Apple Watch) Negative: Requires a specific smartwatch (Apple watch)	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
Parky (h2o therapeutics) powered by Apple Movement Disorders API	Similar to Strive PD - Free iOS disease management application passively collects tremor	FDA cleared and validated for symptom tracking	Positive: User friendly, phone app in sync with an off-the-self smartwatch (Apple Watch) Negative: Requires a specific smartwatch (Apple watch)	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium

¹ Apple Movement Disorders API - <https://developer.apple.com/documentation/coremotion/cmmovementdisordermanager>

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
	and dyskinesia data via Apple's movement disorder API – requires a compatible Apple Watch.			

4 Identified datasets of interest

In this section, we present an epitomised description of the twenty-four third-party and consortium partner retrospective datasets that have been considered of interest by the consortium of partners for the development of the project. In this updated version, we have also included the current status of the datasets of interest obtained throughout the period from late 2023 to early 2025. In **Table 30** we present the name of the data set, a brief description of its contents, what AI-PROGNOSIS model it contributes to and the current access status.

Table 30 Multi-source datasets from consortium partners and third-parties for the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
PPMI	Observational study collecting participant reported information from people with and without PD. Longitudinal measurements for more than 1700 individuals from multiple cohorts of interest (e.g., clinically diagnosed PD, non-manifest gene carriers, healthy controls, and prodromal)	Risk, Genetic profiling, Progression, Medication response	Yes
ILON portal	Asyn SAA (Alpha-synuclein Seed Amplification Assay) and DaTSCAN data subset of the PPMI	Risk, Genetic profiling	Yes
Verily Study Watch Data	Subset of the PPMI dataset. Smartwatch accelerometer data	Risk, Genetic profiling, Progression, Medication response	Yes
Swedish Biofinder	Several large, longitudinal, prospective cohorts of more than 1600 patients with mild cognitive symptoms, dementia and parkinsonian symptoms as well as cognitively healthy elderly. The subjects undergo examinations repeated bi-annually and including imaging MRI, CSF and plasma analysis, amyloid and tau PET, skin biopsies, detailed clinical assessments and neuropsychological examinations.	Risk, Progression, Medication response	No
UK Biobank	Extensive environmental, lifestyle, and genetic data on half a million participants, including HC, diagnosed PD and prodromal PD	Risk. Genetic profiling	Yes

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
NS-PARK	Observational and longitudinal multicenter study conducted in France. Data on demographics, diagnosis, motor and non-motor symptoms, and treatments and a baseline blood sample for genetic testing.	PD progression predictive modelling. Genetic profiling.	No
OPDC Discovery cohort	A prospective, longitudinal study that has recruited patients with early idiopathic PD, healthy controls and participants at risk of PD, and participants with RBD	Risk, Progression, Medication response	No
COPPADIS	N = 1000. Observational longitudinal (5y) study. Clinical and demographic data. Comparison with healthy controls (caregivers). Motor, non-motor symptoms (incl cognitive data, QoL), biochemistry and imaging data	Progression, Medication response	Yes
AMP-PD cohorts	Clinical and omics (transcriptomic, genomic, proteomic, and single nucleus brain data) data from eight unified cohorts (BioFIND, HBS, LBD, LCC, PDBP, PPMI, STEADY-PD3 and SURE-PD3) including over 10,000 participants.	Progression, Genetic profiling.	Yes
Fox Insight	Demographics, Imaging, Medical Cannabis use, Genetic	Genetic profiling	Yes
RBD-Czech	Actigraphic recording (MotionWatch, CamNtech Ltd.) and confirming polysomnographic recording. 45 RBD patients, 30 with other sleep related motor disorders, 20 Healthy subjects	Risk	Yes
IRBDSG	International RBD Study Group. No publication yet	Risk	Yes
PRESENCE	Phase 2 trial assessing response to symptomatic treatment of Lewy body dementia (LBD). 238 patients wore actigraphy for three 2-week periods daytime sleepiness was evaluated using the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS)	Progression, Medication Response	No
CIS-PD	Accelerometer data and severity scores for tremor, dyskinesias and ON/OFF medication status. Symptoms are reported through 30-minute interval reports	Progression, Medication response	Yes
REAL-PD IMU smartwatch data	Smartwatch accelerometer gyroscope data Smartphone accelerometer data	Progression, Medication response	Yes
MJFF Levodopa response study	Accelerometer data collected in the laboratory with ground truth labels of symptom severity during the performance of scripted motor tasks as well as wearable sensor data collected in the home setting during the performance of unscripted motor tasks.	Progression, Medication response	Yes
i-PROGNOSIS	Body tracking-based intelligent Motor Assessment Tests (iMAT) in accurately reflecting the motor skill status of PD patients. Keystroke timing and pressure	Progression, Medication response	Yes

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
	data that correspond to short text excerpts typed by early PD patients and healthy controls		
LIXIPARK	Data were collected in the framework of LIXIPARK, a multicenter, randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind, parallel-group study of lixisenatide in 156 patients with early PD. It was run at 21 centers of the French NS-Park/FCRIN network. Patients with early PD (< 3 years since diagnosis) on stable symptomatic medications and without motor complications were randomised to receive subcutaneous injections of placebo or 20 µg lixisenatide once daily for 12 months, followed by a 2-month wash-out period. The primary endpoint was the change from baseline to month-12 in the MDS-UPDRS part III (motor examination) score in the ON condition.	Progression, Medication response	No
LEAP clinical trial	Randomized double blind placebo controlled delayed start trial that assigned patients with early PD to receive levodopa or placebo for 40 weeks followed by levodopa (delayed-start group).	Medication response, Progression	No
PD-MED study	Pragmatic, open-label randomised trial, including de novo PD patients who were randomly assigned between levodopa-sparing therapy (dopamine agonists or MAOBI) and levodopa alone.	Medication response	No
Iceberg Cohort (France)	Observational, prospective, monocentric study to assess clinical features, imaging and biologic biomarkers PD patients and rate of progression compared to healthy controls and subjects at risk to develop (subjects with iRBD and subjects related to a patient with genetically confirmed PD).	Risk, Progression, medication response	No
RBDact	Home wrist actigraphy and PSG of patients.	Risk	No
NILS	Longitudinal study of PD patients baseline and follow up to 7 to 10 years	Progression, Medication response	No
KCH PKG data	Wearable device data contains values and percentiles of bradykiensia, imobility, sleep, dyskinesia and tremor	Progression, Medication response	No
Opisleep data	PD patients sleep data of PDSS, ESS daytime somnolence and demographic followup data of 20 patients	Progression, Medication response	Yes
BIAL dataset (pharma company)	Contains pseudonymized demographic and clinical data of patients from the BIPARK I (ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01568073) and the BIPARK-II (ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01227655) phase III trials.	Progression, Medication response	In progress
Capture24	Not PD specific. Contains 24 hour accelerometry data from 151 participants with annotated activity periods.	Progression, Medication response	Yes
NTD Dataset	A German cohort of approximately 260 PD patients with longitudinal follow-up of at least one year. Includes clinical, demographic, and medication data.	Progression, Medication response	Yes, but not useful

The data have been extracted by each data provider from their existing records and made available to project partners designated as joint controllers, in accordance with the terms set

out in a Data Processing Agreement (DPA), which ensures compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The use of retrospective data within the AI-PROGNOSIS project has been carried out in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and applicable national legislation. Only personal data deemed strictly necessary by the consortium for the achievement of the project's scientific objectives has been accessed or processed.

Specifically, in accordance with Article 5(1)(b) GDPR, personal data that has been lawfully collected for specified purposes must not be further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those original purposes. However, further processing for scientific research purposes is, by default, not considered incompatible, provided that appropriate safeguards – such as those described in Article 89(1)– are in place. Accordingly, the original legal basis for the initial collection remains valid for subsequent scientific processing, particularly under Article 9(2)(j) GDPR. From the aforementioned retrospective data, the data subjects are not identifiable, as all personally identifiable information has been removed in accordance with the principles of the GDPR. This ensures that the data cannot be attributed to any specific individual, either directly or indirectly, thereby reducing any associated privacy risks.

All retrospective data are securely stored and processed for the duration of the project on Hetzner, a trusted and GDPR-compliant cloud service provider, or on local secure infrastructure of partners, ensuring protection against unauthorised access, alteration, or loss.

All processing operations involving shared personal data are conducted in accordance with the GDPR principles of lawfulness, fairness and transparency, purpose limitation, and data minimisation. Adequate technical and organisational measures have been implemented to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the data.

Once the shared personal data is no longer required for the purposes of the project, the partners shall proceed with the irreversible deletion of the data from their systems.

5 Dataset harmonisation and curation

As healthcare systems generate vast volumes of heterogeneous data from diverse sources, ranging from clinical data to genomic sequences or time series, the need to harmonise this information becomes critical. Data harmonisation involves the processes of standardization, integration, and normalization, aimed at aligning disparate datasets into a coherent form. For the updated report D2.4, one dataset (NTD dataset) was initially explored but discarded because it did not contain key variables for the project. There haven't been any other updates during this time.

5.1 The process

The harmonisation process along with any preprocessing steps are extensively described in Section 5 of deliverable D2.3 and it remains the same for all datasets with minor amendments that may need to be done to meet the needs of each dataset that needs to be harmonized. Until the submission of D2.3 only the PPMI dataset had been fully harmonized. In the following section we will discuss the harmonization actions that took place for the rest of the datasets following the same procedures and action as with the PPMI.

5.2 From PPMI to the rest of datasets

Since PPMI was both the first available and the largest dataset in the project, the harmonization process was designed and implemented based on PPMI. This was a strategic choice performed under the assumption that smaller datasets could be pre-processed, transformed and harmonized more easily by a process fit for the larger dataset of the project where significant preprocessing was needed (temporary alignment, extensive mapping of variables, values and units etc.as described in D2.3). With that in mind, during the harmonization procedure for the rest of the retrospective, as well as prospective datasets, (NTD, mAI health dataset, dBM-DEV dataset etc.) the same standard concepts as with the PPMI were used as much as possible in order to ensure data accuracy and consistency across all datasets. For some cases where it was not possible to use the same standard concepts, i.e. because some information was not recorded in all datasets or that some information was recorded with similar but not exactly the same way, new custom vocabularies and concepts were defined per case.

5.3 Harmonisation method

As the process for the new datasets began, the harmonisation workflow, detailed in D.2.3 was extended into two phases. New special use cases also emerged, using PPMI as a foundation for developing a common data model.

5.3.1 Updated method

The first phase of the process involves the identification of relevant datasets, a task led by the model leaders in collaboration with clinical partners (**Figure 5**). Once the datasets are selected, the harmonization requirements are assessed, and the necessary adjustments are proposed to ensure alignment with the Common Data Model (CDM). After all variables of interest are finalized, the process moves into the second phase:the data harmonization stage (**Figure 6**).

Figure 5 Dataset Identification for data harmonisation

Figure 6 Harmonization Process

This phase begins with an in-depth exploration of the datasets to better understand their variables, address real-world data inconsistencies, and accommodate dataset-specific nuances. Once this initial analysis is complete, the appropriate OMOP CDM tables for each variable are determined. Mapping then begins using clinically validated variables and their

corresponding values, leveraging the Athena portal (OHDSI. (n.d.). *Athena: Search Terms*) for standardized terminology and concept matching. On the technical side, the harmonization process was implemented using Python and SQL and deployed on the project's Hetzner cloud infrastructure.

5.3.2 Special use cases

Throughout this process, several noteworthy challenges were encountered. These are discussed in detail in deliverable D3.2. For example, custom concepts had to be created for variables not covered by the standard OMOP vocabulary. In some instances, data aggregation was required in order to map information to existing OMOP concepts. Missing values were also addressed, and total scores were calculated for specific questionnaires.

A final challenge emerged after integrating the newly harmonized datasets. Since the PPMI dataset serves as the reference point, work is currently underway to determine the most effective approach for integrating the new variables and ensuring seamless interoperability across the datasets.

5.4 Retrospective data

Regarding the retrospective data aligned with PPMI, the harmonization and curation process has been initiated for the NTD dataset, but after an exploration, we're not proceeding with the NTD data because the MDS-UPDRS data, which contains key variables for the project, is missing. Also, in terms of the older UPDRS version, only total scores are available, while the individual item scores are missing.

The next dataset in line is COPPADIS, which is currently on hold until the variables of interest are defined followed by the other BIAL dataset, for which access is still pending.

5.5 Prospective data

On the prospective data side, there are two available datasets for which the harmonization and curation process can begin. Although no data have been collected yet, the variables of interest and their expected values have already been defined. Therefore, the initial phase of examining all harmonization requirements for these datasets can proceed. More detailed information about each of these is provided below.

5.5.1 mAI-Health app questionnaire

The purpose of the mai-Health Questionnaire is to collect information about risk factors for PD. The main factors examined were selected based on the "official" risk factors published by the Movement Disorder Society (Heinzel, S. et. Al., 2019). The primary goal is to collect this information as accurately as possible, in alignment with how it is described in the official documentation, since doctors and researchers use these specific terms when evaluating Parkinson's risk. Also, the chosen factors are relatively easy to assess through questionnaires and most of them were presented in PPMI study.

5.5.1.1 Questionnaire challenges

The initial version of the questionnaire includes 16 distinct questions, each related to risk factors associated with PD. Some of these questions are already available within the Athena portal, and the appropriate concept IDs have been identified. Two of the variables, however, are not currently included in the OMOP standard vocabulary, so custom concepts will need to be created for them.

One issue we encountered involves the variable on family history of PD. The mai-Health Questionnaire includes a single item covering family history, whereas the PPMI dataset

separates this information into two variables—one for the mother and one for the father. A proposed solution, is to combine these two variables in the PPMI dataset into a single unified variable in order to align with the structure of the questionnaire

Additionally, some variables in the questionnaire correspond to comorbidities found in the PPMI dataset but are structured differently. In the PPMI dataset, all comorbidities are captured within a single field using binary indicators (1 for presence, 0 for absence). In contrast, the questionnaire provides multiple response options: "Yes," "No," "Not sure," and "I prefer not to say." For the purposes of predictive modeling, only the "Yes" and "No" responses are assigned probability weights, while "Not sure" and "I prefer not to say" are treated as missing information. It is important to note that the absence of a response should not be interpreted as a "No." We are currently in discussions with the models' leaders to determine the most appropriate way to handle this discrepancy.

5.5.2 dBM-DEV study eCRFs

The dBM-DEV study clinical data collection include seven eCRFs (electronic Case Report Forms). More specifically:

- MDS-UPDRS
- Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)
- REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ)
- Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS)
- Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria
- Baseline Information
- Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire (PDQ-8)

Among the above eCRFs, the first four are already part of the PPMI study, so appropriate mapping to OMOP standards has already been developed for them. For the remaining three, the Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria and Baseline Information eCRFs contain non-standard scales that require additional attention, and some variables may not be relevant for mapping. Therefore, the final list of variables of interest is still pending. As for the PDQ-8 Questionnaire, it may need to be handled as a custom concept in order to fully align with the content of its variables. This dataset is still in progress, and so far, not many special cases have emerged.

6 Conclusions

This updated report provides a domain review regarding PD risk and PD progression and medication response within the framework of the AI-PROGNOSIS project considering the articles published in the past 12 years (1/1/2013-1/2/2025). It also provides the currently approved digital technologies used today as well as an overview of the third-party datasets that have been accessed and where they will be applied in the project along with harmonisation and curation techniques.

The key messages from this updated report are:

- The extensive review assessing PD risk and prodromal PD based on clinical, lifestyle and demographic factors, genetic markers, AI models and the digital tracking of two pre-motor symptoms: (daytime somnolence and RBD) provides the current SoA and the gaps in our current knowledge. The scarcity of studies investigating dBM that can efficiently detect RBD and daytime somnolence highlights the importance of our project. There is currently active discussion about how to biologically define, classify, and stage PD. The goal is to better characterize the early stages of the disease for

research by using biological markers like synuclein tests, genetic information, and neuroimaging. In these synuclein positive populations at risk of developing motor PD, dBMs may play a key role in defining prodromal symptoms such as RBD and daytime somnolence and thus aid in predicting phenotypic conversion to prodromal PD and motor PD. AI-driven approaches considering this data may help characterize the heterogeneity of PD prodromal states and thus allow for targeted intervention trials.

- The extensive review assessing PD progression and medication response considering lifestyle, demographic and clinical variables, genetic markers, AI-driven methodologies and digital assessments of motor symptoms such as tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, postural instability and side effects, such as dyskinesias, as well as cognitive decline, provides an updated background of our current knowledge and also points to the unmet needs and research opportunities in monitoring PD. Notably, there is a lack of knowledge and investigating tools that explore the interaction between disease progression and treatment beneficial effects and side effects, such as dyskinesias or hallucinations. AI-driven approaches hold the future of transforming our understanding of the complexities of PD as numerous amounts of data can be fed into the models to delineate dynamic PD subtypes.
- There are currently eleven FDA or CE approved digital technologies used to monitor PD, each with strengths and weaknesses that the AI-PROGNOSIS project will build on.
- Fifteen (one more in progress) multi-source datasets from AI-PROGNOSIS partners and third-party databases/biobanks/cohorts have been accessed by the project to date. Eight will be used for disease progression and medication response models, four for PD risk and prodromal PD models, two for genetic profiling models, and two for all these objectives.
- Data from different sources must be sanitised, debiased, munged and harmonised. The updated report describes the common data model to be used following established standards and clinical knowledge for the standardisation of representations of multi-site outcome assessments.

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